

Supplemental Data - Final results from a 90-day brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Final results from a 90-day quantitative inhalation toxicology study evaluating the dose-response and fate in the lung and pleura of chrysotile-containing brake dust compared to TiO₂, chrysotile, crocidolite or amosite asbestos: Histopathological examination, confocal microscopy and collagen quantification of the lung and pleural cavity. D.M. Bernstein, B. Toth, R.A. Rogers, D.E. Kling, P. Kunzendorf, J.I. Phillips, D. Schaudien

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S-1 Lung Weights

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Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 45 days:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	45 days				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	8.156				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.5088				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	2.209 (8, 63)				
P value	0.0383				
P value summary	*				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)	15.97				
P value	0.0429				
P value summary	*				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	0.1221	8	0.01526	F (8, 63) = 8.156	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	0.1179	63	0.001871		
Total	0.2400	71			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	72				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 45 days:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
1 vs. 2	0.02500	-0.03402 to 0.08402	No	ns	0.7925	B	2	
1 vs. 3	0.02000	-0.03902 to 0.07902	No	ns	0.9186	C	3	
1 vs. 4	0.03375	-0.02527 to 0.09277	No	ns	0.5027	D	4	
1 vs. 5	0.03375	-0.02527 to 0.09277	No	ns	0.5027	E	5	
1 vs. 6	-0.01625	-0.07527 to 0.04277	No	ns	0.9722	F	6	
1 vs. 7	-0.02500	-0.08402 to 0.03402	No	ns	0.7925	G	7	
1 vs. 8	-0.07500	-0.1340 to -0.01598	Yes	**	0.0066	H	8	
1 vs. 9	-0.07875	-0.1378 to -0.01973	Yes	**	0.0039	I	9	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
1 vs. 2	0.3875	0.3625	0.02500	0.02163	8	8	1.156	63
1 vs. 3	0.3875	0.3675	0.02000	0.02163	8	8	0.9246	63
1 vs. 4	0.3875	0.3538	0.03375	0.02163	8	8	1.560	63
1 vs. 5	0.3875	0.3538	0.03375	0.02163	8	8	1.560	63
1 vs. 6	0.3875	0.4038	-0.01625	0.02163	8	8	0.7513	63
1 vs. 7	0.3875	0.4125	-0.02500	0.02163	8	8	1.156	63
1 vs. 8	0.3875	0.4625	-0.07500	0.02163	8	8	3.467	63
1 vs. 9	0.3875	0.4663	-0.07875	0.02163	8	8	3.641	63

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 45 days:Mul. comp. CI plot

	Column means diff.		
	Mean	UpperLimit	LowerLimit
1 - 2	0.025	0.0840226161010143	-0.0340226161010143
1 - 3	0.02	0.0790226161010143	-0.0390226161010143
1 - 4	0.03375	0.0927726161010143	-0.0252726161010143
1 - 5	0.03375	0.0927726161010143	-0.0252726161010143
1 - 6	-0.01625	0.0427726161010143	-0.0752726161010143
1 - 7	-0.025	0.0340226161010143	-0.0840226161010143
1 - 8	-0.075	-0.0159773838989857	-0.134022616101014
1 - 9	-0.07875	-0.0197273838989857	-0.137772616101014

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 45 days:Descriptive statistics

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Number of values	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Minimum	0.3000	0.3000	0.3200	0.3300	0.3200	0.3600	0.4000	0.4000	0.4100
25% Percentile	0.4000	0.3000	0.3400	0.3400	0.3200	0.3650	0.4000	0.4000	0.4125
Median	0.4000	0.4000	0.3750	0.3500	0.3400	0.4150	0.4000	0.4500	0.4750
75% Percentile	0.4000	0.4000	0.3950	0.3700	0.3900	0.4350	0.4000	0.5000	0.5000
Maximum	0.4000	0.4000	0.4100	0.3800	0.4100	0.4400	0.5000	0.6000	0.5400
Mean	0.3875	0.3625	0.3675	0.3538	0.3538	0.4038	0.4125	0.4625	0.4663
Std. Deviation	0.03536	0.05175	0.03151	0.01768	0.03739	0.03292	0.03536	0.07440	0.04838
Std. Error of Mean	0.01250	0.01830	0.01114	0.006250	0.01322	0.01164	0.01250	0.02631	0.01711
Lower 95% CI	0.3579	0.3192	0.3412	0.3390	0.3225	0.3762	0.3829	0.4003	0.4258
Upper 95% CI	0.4171	0.4058	0.3938	0.3685	0.3850	0.4313	0.4421	0.5247	0.5067

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 89 days:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	89 days				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	9.596				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.5613				
Brown-Forsythe test					

F (DFn, DFd)	0.9557 (8, 60)				
P value	0.4788				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)	5.504				
P value	0.7025				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	0.09762	8	0.01220	F (8, 60) = 9.596	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	0.07630	60	0.001272		
Total	0.1739	68			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	69				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 89 days:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
1 vs. 2	0.05350	-0.0009533 to 0.1080	No	ns	0.0559	B	2	
1 vs. 3	0.03975	-0.01470 to 0.09420	No	ns	0.2317	C	3	
1 vs. 4	0.02975	-0.02470 to 0.08420	No	ns	0.5088	D	4	
1 vs. 5	0.04600	-0.008453 to 0.1005	No	ns	0.1271	E	5	
1 vs. 6	0.02350	-0.03095 to 0.07795	No	ns	0.7313	F	6	
1 vs. 7	0.02850	-0.02595 to 0.08295	No	ns	0.5520	G	7	
1 vs. 8	-0.05400	-0.1085 to 0.0004533	No	ns	0.0528	H	8	
1 vs. 9	-0.04650	-0.1010 to 0.007953	No	ns	0.1208	I	9	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
1 vs. 2	0.3860	0.3325	0.05350	0.02033	5	8	2.632	60
1 vs. 3	0.3860	0.3463	0.03975	0.02033	5	8	1.955	60
1 vs. 4	0.3860	0.3563	0.02975	0.02033	5	8	1.463	60
1 vs. 5	0.3860	0.3400	0.04600	0.02033	5	8	2.263	60
1 vs. 6	0.3860	0.3625	0.02350	0.02033	5	8	1.156	60
1 vs. 7	0.3860	0.3575	0.02850	0.02033	5	8	1.402	60
1 vs. 8	0.3860	0.4400	-0.05400	0.02033	5	8	2.656	60
1 vs. 9	0.3860	0.4325	-0.04650	0.02033	5	8	2.287	60

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 89 days:Mul. comp. CI plot

	Column means diff.		
	Mean	UpperLimit	LowerLimit
1 - 2	0.0535	0.107953294563756	-0.000953294563755619
1 - 3	0.03975	0.0942032945637556	-0.0147032945637556
1 - 4	0.02975	0.0842032945637556	-0.0247032945637556
1 - 5	0.046	0.100453294563756	-0.00845329456375557
1 - 6	0.0235	0.0779532945637556	-0.0309532945637556
1 - 7	0.0285	0.0829532945637556	-0.0259532945637556
1 - 8	-0.054	0.000453294563755618	-0.108453294563756
1 - 9	-0.0465	0.00795329456375563	-0.100953294563756

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 89 days:Descriptive statistics

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Number of values	5	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Minimum	0.3400	0.2900	0.2900	0.3000	0.2900	0.3300	0.3000	0.3900	0.3600
25% Percentile	0.3500	0.3025	0.3100	0.3225	0.3300	0.3325	0.3300	0.4200	0.3725
Median	0.4000	0.3350	0.3550	0.3650	0.3450	0.3650	0.3600	0.4400	0.4450
75% Percentile	0.4150	0.3500	0.3775	0.3900	0.3575	0.3900	0.3800	0.4575	0.4675
Maximum	0.4200	0.3900	0.4000	0.3900	0.3700	0.3900	0.4000	0.5000	0.5100

Mean	0.3860	0.3325	0.3463	0.3563	0.3400	0.3625	0.3575	0.4400	0.4325
Std. Deviation	0.03435	0.03240	0.03889	0.03623	0.02449	0.02765	0.03284	0.03251	0.05339
Std. Error of Mean	0.01536	0.01146	0.01375	0.01281	0.008660	0.009774	0.01161	0.01150	0.01887
Lower 95% CI	0.3433	0.3054	0.3137	0.3260	0.3195	0.3394	0.3300	0.4128	0.3879
Upper 95% CI	0.4287	0.3596	0.3788	0.3865	0.3605	0.3856	0.3850	0.4672	0.4771

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 180 days:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	180 days				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	10.15				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.5632				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	1.756 (8, 63)				
P value	0.1029				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)	12.73				
P value	0.1216				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	0.1064	8	0.01330	F (8, 63) = 10.15	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	0.08255	63	0.001310		
Total	0.1890	71			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	72				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 180 days:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
1 vs. 2	0.02000	-0.02939 to 0.06939	No	ns	0.8249	B	2	
1 vs. 3	0.02000	-0.02939 to 0.06939	No	ns	0.8249	C	3	
1 vs. 4	0.01500	-0.03439 to 0.06439	No	ns	0.9528	D	4	
1 vs. 5	0.006250	-0.04314 to 0.05564	No	ns	0.9995	E	5	
1 vs. 6	-0.03000	-0.07939 to 0.01939	No	ns	0.4365	F	6	
1 vs. 7	-0.003750	-0.05314 to 0.04564	No	ns	0.9997	G	7	
1 vs. 8	-0.05875	-0.1081 to -0.009362	Yes	*	0.0125	H	8	
1 vs. 9	-0.09875	-0.1481 to -0.04936	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	9	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
1 vs. 2	0.3000	0.2800	0.02000	0.01810	8	8	1.105	63
1 vs. 3	0.3000	0.2800	0.02000	0.01810	8	8	1.105	63
1 vs. 4	0.3000	0.2850	0.01500	0.01810	8	8	0.8288	63
1 vs. 5	0.3000	0.2938	0.006250	0.01810	8	8	0.3453	63
1 vs. 6	0.3000	0.3300	-0.03000	0.01810	8	8	1.658	63
1 vs. 7	0.3000	0.3038	-0.003750	0.01810	8	8	0.2072	63
1 vs. 8	0.3000	0.3588	-0.05875	0.01810	8	8	3.246	63
1 vs. 9	0.3000	0.3988	-0.09875	0.01810	8	8	5.456	63

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 180 days:Mul. comp. CI plot

	Column means diff.		
	Mean	UpperLimit	LowerLimit
1 - 2	0.02	0.069387846695335	-0.0293878466953351
1 - 3	0.02	0.069387846695335	-0.0293878466953351
1 - 4	0.015	0.064387846695335	-0.0343878466953351
1 - 5	0.0062499999999998	0.0556378466953351	-0.0431378466953351
1 - 6	-0.03	0.0193878466953351	-0.0793878466953351
1 - 7	-0.00375000000000003	0.0456378466953351	-0.0531378466953351
1 - 8	-0.05875	-0.00936215330466494	-0.108137846695335
1 - 9	-0.09875	-0.0493621533046649	-0.148137846695335

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 180 days:Descriptive statistics

	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Number of values	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8	8
Minimum	0.2500	0.2300	0.2000	0.2400	0.2600	0.2900	0.2700	0.2600	0.3600
25% Percentile	0.2725	0.2400	0.2375	0.2450	0.2725	0.2925	0.3000	0.3250	0.3750
Median	0.3050	0.2950	0.2800	0.2750	0.2900	0.3300	0.3000	0.3700	0.4100
75% Percentile	0.3275	0.3075	0.3275	0.3275	0.3175	0.3600	0.3200	0.3975	0.4175
Maximum	0.3400	0.3300	0.3400	0.3400	0.3300	0.3800	0.3200	0.4200	0.4200
Mean	0.3000	0.2800	0.2800	0.2850	0.2938	0.3300	0.3038	0.3588	0.3988
Std. Deviation	0.03117	0.03780	0.04957	0.04071	0.02504	0.03464	0.01685	0.05139	0.02295
Std. Error of Mean	0.01102	0.01336	0.01753	0.01439	0.008851	0.01225	0.005957	0.01817	0.008115
Lower 95% CI	0.2739	0.2484	0.2386	0.2510	0.2728	0.3010	0.2897	0.3158	0.3796
Upper 95% CI	0.3261	0.3116	0.3214	0.3190	0.3147	0.3590	0.3178	0.4017	0.4179

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 270 days:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	270 days				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	6.659				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.6636				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	1.815 (8, 27)				
P value	0.1180				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)	13.68				
P value	0.0905				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	0.02891	8	0.003613	F (8, 27) = 6.659	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	0.01465	27	0.0005426		
Total	0.04356	35			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	36				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 270 days:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							

Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
Group 1 vs. Group 2	-0.01500	-0.06171 to 0.03171	No	ns	0.9209	B	Group 2	
Group 1 vs. Group 3	0.01250	-0.03421 to 0.05921	No	ns	0.9682	C	Group 3	
Group 1 vs. Group 4	-0.01000	-0.05671 to 0.03671	No	ns	0.9914	D	Group 4	
Group 1 vs. Group 5	0.005000	-0.04171 to 0.05171	No	ns	0.9996	E	Group 5	
Group 1 vs. Group 6	-0.01500	-0.06171 to 0.03171	No	ns	0.9209	F	Group 6	
Group 1 vs. Group 7	-0.01000	-0.05671 to 0.03671	No	ns	0.9914	G	Group 7	
Group 1 vs. Group 8	-0.07750	-0.1242 to -0.03079	Yes	***	0.0005	H	Group 8	
Group 1 vs. Group 9	-0.06000	-0.1067 to -0.01329	Yes	**	0.0074	I	Group 9	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Group 1 vs. Group 2	0.3100	0.3250	-0.01500	0.01647	4	4	0.9107	27
Group 1 vs. Group 3	0.3100	0.2975	0.01250	0.01647	4	4	0.7589	27
Group 1 vs. Group 4	0.3100	0.3200	-0.01000	0.01647	4	4	0.6071	27
Group 1 vs. Group 5	0.3100	0.3050	0.005000	0.01647	4	4	0.3036	27
Group 1 vs. Group 6	0.3100	0.3250	-0.01500	0.01647	4	4	0.9107	27
Group 1 vs. Group 7	0.3100	0.3200	-0.01000	0.01647	4	4	0.6071	27
Group 1 vs. Group 8	0.3100	0.3875	-0.07750	0.01647	4	4	4.705	27
Group 1 vs. Group 9	0.3100	0.3700	-0.06000	0.01647	4	4	3.643	27

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 270 days:Descriptive statistics

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	Group 8	Group 9
Number of values	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Minimum	0.2900	0.3100	0.2500	0.3000	0.3000	0.3200	0.2900	0.3700	0.3500
25% Percentile	0.2925	0.3100	0.2575	0.3000	0.3000	0.3200	0.2950	0.3700	0.3550
Median	0.3050	0.3200	0.3000	0.3100	0.3050	0.3250	0.3150	0.3850	0.3700
75% Percentile	0.3325	0.3450	0.3350	0.3500	0.3100	0.3300	0.3500	0.4075	0.3850
Maximum	0.3400	0.3500	0.3400	0.3600	0.3100	0.3300	0.3600	0.4100	0.3900
Mean	0.3100	0.3250	0.2975	0.3200	0.3050	0.3250	0.3200	0.3875	0.3700
Std. Deviation	0.02160	0.01915	0.04031	0.02828	0.005774	0.005774	0.02944	0.02062	0.01633
Std. Error of Mean	0.01080	0.009574	0.02016	0.01414	0.002887	0.002887	0.01472	0.01031	0.008165
Lower 95% CI	0.2756	0.2945	0.2334	0.2750	0.2958	0.3158	0.2732	0.3547	0.3440
Upper 95% CI	0.3444	0.3555	0.3616	0.3650	0.3142	0.3342	0.3668	0.4203	0.3960

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 451 days:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	451 days				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	2.270				
P value	0.0560				
P value summary	ns				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	No				
R squared	0.4207				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	0.7650 (8, 25)				
P value	0.6361				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	0.02423	8	0.003029	F (8, 25) = 2.270	P=0.0560
Residual (within columns)	0.03336	25	0.001334		
Total	0.05759	33			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	34				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 451 days:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
Group 1 vs. Group 2	0.01167	-0.06811 to 0.09145	No	ns	0.9994	B	Group 2	
Group 1 vs. Group 3	0.02000	-0.05386 to 0.09386	No	ns	0.9665	C	Group 3	
Group 1 vs. Group 4	0.02500	-0.04886 to 0.09886	No	ns	0.9006	D	Group 4	
Group 1 vs. Group 5	0.005000	-0.06886 to 0.07886	No	ns	0.9997	E	Group 5	
Group 1 vs. Group 6	0.02250	-0.05136 to 0.09636	No	ns	0.9389	F	Group 6	
Group 1 vs. Group 7	0.04167	-0.03811 to 0.1214	No	ns	0.5676	G	Group 7	
Group 1 vs. Group 8	-0.02250	-0.09636 to 0.05136	No	ns	0.9389	H	Group 8	
Group 1 vs. Group 9	-0.05250	-0.1264 to 0.02136	No	ns	0.2551	I	Group 9	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Group 1 vs. Group 2	0.3150	0.3033	0.01167	0.02790	4	3	0.4182	25
Group 1 vs. Group 3	0.3150	0.2950	0.02000	0.02583	4	4	0.7743	25
Group 1 vs. Group 4	0.3150	0.2900	0.02500	0.02583	4	4	0.9679	25
Group 1 vs. Group 5	0.3150	0.3100	0.005000	0.02583	4	4	0.1936	25
Group 1 vs. Group 6	0.3150	0.2925	0.02250	0.02583	4	4	0.8711	25
Group 1 vs. Group 7	0.3150	0.2733	0.04167	0.02790	4	3	1.493	25
Group 1 vs. Group 8	0.3150	0.3375	-0.02250	0.02583	4	4	0.8711	25
Group 1 vs. Group 9	0.3150	0.3675	-0.05250	0.02583	4	4	2.033	25

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 451 days:Descriptive statistics

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	Group 8	Group 9
Number of values	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	4
Minimum	0.2400	0.2700	0.2800	0.2500	0.2800	0.2700	0.2400	0.3200	0.3400
25% Percentile	0.2550	0.2700	0.2825	0.2625	0.2800	0.2725	0.2400	0.3200	0.3475
Median	0.3100	0.2700	0.2900	0.3000	0.3100	0.2900	0.2700	0.3300	0.3700
75% Percentile	0.3800	0.3700	0.3125	0.3075	0.3400	0.3150	0.3100	0.3625	0.3850
Maximum	0.4000	0.3700	0.3200	0.3100	0.3400	0.3200	0.3100	0.3700	0.3900
Mean	0.3150	0.3033	0.2950	0.2900	0.3100	0.2925	0.2733	0.3375	0.3675
Std. Deviation	0.06608	0.05774	0.01732	0.02708	0.03464	0.02217	0.03512	0.02363	0.02062
Std. Error of Mean	0.03304	0.03333	0.008660	0.01354	0.01732	0.01109	0.02028	0.01181	0.01031
Lower 95% CI	0.2099	0.1599	0.2674	0.2469	0.2549	0.2572	0.1861	0.2999	0.3347
Upper 95% CI	0.4201	0.4468	0.3226	0.3331	0.3651	0.3278	0.3606	0.3751	0.4003

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 635 days:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	635 days				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	3.966				
P value	0.0053				
P value summary	**				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.6017				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	0.04253	8	0.005316	F (8, 21) = 3.966	P=0.0053
Residual (within columns)	0.02815		0.001340		

Total	0.07068	21			
Data summary		29			
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	30				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 635 days:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
Group 1 vs. Group 2	-0.02417	-0.1058 to 0.05749	No	ns	0.9475	B	Group 2	
Group 1 vs. Group 3	0.01583	-0.06583 to 0.09749	No	ns	0.9943	C	Group 3	
Group 1 vs. Group 4	-0.02500	-0.1006 to 0.05060	No	ns	0.9112	D	Group 4	
Group 1 vs. Group 5	0.002500	-0.07310 to 0.07810	No	ns	0.9999	E	Group 5	
Group 1 vs. Group 6	0.01250	-0.06310 to 0.08810	No	ns	0.9974	F	Group 6	
Group 1 vs. Group 7	0.01250	-0.1070 to 0.1320	No	ns	0.9996	G	Group 7	
Group 1 vs. Group 8	-0.04750	-0.1231 to 0.02810	No	ns	0.3736	H	Group 8	
Group 1 vs. Group 9	-0.1142	-0.1958 to -0.03251	Yes	**	0.0037	I	Group 9	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Group 1 vs. Group 2	0.3025	0.3267	-0.02417	0.02796	4	3	0.8642	21
Group 1 vs. Group 3	0.3025	0.2867	0.01583	0.02796	4	3	0.5662	21
Group 1 vs. Group 4	0.3025	0.3275	-0.02500	0.02589	4	4	0.9657	21
Group 1 vs. Group 5	0.3025	0.3000	0.002500	0.02589	4	4	0.09657	21
Group 1 vs. Group 6	0.3025	0.2900	0.01250	0.02589	4	4	0.4828	21
Group 1 vs. Group 7	0.3025	0.2900	0.01250	0.04093	4	1	0.3054	21
Group 1 vs. Group 8	0.3025	0.3500	-0.04750	0.02589	4	4	1.835	21
Group 1 vs. Group 9	0.3025	0.4167	-0.1142	0.02796	4	3	4.083	21

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 635 days:Descriptive statistics

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	Group 8	Group 9
Number of values	4	3	3	4	4	4	1	4	3
Minimum	0.2700	0.3100	0.2700	0.3000	0.2900	0.2600	0.2900	0.2800	0.3700
25% Percentile	0.2800	0.3100	0.2700	0.3050	0.2900	0.2675	0.2900	0.2925	0.3700
Median	0.3100	0.3100	0.2900	0.3250	0.2950	0.2900	0.2900	0.3550	0.3800
75% Percentile	0.3175	0.3600	0.3000	0.3525	0.3150	0.3125	0.2900	0.4025	0.5000
Maximum	0.3200	0.3600	0.3000	0.3600	0.3200	0.3200	0.2900	0.4100	0.5000
Mean	0.3025	0.3267	0.2867	0.3275	0.3000	0.2900	0.2900	0.3500	0.4167
Std. Deviation	0.02217	0.02887	0.01528	0.02500	0.01414	0.02449	0.000	0.05715	0.07234
Std. Error of Mean	0.01109	0.01667	0.008819	0.01250	0.007071	0.01225	0.000	0.02858	0.04177
Lower 95% CI	0.2672	0.2550	0.2487	0.2877	0.2775	0.2510		0.2591	0.2370
Upper 95% CI	0.3378	0.3984	0.3246	0.3673	0.3225	0.3290		0.4409	0.5964

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 741 days:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	741 days				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	4.450				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.1426				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	0.8817 (8, 214)				
P value	0.5327				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				

Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)	45.64				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	0.1025	8	0.01282	F (8, 214) = 4.450	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	0.6163	214	0.002880		
Total	0.7189	222			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	223				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 741 days:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
Group 1 vs. Group 2	0.002785	-0.03707 to 0.04264	No	ns	0.9997	B	Group 2	
Group 1 vs. Group 3	0.007970	-0.03189 to 0.04783	No	ns	0.9966	C	Group 3	
Group 1 vs. Group 4	-0.009900	-0.05094 to 0.03114	No	ns	0.9899	D	Group 4	
Group 1 vs. Group 5	-0.02276	-0.06227 to 0.01676	No	ns	0.5129	E	Group 5	
Group 1 vs. Group 6	-0.01471	-0.05493 to 0.02552	No	ns	0.8976	F	Group 6	
Group 1 vs. Group 7	-0.03283	-0.07432 to 0.008655	No	ns	0.1866	G	Group 7	
Group 1 vs. Group 8	-0.04430	-0.08681 to -0.001799	Yes	*	0.0368	H	Group 8	
Group 1 vs. Group 9	-0.06195	-0.1039 to -0.01997	Yes	***	0.0008	I	Group 9	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Group 1 vs. Group 2	0.2976	0.2948	0.002785	0.01490	25	27	0.1870	214
Group 1 vs. Group 3	0.2976	0.2896	0.007970	0.01490	25	27	0.5351	214
Group 1 vs. Group 4	0.2976	0.3075	-0.009900	0.01534	25	24	0.6455	214
Group 1 vs. Group 5	0.2976	0.3204	-0.02276	0.01477	25	28	1.541	214
Group 1 vs. Group 6	0.2976	0.3123	-0.01471	0.01503	25	26	0.9784	214
Group 1 vs. Group 7	0.2976	0.3304	-0.03283	0.01551	25	23	2.118	214
Group 1 vs. Group 8	0.2976	0.3419	-0.04430	0.01589	25	21	2.789	214
Group 1 vs. Group 9	0.2976	0.3595	-0.06195	0.01569	25	22	3.949	214

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 741 days:Descriptive statistics

	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	Group 8	Group 9
Number of values	25	27	27	24	28	26	23	21	22
Minimum	0.2100	0.2100	0.2100	0.2500	0.2600	0.2400	0.2600	0.2500	0.2600
25% Percentile	0.2700	0.2600	0.2600	0.2925	0.2825	0.2875	0.3000	0.2900	0.3200
Median	0.2900	0.2900	0.2800	0.3100	0.3100	0.3050	0.3300	0.3300	0.3500
75% Percentile	0.3250	0.3200	0.3100	0.3200	0.3375	0.3300	0.3600	0.3600	0.3925
Maximum	0.4500	0.4100	0.4800	0.3600	0.6400	0.4000	0.4100	0.7000	0.4800
Mean	0.2976	0.2948	0.2896	0.3075	0.3204	0.3123	0.3304	0.3419	0.3595
Std. Deviation	0.04746	0.04458	0.05177	0.02575	0.06973	0.04246	0.03649	0.09048	0.05178
Std. Error of Mean	0.009492	0.008580	0.009964	0.005256	0.01318	0.008326	0.007609	0.01974	0.01104
Lower 95% CI	0.2780	0.2772	0.2691	0.2966	0.2933	0.2952	0.3147	0.3007	0.3366
Upper 95% CI	0.3172	0.3125	0.3101	0.3184	0.3474	0.3295	0.3462	0.3831	0.3825

45 days

89 days

180 days

270 days

451 days

635 days

741 days

S-2 Histopathological findings by exposure group

Histopathology of the Respiratory Tract

The protocol organs included all respiratory tract organs, i.e. the nasal cavity, nasopharynx, larynx, trachea, lung and lung-associated lymph nodes. These organs/tissues were examined in all animals, i.e. 4 rats per group and necropsy subgroup. Additional organs/tissues were only examined if macroscopic findings were present.

S-2.1 45 day interim sacrifice

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

Lungs

a) Exposure-related findings

(Multi)focal very slight (minimal) alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden (Brake dust, Titanium-dioxide and Chrysotile groups) or fiber-laden (Crocidolite and Amosite groups) macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 4/4 rats each of group 2 (Brake dust low), 3 (Brake dust mid), 4 (Brake dust high), 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high) as well as in 3/4 rats of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; 1/4 rats: slight degree). And correspondingly, 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight) showed multifocal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. In group 1 (Clean air control), alveolar histiocytosis could not be observed. Very slight (multi)focal occurrence of multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells was seen in a single rat of group 7 (Chrysotile high) and in 3/4 and 4/4 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite), respectively.

(Multi)focal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was exclusively observed in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite, all very slight) and 9 (Amosite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight). The same was true for multifocal alveolar/interstitial (intra-septal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells, which occurred in all rats of group 8 (3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (all slight). The incidence of (multi)focal perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration ranged between 1/4 rats per group in all Brake dust groups and in the Chrysotile low group (all very slight), 2/4 rats per group in the Chrysotile high group (all very slight) and 4/4 rats per group in the Crocidolite and Amosite group (each 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight). In addition, a single rat of the Titanium-dioxide group showed focal very slight perivascular mononuclear cell infiltration and 1/4 rats of group 9 (Amosite) revealed focal very slight pleural (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration.

As a further exposure-related finding, focal or multifocal very slight microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 2/4 and 4/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), respectively, while all rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) revealed slight multifocal microgranulomas.

(Multi)focal adaptive bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was diagnosed as spontaneous finding in a single control animal (very slight), and as exposure-related finding in 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), 8 (Crocidolite; all slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight).

Multifocal very slight interstitial fibrosis was observed in all rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) only. In addition, single rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low), 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed very slight or slight focal pleural fibrosis.

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control), while all rats of group 2 – 4 (Brake dust low, -mid and -high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide) as well as 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) were scored with Wagner grade 2 (a few macrophages present within terminal bronchioles and alveoli). The remaining 2 animals of group 6 and all rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high) received Wagner grade 3 (bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia present and more conspicuous macrophages and inflammatory cells). Wagner grade 4 (presence of minimal interstitial fibrosis) was applied to 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) only.

b) Spontaneous findings

Further spontaneous findings included very slight or slight focal neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia and lymphoma/leukemia cell infiltration (s. below). These changes affected single animals of different groups.

LALN

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of single animals from group 2-6 and 9, (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages could be observed. In addition, the LALN of single or up to 2/4 rats of most of these groups revealed slight lymphoid hyperplasia.

Other organs

In a single animal of group 8 (Crocidolite; animal no.: 8002), a malignant lymphoma was diagnosed as the only neoplasm in the current sacrifice group. Lymphoma cell infiltrates were observed in the larynx, lung, LALN and nasal cavity, as well as in the macroscopically enlarged liver, iliac lymph node (lymph node, NOS) and spleen. This neoplasm is also considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment of the animal.

No findings at all could be observed in the nasopharynx.

In the larynx, single rats of 3 exposure groups showed spontaneous very slight to slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration. This finding was also observed in the trachea of 1/4 and 3/4 rats of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and 4 (Brake dust high), respectively.

S-2.2 89 day sacrifice

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

Lungs

a) Exposure-related findings

(Multi)focal very slight (minimal) alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden (Brake dust, Titanium-dioxide and Chrysotile groups) or fiber-laden (Crocidolite and Amosite groups) macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 4/4 rats each of group 2 (Brake dust low), 3 (Brake dust mid), 4 (Brake dust high), 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high) as well as in 3/4 rats of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; 1/4 rats: slight degree). Multifocal slight alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages was seen in all (4/4 rats each group) rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite), respectively, while 2/4 animals of group 1 (Clean air control) showed focal very slight or slight alveolar histiocytosis. In addition, single animals each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) revealed very slight multifocal accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages in the BALT (bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue).

(Multi)focal occurrence of multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells was observed in a single rat of group 7 (Chrysotile high; very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; all very slight) and 9 (Amosite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight).

(Multi)focal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was diagnosed in a single rat of group 7 (Chrysotile high; very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite, 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight). The incidence of very slight (multi)focal perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration ranged between 2/4 rats per group in group 2 (Brake dust low), 3 (Brake dust mid), 4 (Brake dust high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide), 3/4 rats per group each in group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high) and 4/4 animals per group each in group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite). Very slight (multi)focal alveolar/interstitial (intraseptal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells occurred in a single rat of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) and in 3/4 and 4/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), respectively, while all rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed alveolar/interstitial inflammatory cell infiltration at a slight degree of severity.

As a further exposure-related finding, multifocal very slight microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 4/4 rats each of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), while all rats (4/4 each group) of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) revealed slight multifocal microgranulomas.

(Multi)focal very slight adaptive bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was observed as exposure-related finding in single animals each of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and 4 (Brake dust high) and in 4/4 rats each of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), while 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed this change at a slight degree of severity.

Multifocal interstitial fibrosis was seen in 2/4 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight). In addition, a single rat of group 9 (Amosite) showed very slight focal pleural fibrosis.

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control), while all rats of group 2 – 4 (Brake dust low, -mid and -high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide) were scored with Wagner grade 2. Wagner grade 3 was applied to all rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and to 2/4 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high). The remaining 2 animals of group 7 (Chrysotile high) as well as all rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) received Wagner grade 4.

b) Spontaneous findings

Incidental findings included very slight focal alveolar hemorrhage in a single control animal and very slight or slight focal neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia in single rats each of group 4 (Brake dust high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide).

LALN

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of up to 3/4 animals per group from nearly all particle- or fiber-exposure groups, (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages could be observed. In addition, the LALN of single or up to 2/4 rats of some of these groups revealed slight lymphoid hyperplasia.

Other organs

No findings at all could be observed in the nasopharynx.

In the larynx, single or up to 2/4 rats of some exposure groups showed very slight to slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell or (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration. Very slight or slight focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration was also observed in the trachea of single rats of group 1 (Clean Air Control) and group 8 (Crocidolite).

In the nasal cavity, a single rat of group 9 (Amosite) revealed multifocal very slight hyaline (eosinophilic) droplets of the olfactory epithelium.

All these findings were considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to particle- or fiber-exposure.

S-2.3 3 months postexposure sacrifice

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

Lungs

a) Exposure-related findings

Multifocal very slight (minimal) alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 4/4 rats each of group 2 (Brake dust low), 3 (Brake dust mid), 4 (Brake dust high), 5 (Titanium-dioxide), 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), while 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed multifocal slight alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. Spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregation (alveolar histiocytosis) was diagnosed in a single control animal (group 1). The incidences of (multi)focal very slight to slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages in the BALT (bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue) were increased as compared to the previous sacrifices: 2/4 each (group 2 and 4), 3/4 (group 3) and 4/4 each (group 5 - 9). Multifocal multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells were observed exclusively in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight).

(Multi)focal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was diagnosed in a single rat of group 7 (Chrysotile high; very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite, 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight). The incidences of (multi)focal perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration were 3/4 in group 2 (2/4 very slight, 1/4 slight), 2/4 each in group 4 (all very slight) and group 7 (1/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 4/4 each in group 6 (all very slight), 8 (1/4 very slight, 3/4 slight) and 9 (2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight), respectively. Very slight (multi)focal alveolar/interstitial (intra-septal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells occurred in 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and in 4/4 animals of group 7 (Chrysotile high), while all rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed alveolar/interstitial inflammatory cell infiltration at a slight degree of severity. In addition, single animals of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and 7 (Chrysotile high) showed very slight focal pleural (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration.

As a further exposure-related finding, multifocal very slight microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 3/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and in 4/4 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high). All rats (4/4 each group) of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) revealed slight multifocal microgranulomas.

(Multi)focal very slight bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was observed in single animals each of group 1 (Clean air control) and 5 (Titanium dioxide), in 2/4 males of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and in 4/4 rats each of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), while 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed this change at a slight degree of severity.

(Multi)focal interstitial fibrosis was seen in a single male of group 2 (Brake dust low; very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), 8 (Crocidolite; all slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight), respectively.

In addition, single rats of group 2 (Brake dust low), 5 (Titanium dioxide), 7 (Chrysotile high) and 8 (Crocidolite), as well as 2/4 males of group 9 (Amosite) showed very slight focal pleural fibrosis.

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control), while all rats of group 2 – 4 (Brake dust low, -mid and -high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide) were scored with Wagner grade 2. Wagner grade 3 was applied to all rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), while all rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite), respectively, received Wagner grade 4.

b) Spontaneous findings

A single rat of group 3 (Brake dust mid) showed slight focal neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia as a further incidental finding.

LALN

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of 2/4 to 4/4 animals per group from the particle-exposure groups 2-7, (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle-laden macrophages could be observed, while 4/4 rats each of the fiber-exposure groups 8 (Crocidolite; all slight) and 9 (Amosite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight), respectively, revealed (multi)focal accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. In addition, the LALN of single or up to 2/4 rats of some of these groups revealed slight lymphoid hyperplasia.

Other organs

No findings at all could be observed in the nasopharynx.

In the larynx, single or up to 2/4 rats of the control group and some exposure groups showed very slight to slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell or (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration. In addition, single animals of some groups revealed (multi)focal very slight to slight subepithelial (agonal) hemorrhage.

In the nasal cavity, up to 3/4 rats per group showed multifocal very slight to slight (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the respiratory and/or olfactory epithelium. The incidence of this age-related change was increased as compared to the previous examination subsets. In addition, single rats of some groups showed very slight focal mucous cell hyperplasia, slight hyperplasia of the NALT (nasal mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue) and (multifocal) very slight subepithelial (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration.

In the trachea, single animals of most groups revealed very slight focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration.

As a correlate to macroscopic observations, control animal no. 1021 showed a severe diffuse purulent (suppurative) inflammation of the prostate and rat no. 4023 (Brake dust high) was affected by a severe focal subcutaneous abscess.

All these findings were considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment.

S-2.4 6 months postexposure sacrifice

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

Lungs

a) Exposure-related findings

(Multi)focal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 3/4 rats of group 2 (Brake dust low; all very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 3 (Brake dust mid; all very slight), 4 (Brake dust high; all very slight), 5 (Titanium-dioxide; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight), 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight) and 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), while 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 1/4 very slight, 3/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight) showed multifocal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. There was no occurrence of spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregation (alveolar histiocytosis) in the clean air control group (group 1). The incidences of (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages in the BALT (bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue) were 1/4 each in group 2 and 3, 3/4 each in group 4 and 5, and 4/4 each in group 6 - 9. Multifocal multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells were exclusively observed in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight).

Multifocal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was diagnosed in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite, 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight) only. The incidences of (multi)focal very slight perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration were 1/4 each in group 2 - 5 (all very slight), 3/4 in group 7 (all very slight) and 4/4 each in group 6 (2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight), 8 (all very slight) and 9 (2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight), respectively. (Multi)focal alveolar/interstitial (intra-septal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells occurred in 2/4 rats of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; all very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight), 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), 8 (Crocidolite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight). In addition, single animals of group 1 (Clean air control) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide) showed very slight focal interstitial or pleural (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration.

As a further exposure-related finding, multifocal very slight microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and in 4/4 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high). All rats (4/4 each group) of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) revealed slight multifocal microgranulomas.

(Multi)focal very slight bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was observed in single animals each of group 2 (Brake dust low), 4 (Brake dust high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide), as well as in 2/4 males of group 3 (Brake dust mid). In group 6 (Chrysotile low; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight), 7 (Chrysotile high; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight), 8 (Crocidolite; all slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight), 4/4 rats each were affected by this change at a very slight to slight degree of severity.

Multifocal interstitial fibrosis was seen in a single male of group 6 (Chrysotile low; very slight)

and in 4/4 rats each of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), 8 (Crocidolite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight), respectively. In addition, 2/4 males of group 9 (Amosite) showed very slight or slight focal pleural fibrosis.

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control) and to 1/4 males of group 2 (Brake dust low), while 3/4 rats each of group 2 and 5 (Titanium-dioxide), as well as 4/4 rats each of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and 4 (Brake high) were scored with Wagner grade 2. Wagner grade 3 was applied to a single rat of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) and to 3/4 and 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), respectively. All rats from group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) as well as 1/4 and 2/4 animals of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), respectively, received Wagner grade 4.

b) Spontaneous findings

Single rats each of group 3 (Brake dust mid), 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) showed slight focal chondro-osseous metaplasia as an incidental finding.

LALN

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of 1/4 to 4/4 animals per group from the particle-exposure groups 2-7, (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle-laden macrophages could be observed, while 4/4 rats each of the fiber-exposure groups 8 (Crocidolite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) revealed multifocal accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. In addition, the LALN of single or up to 2/4 rats of some of these groups revealed slight lymphoid hyperplasia.

Other organs

No findings at all could be observed in the nasopharynx.

In the larynx, single or up to 2/4 rats of the control group and some exposure groups showed very slight to slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration. In addition, up to 2/4 rats of two groups revealed focal slight subepithelial (agonal) hemorrhage and a single rat of group 2 (Brake dust low) showed slight focal dilatation of the submucosal glands.

In the nasal cavity, single rats of the control, Brake dust mid and both Chrysotile groups as well as 3/4 and 2/4 rats of the Crocidolite and Amosite exposure groups, respectively, showed multifocal very slight to slight (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the olfactory epithelium. Very slight multifocal (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the respiratory epithelium were only observed in 2/4 animals of group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite). In addition, single rats of some groups showed very slight focal corpora amylacea within the olfactory epithelium, (multi)focal very slight to slight mucous cell hyperplasia and focal very slight subepithelial (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration. Slight hyperplasia of the NALT (nasal mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue) was observed in single animals of most particle-exposure groups and in 3/4 rats of group 9 (Amosite).

In the trachea, single animals of different groups revealed very slight or slight focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration.

All these findings were considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment.

S-2.5 12 months postexposure sacrifice

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

Lungs

a) Exposure-related findings

(Multi)focal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 1/3 rats of group 2 (Brake dust low; very slight) and in 3/4 rats each of group 3 (Brake dust mid; all very slight), 4/4 rats of group 4 (Brake dust high; all very slight), 5 (Titanium-dioxide; all very slight), 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight) and in 3/3 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), while 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; all slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight) showed multifocal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. One animal of the clean air control group (group 1), group 2 and group 3 showed spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregation (alveolar

histiocytosis). The incidences of (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages in the BALT (bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue) were 2/3 in group 2, 4/4 each in group 3 and 5, 3/4 each in group 4 and 9, 2/4 each in group 6 and 8, and 3/3 in group 7. Multifocal multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells were exclusively observed in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; all very slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight).

Multifocal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was diagnosed in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) only. The incidences of (multi)focal very slight perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration were 1/4 each in group 4 and 6 (all very slight) and 4/4 each in group 8 and 9 (all very slight), respectively. (Multi)focal alveolar/interstitial (intra-septal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells occurred in 1/4 rats of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; very slight), in 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight) and in 2/3 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), and in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 1/4 very slight, 3/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight).

As a further exposure-related finding, multifocal microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 1/3 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high; very slight) and in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight).

(Multi)focal very slight bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was observed in a single animal of group 3 (Brake dust mid) and in 2/4 rats of group 4 (Brake dust high) as well as in 4/4 males of group 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight) and in 2/3 animals of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight). All animals, 4/4 rats each, were affected by this change of group 8 (Crocidolite; 1/4 very slight, 3/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight).

In one animal of group 8 (Crocidolite) a multifocal slight bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia of the alveolar type (hyperplasia of pneumocytes type 2) was seen.

Multifocal interstitial fibrosis was seen in a single male of group 6 (Chrysotile low; very slight) and 7 (Chrysotile high; very slight), as well as in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 1/4 very slight, 3/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; all slight). In addition, 2/4 males of group 9 (Amosite) showed very slight or slight focal pleural fibrosis.

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control), to 2/3 males of group 2 (Brake dust low) and to 1/4 males of group 3 (Brake dust mid). One animal of group 2 (Brake dust low), 3/4 animals of group 3 (Brake dust mid), 4/4 animals each of group 4 (Brake dust high) and 5 (Titanium-dioxide), 2/4 animals of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 1/3 animals of group 7 (Chrysotile high) were scored with Wagner grade 2. Wagner grade 3 was applied to 2/4 and 2/3 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 7 (Chrysotile high), respectively. All rats from group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) received Wagner grade 4.

Many animals of all groups showed macroscopically few to many pale foci in all lung lobes. This change can be correlated in most cases to alveolar macrophage aggregation or accumulation of particle-/fibre-laden macrophages.

b) Spontaneous findings

A single rat of group 2 (Brake dust low) showed slight focal neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia as an incidental finding.

LALN

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of 3/4 to 4/4 or 3/3 animals per group from the particle-exposure groups 3-5 or 7, (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle-laden macrophages could be observed with one animal of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) showing this lesion to a slight extent. All animals, 4/4 rats, each of the fiber-exposure groups 8 (Crocidolite; 2/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 9 (Amosite; 3/4 very slight, 1/4 slight) revealed multifocal accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. In addition, the LALN of single or up to 2/4 rats of some of these groups revealed slight lymphoid hyperplasia.

Other organs

No findings at all could be observed in the nasopharynx.

In the larynx, single or up to 2/4 rats of the control group and some exposure groups showed very slight to slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration. In addition, single rats of the control group and most exposure groups showed very slight to slight focal dilatation of the submucosal glands.

In the nasal cavity, single to all rats of the different groups showed multifocal very slight to moderate (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the olfactory epithelium. Very slight multifocal (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the respiratory epithelium were observed in single animals of many groups. In addition, single rats of some groups showed very slight focal corpora amylacea within the olfactory epithelium, (multi)focal very slight to slight mucous cell hyperplasia, focal very slight to slight subepithelial (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration and slight hyperplasia of the NALT (nasal mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue).

In the trachea, single animals of different groups revealed very slight or slight focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration.

All these findings were considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment.

One animal of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) showed macroscopically a firm nodule at the tail, which was histologically diagnosed as subcutaneous abscess with overlying serocellular crust.

One animal of group 6 (Chrysotile low) showed macroscopically a single pale mass in the lumbar region, which was diagnosed as benign hair follicle tumor of the pilomatricoma type. The same animal exhibited an enlargement of the lung-associated lymph nodes, which was diagnosed as malignant thymoma.

S-2.6 18 months postexposure sacrifice

The following animals suffered from an unscheduled death/necropsy prior to the 18 months post exposure time point and were therefore not included in the 18 months post exposure time point investigation. These animals had the number: 2061, 3061, 7060, 7062, 7063 and 9061.

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

Lungs

a) Exposure-related findings

(Multi)focal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 1/3 rats of group 2 (Brake dust low; very slight), in 2/3 rats of group 3 (Brake dust mid; all very slight), in 4/4 rats of group 4 (Brake dust high; all very slight), 5 (Titanium-dioxide; all very slight), 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight) and in 1/1 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), while 4/4 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite; 1/4 very slight; 3/4 slight) and 3/3 rats of

group 9 (Amosite; all slight) showed multifocal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. Three animals (two animals very slight; one animal slight) each of the clean air control group (group 1) and group 2, and one animal each of group 3 (slight), group 4 (slight) and group 6 (very slight) showed spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregation (alveolar histiocytosis). The incidences of (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages in the BALT (bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue) were 1/3 in group 3, 3/4 in group 4, 4/4 in group 5, 1/4 in group 6, 1/1 in group 7, 3/4 in group 8 and 2/3 in group 9. Multifocal multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells were exclusively observed in 4/4 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite; all very slight) and in 3/3 rats of group 9 (Amosite; 1/3 very slight; 2/3 slight).

Multifocal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was diagnosed only in 4/4 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite; all very slight) and in 3/3 rats of group 9 (Amosite; all slight). The incidences of (multi)focal very slight perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration were 1/4 in group 4 (very slight) and 4/4 in group 8 (all very slight) and 3/3 in group 9 (all very slight). (Multi)focal alveolar/interstitial (intra-septal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells occurred in 1/4 rats of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; very slight), in 1/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low; very slight), and in 4/4 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite; all very slight) and in 3/3 rats of group 9 (Amosite; all slight).

As a further exposure-related finding, multifocal microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 4/4 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite; all very slight) and in 3/3 rats of group 9 (Amosite; 1/3 very slight, 2/3 slight).

A single animal of group 9 (Amosite) exhibited a multifocal slight alveolar lipoproteinosis. The intra-alveolar lipoproteinaceous material was mainly granular and eosinophilic reflecting basically an origin from degenerating macrophages.

(Multi)focal very slight bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was observed in a single animal of group 2 (Brake dust low), group 4 (Brake dust high) and group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) as well as in 2/4 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight), in 1/1 animal of group 7 (Chrysotile high; very slight), in 4/4 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite; 1/4 very slight, 3/4 slight) and in 3/3 animals of group 9 (Amosite; all slight). In one animal of group 8 (animal 8060) and in one animal of group 9 (animal 9060) a focal very severe bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia of the alveolar type with atypia (hyperplasia of pneumocytes type 2) were observed.

In one animal of group 1 (Clean air control) a focal slight bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia of the alveolar type (hyperplasia of pneumocytes type 2) concurrent with an alveolar macrophage aggregation and a chronic inflammation was seen.

Multifocal interstitial fibrosis was seen in 4/4 rats each of group 8 (Crocidolite; 1/4 very slight, 3/4 slight) and in 3/3 animals of group 9 (Amosite; all slight).

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control), to 2/3 males of group 2 (Brake dust low) and to 1/3 males of group 3 (Brake dust mid). One animal of group 2 (Brake dust low), 2/3 animals of group 3 (Brake dust mid), 4/4 animals each of group 4 (Brake dust high), 5 (Titanium-dioxide) and group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 1/1 animal of group 7 (Chrysotile high) were scored with Wagner grade 2. All rats investigated from group 8 (Crocidolite) and 9 (Amosite) received Wagner grade 4.

Many animals of all groups showed macroscopically few to many pale foci in all lung lobes. This change can be correlated in most cases to alveolar macrophage aggregation or accumulation of particle-/fibre-laden macrophages. Furthermore, the macroscopic changes observed in the lung of animals 8060 and 9060 were diagnosed as focal very severe bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia of the alveolar type with atypia (see above).

b) Spontaneous findings

Single rats each of group 1 (Clean air control; very slight), group 2 (Brake dust low; very slight) and group 6 (Chrysotile low; slight) as well as two animals of group 4 (Brake dust high) showed an interstitial mononuclear cell infiltration as an incidental finding.

Single rats each of group 1 (Clean air control), group 4 (Brake dust high) and group 6 (Chrysotile low) had a very slight (multi)focal chronic inflammation concurrent with alveolar macrophage aggregation as an incidental finding.

A single rat of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) showed slight multifocal foreign-body granulomas probably due to inhalation of bedding material as an incidental finding.

A single rat of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) showed slight focal neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia as an incidental finding.

Single rats each of group 1 (Clean air control; very slight), group 3 (Brake dust mid; very slight), group 4 (Brake dust high; slight), group 6 (Chrysotile low; very slight), and 9 (Amosite; very slight) showed slight (multi)focal chondro-osseous metaplasia as an incidental finding.

LALN

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of 2/3, 4/4 and 3/4 animals from the particle-exposure groups 3, 4 and 5, respectively, a (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle-laden macrophages could be observed with one animal of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) showing this lesion to a slight extent. The LALN of 3/4 rats of the fiber-exposure group 8 (Crocidolite; 1/4 very slight, 2/4 slight) and 3/3 rats of the group 9 (Amosite; 1/3 very slight, 2/3 slight) revealed multifocal accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages.

Other organs of the respiratory tract

No findings at all could be observed in the nasopharynx.

In the larynx, single or up to 3/4 rats of the control group and some exposure groups showed very slight to slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration. In addition, single rats of the control group and group 3 (Brake dust mid) and 2/4 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite) showed very slight focal dilatation of the submucosal glands. A single animal of the clean air control group exhibited a focal slight, inflammatory cell infiltration.

In the nasal cavity, single to all rats of the different groups showed multifocal very slight to severe (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the olfactory epithelium. Very slight to slight multifocal (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the respiratory epithelium were observed in single up to 3 animals of some groups. In addition, single rats of some groups showed (multi)focal very slight mucous cell hyperplasia, (multi)focal very slight subepithelial (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration and slight hyperplasia of the NALT (nasal mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue).

In the trachea, single animals up to two animals of different groups revealed very slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration.

All these findings were considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment.

Histologically investigated macroscopic lesions

One animal (#1061) of group 1 (Clean air control) showed macroscopically a single mass at the hind paw, which was histologically diagnosed as focal severe ulcerated chronic-active inflammation. Another animal (#1062) of group 1 (Clean air control) had a single wound at the right flank, which was histologically diagnosed as focal slight laceration with a moderate subcutaneous hemorrhage. Another animal (#1063) of group 1 (Clean air control) exhibited a single mass at the right hind paw, which was diagnosed as focal slight chronic-active inflammation. This animal showed also an enlargement of the pituitary gland being histological an adenoma of the pars distalis.

One animal (#2062) of group 2 (Brake dust low) had a single mass in the left medial lobe of the liver. This was diagnosed histologically as a hepatocellular adenoma.

One animal (#3062) of group 3 (Brake dust mid) showed a cysts of the pituitary gland being histological an adenoma of the pars distalis. The kidneys of the same animal were bilaterally multifocal pale, which was histological a bilateral slight multifocal chronic-progressive nephropathy. In addition, the testes of this animal were bilaterally reduced in size. This represented a severe diffuse tubular atrophy.

One animal (#4062) of group 4 (Brake dust high) showed an enlargement of the right thyroid gland, which was diagnosed as a follicular cell carcinoma.

One animal (#6060) of group 6 (Chrysotile low) exhibited an enlargement of the lung-associated lymph nodes, which was diagnosed as malignant thymoma.

One animal (#8060) of group 8 showed an enlargement of the right testis, which was diagnosed as an Interstitial (Leydig) cell adenoma. The contralateral left side was reduced in size, which was histologically diagnosed as a multifocal very slight tubular atrophy. The epididymis of the right side of the same animal was reduced in size being histological a very severe luminal reduction of sperm. In addition, the seminal vesicles were bilaterally reduced in size with a histologically diagnosed bilateral slight diffuse atrophy. Furthermore, the liver of this animal had a pale single focus in the left lateral lobe. This represented histologically a basophilic focus of cellular alteration.

S-2.7 24 months postexposure sacrifice

Due to increased numbers of preterminal deaths, animals assigned for the final sacrifices time point were reassigned to the 24 month time point. Further, animals previously assigned to the 24 months low temperature microscopy and lung burden evaluation were investigated as well. Therefore the investigation of this time point included animals of group 1 to 9 with the animals numbers x070 – x073, x080 – x098, x170 – x173 as well as x270 – x273. In summary all groups consisted of 31 animals at this time point. The following animals suffered from an unscheduled death/necropsy prior to the 24 months post exposure time point. These animals had the number: 1083, 1085, 1087, 1090, 1091, 1092, 1273, 2071, 2085, 2170, 2171, 3072, 3073, 3081,

3084, 4071, 4082, 4087, 4088, 4089, 4092, 4170, 4172, 5080, 5089, 5091, 5272, 5273, 6070, 6089, 6093, 6097, 6098, 6170, 6173, 7070, 7080, 7088, 7089, 7092, 7094, 7095, 7097, 7272, 8071, 8072, 8080, 8086, 8088, 8092, 8093, 8173, 8271, 8273, 9070, 9082, 9083, 9084, 9086, 9089, 9093, 9095, 9170, 9273. However, these animals were included in this investigation.

Exposure-related findings were observed in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN).

S-2.7.1 Lungs

S-2.7.1.1 a) Neoplastic findings

Tumors within the lung were detected in the groups clean air (one tumor), brake dust high (one tumor), titanium dioxide (one tumor), Chrysotile low (one tumor), Crocidolite (five tumors), and Amosite (nine tumors). These consisted of malignant tumors in one animal of group brake dust high (this animal had two bronchiolo-alveolar carcinomas), one malignant tumor in group titanium dioxide (bronchiolo-alveolar carcinoma), three malignant tumors in group Crocidolite (all bronchiolo-alveolar carcinomas), and four malignant tumors in group Amosite (three bronchiolo-alveolar carcinomas and one adenocarcinoma) and benign bronchiolo-alveolar adenomas in group clean air (one adenoma), Chrysotile low (one adenoma), Crocidolite (one adenoma and one adenoma with atypia), and Amosite (four adenomas and one adenoma with atypia). In addition, there were preneoplastic bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasias of the alveolar type with atypia (hyperplasia of pneumocytes type 2) in the groups clean air (one), brake dust low (one), brake dust high (two), Chrysotile high (one), Crocidolite (four), and Amosite (three). One of the three animals of the Amosite group with the bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasias of the alveolar type with atypia had two of these lesions. Bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasias of the alveolar type without atypia (hyperplasia of pneumocytes type 2) were observed in the groups clean air (one), brake dust low (five), brake dust mid (one), brake dust high (four), titanium dioxide (three), Chrysotile low (four), Chrysotile high (seven), Crocidolite (eight), and Amosite (six). Bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasias of the alveolar type were only diagnosed if they were not correlated to spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregation.

Bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasias of the bronchiolar type (bronchiolization) were diagnosed as “hyperplasia, bronchiolo-alveolar”. This findings is interpreted to be an adaptive change and is discussed in the next chapter.

Metastases into the lung of primary tumors outside the respiratory tract were seen in one animal of group 1 (clean air; carcinoma of the thyroid gland), one animal of group 2 (brake dust low; carcinoma of the thyroid gland), in one animal of group 9 (Amosite; carcinoma of the adrenal gland), and in one animal of group 9 (Amosite; carcinoma of the liver). In one animal of group 4 (brake dust high) metastases from an organ outside the respiratory tract were detected, of which the origin remained unknown (primary site unknown) since no malignant tumor was seen on the slides provided. One animal of group 4 (brake dust high) showed an infiltration of the lung by lymphoma cells. The metastases and the lymphoma were interpreted to be incidental without any relation to the treatment.

S-2.7.1.2 b) Macroscopically suspected visceral pleural lesions in the lung

Within the animals 8070, 8073, 8082, 8097, 9071, 9073, 9080, 9085, 9087, 9090, 9092, 9094, 9096, 9097, 9098, and 9171 macroscopically changes of the lung were suspected to be visceral pleural lesions. The macroscopic changes correlated with bronchiolo-alveolar carcinoma, bronchiolo-alveolar adenoma or bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar type with atypia) in the lung parenchyma. The lesions in the overlying lung visceral pleura consisted of (multi)focal very slight to slight mesothelial (visceral pleural) hyperplasias and/or pleural fibrosis.

One animal, animal 9097, showed an adhesion of the lung pleura to the thoracic wall. All of these pleural lesions were interpreted to be a consequence of the respective lung parenchymal lesions. Further, due to the mild extent (very slight to slight) of the pleural lesions, they were unlikely to have caused the macroscopically visible changes alone.

S-2.7.1.3 c) Exposure-related findings

(Multi)focal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of particle-laden macrophages (alveolar histiocytosis / increased alveolar macrophages), predominantly at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions, was observed in 3/31 rats of group 2 (Brake dust low; all very slight), in 10/31 rats of group 3 (Brake dust mid; all very slight), in 22/31 rats of group 4 (Brake dust high; 20 very slight; 2 slight), in 24/31 of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; 24 very slight; 1 slight), in 19/31 of group 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight) and in 22/31 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high; all very slight), while 29/31 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite; 21/31 very slight; 8/31 slight) and 29/31 rats of group 9 (Amosite; 18/31 very slight; 11/31 slight) showed multifocal alveolar/interstitial accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages. Spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregation (alveolar histiocytosis / increased alveolar macrophages) was seen in 22/31 animals (14/31 very slight; 9/31 slight; 1/31 moderate) of the clean air control group (group 1), in 21/31 animals (12/31 very slight; 8/31 slight; 1/31 moderate) of group 2, in 23/31 animals (15/31 very slight; 6/31 slight; 2/31 moderate) of group 3, in 22/31 animals (13/31 very slight; 9/31 slight) of group 4, in 16/31 animals (15/31 very slight; 1/31 slight) of group 5, in 20/31 animals (7/31 very slight; 12/31 slight; 1/31 moderate) of group 6, in 18/31 animals (8/31 very slight; 10/31 slight) of group 7, in 12/31 animals (8/31 very slight; 4/31 slight) of group 8, and in 10/31 animals (3/31 very slight; 7/31 slight) of group 9. The spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregation sometimes induced infiltration of inflammatory cells, minimal fibrosis and hyperplasia of pneumocytes type 2, which was diagnosed as chronic inflammation. Since these spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregations were sometimes localized subpleurally, there was sometimes a subpleurally localized chronic inflammation including a concurrent pleural fibrosis. The chronic inflammation was seen in 13/31 animals (6/31 very slight; 7/31 slight) of group 1, in 9/31 animals (8/31 very slight; 1/31 slight) of group 2, in 12/31 animals (9/31 very slight; 3/31 slight) of group 3, in 3/31 animals of group 4 (2/31 very slight; 1/31 slight), in 7/31 animals (6/31 very slight; 1/31 slight) of group 5, in 15/31 animals (13/31 very slight; 2/31 slight) of group 6, in 13/31 animals (10/31 very slight; 3/31 slight) of group 7, in 2/31 animals (1/31 very slight; 1/31 slight) of group 8, and in 3/31 animals (all very slight) of group 9. Furthermore, cholesterol granulomas were sometimes induced by the alveolar macrophage aggregation. Both diagnoses were correlated to the alveolar macrophage aggregation.

The incidences of (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle- or fiber-laden macrophages in the BALT (bronchus-associated lymphoid tissue) were 1/31 in group 3, 6/31 in group 4, 20/31 in group 5, 1/31 in group 6, 2/31 in group 7, 4/31 in group 8 and 5/31 in group 9. Multifocal multinucleated (syncytial) giant cells were exclusively observed in 26/31 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite; all very slight) and in 27/31 rats of group 9 (Amosite; all very slight).

Multifocal peribronchial/peribronchiolar infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells was diagnosed only in 10/31 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite; all very slight) and in 11/31 rats of group 9 (Amosite; 10/31 very slight; 1/31 slight). The incidences of (multi)focal very slight perivascular (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration were 1/31 in group 5, 10/31 in group 8, and 12/31 in group 9. (Multi)focal alveolar/interstitial (intraseptal) infiltration of (mixed) inflammatory cells occurred in 2/31 rats of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; very slight), in 1/31 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low; very slight), as well as in 27/31 rats of group 8 (Crocidolite; 24/31 very slight; 3/31 slight) and in 28/31 rats of group 9 (Amosite; 24/31 very slight; 4/31 slight).

As a further exposure-related finding, multifocal microgranulomas at bronchiolo-alveolar junctions were diagnosed in 21/31 rats of group 8 (Crocicolite; all very slight) and in 24/31 rats of group 9 (Amosite; all very slight).

A single animal of group 2 (Brake dust low; 1/31 slight), two animals of group 3 (Brake dust mid; 1/31 very slight; 1/31 slight), one animal of group 4 (Brake dust high; 1/31 very slight), and one animal of group 8 (Crocicolite; 1/31 severe) exhibited a multifocal slight alveolar lipoproteinosis. The intra-alveolar lipoproteinaceous material was mainly granular and eosinophilic reflecting basically an origin from degenerating macrophages.

(Multi)focal bronchiolo-alveolar hyperplasia (alveolar bronchiolization) was observed in two animals of group 3 (Brake dust mid; all very slight), 4/31 animals of group 4 (Brake dust high; 3/31 very slight; 1/31 slight), 3/31 animals of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide; all very slight), 6/31 animals of group 6 (Chrysotile low; all very slight) as well as in 20/31 animals of group 7 (Chrysotile high; 18/31 very slight; 2/31 slight), in 30/31 animals of group 8 (Crocicolite; 4/31 very slight, 20/31 slight; 6/31 moderate) and in 30/31 animals of group 9 (Amosite; 3/31 very slight, 12/31 slight; 15/31 moderate).

Multifocal interstitial fibrosis was seen in 1/31 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high; very slight), in 29/31 rats of group 8 (Crocicolite; 16/31 very slight, 13/31 slight) and in 29/31 animals of group 9 (Amosite; 9/31 very slight, 20/31 slight).

The Wagner scoring grade 1 (corresponding to a normal lung) was applied to all rats of group 1 (Clean air control), to 28/31 males of group 2 (Brake dust low), to 21/31 males of group 3 (Brake dust mid), 9/31 rats of group 4 (Brake dust high), 6/31 rats of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide), 12/31 rats of group 6 (Chrysotile low), and 4/31 rats of group 7 (Chrysotile high). Three animals of group 2 (Brake dust low), 10/31 animals of group 3 (Brake dust mid), 22/31 animals of group 4 (Brake dust high), 25/31 animals of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide), 18/31 animals of group 6 (Chrysotile low), and 14/31 animals of group 7 (Chrysotile high) were scored with Wagner grade 2. One animal of group 6 (Chrysotile low) and 12/31 animals of group 7 (Chrysotile high) were scored with Wagner grade 3. One animal of group 7 (Chrysotile high) and all rats investigated from group 8 (Crocicolite) and 9 (Amosite) received Wagner grade 4.

Many animals of all groups showed macroscopically few to many pale foci in all lung lobes. This change can be correlated in most cases to alveolar macrophage aggregation or accumulation of particle-/fibre-laden macrophages.

S-2.7.1.4 d) Spontaneous findings

Congestion, alveolar emphysema, alveolar hemorrhage, lymphoid hyperplasia of the BALT, neuroendocrine cell hyperplasia, pleural hyperplasia, alveolar granulocytic cell infiltration, acute inflammation, chronic-active inflammation, chondro-osseous or fibro-osseous metaplasia occurred in single up to 4 animals per group and were interpreted to be incidental and without any correlation to the treatment.

In addition, the mononuclear cell infiltrations in different parts of the lung (interstitial, perivascular, or pleural) were seen in up to 10 animals per group, including the control group and were interpreted to be incidental and without any correlation to the treatment.

Spontaneous alveolar macrophage aggregations sometimes with concurrent chronic inflammation and cholesterol granulomas were seen (discussed above).

S-2.7.2 LALN

Since no significant tissue was present on the slide provided or the tissue was not taken at necropsy the LALN was examined of 28, 29, 26, 30, 30, 28, 28, 29, and 30 animals of group 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9, respectively.

a) Exposure-related findings

In the LALN of 2/26, 6/30, 14/30, 3/28, 6/28 animals from the particle-exposure groups 3, 4, 5, 6, and 7, respectively, a (multi)focal very slight accumulation of particle-laden macrophages could be observed with two animals of group 5 (Titanium-dioxide) showing this lesion to a slight extent. The LALN of 16/29 rats of the fiber-exposure group 8 (Crocidolite; 8/29 very slight, 8/29 slight) and 11/30 rats of the group 9 (Amosite; all very slight) revealed multifocal accumulation of fiber-laden macrophages.

b) Spontaneous findings

Lymphoid hyperplasia, plasmacytic inflammatory cell infiltration and blood resorption as well as histiocytic sarcoma and lymphoma cell infiltration were interpreted to be incidental and without any correlation to the treatment.

Other organs of the respiratory tract

In the larynx, single or up to 8/31 rats of the control and the exposure groups showed very slight to moderate (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration or (multi)focal subepithelial inflammatory cell infiltration. In addition, single rats or up to 4/31 rats of the control group and some the exposure groups showed very slight to slight dilatation of the submucosal glands.

In a single animal of group 1 a very slight erosion, in a single animal of group 5 a slight epithelial hyperplasia, and in a single animal of group 2 a slight chronic inflammation was observed.

In the nasal cavity, single to 16/31 rats of the different groups showed multifocal very slight to severe (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the olfactory epithelium. Very slight to slight multifocal (eosinophilic) hyaline droplets within the respiratory epithelium were observed in single up to 9 animals of some groups. In addition, single up to three rats of some groups showed (multi)focal very slight mucous cell hyperplasia, focal very slight respiratory epithelial hyperplasia, (multi)focal very slight subepithelial (mixed) inflammatory cell infiltration and (multi)focal very slight subepithelial mononuclear cell infiltration.

In the trachea, single animals up to four animals of different groups revealed very slight (multi)focal subepithelial mononuclear cell or inflammatory cell infiltration.

In the nasopharynx of one animal of group 9, a metastasis (infiltration) of a primary skin tumor (carcinoma, squamous cell) was seen.

The diaphragm was examined of 28, 28, 28, 27, 28, 28, 29, 29, and 29 animals of group 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, and 9, respectively. In the diaphragm, an infiltration of mixed inflammatory cells was observed in single up to 3 animals per group. Furthermore, one animal of group 7 and one animal of group 9 showed a chronic-active inflammation. The diaphragm of one animal of group 9 exhibited a slight hyperplasia. The diaphragm of one animal of group 5 was infiltrated by histiocytic sarcoma cells.

All these findings were considered to be spontaneous and unrelated to the treatment.

S-2.7.3 Histologically investigated macroscopic lesions

There was one mesothelioma in the abdominal cavity in one animal of group 8 (animal 8093), which was interpreted to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment.

Due to macroscopic lesions the liver (up to 16 animals per group), the prostate (up to 6 animals per group), the skin (up to 11 animals per group), the spleen (up to 3 animals per group), the thymus (up to 2 animals per group), the brain (up to 2 animals per group), the pituitary gland (up to 8 animals per group), the kidney (up to 7 animals per group), the testis (up to 8 animals per group), the epididymis (up to 3 animals per group), the stomach (up to 3 animals per group), the eye (single animals per group), the abdominal cavity (single animals per group), seminal vesicle (up to 6 animals per group), thyroid gland (up to 7 animals per group), the pancreas (single animals per group), the adrenal gland (single animals per group), the teeth (up to 4 animals per group), the oral cavity (single animals per group), the parathyroid gland (single animals per group), the esophagus (single animals per group), as well as the mandibular, mesenteric and mediastinal lymph nodes (up to 4 animals per group) were examined.

Within all these organs, there were findings, which represented incidental lesions. They were all interpreted to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment.

S-2.8 Preterminal sacrifices of previous time points, other groups and animals with macroscopic lesions of other groups

The following animals suffered from an unscheduled death/necropsy prior to their assigned post exposure time point. These were the animals 2053 and 7053 assigned for the 12 months as well as the animals 2061, 3061, 7060, 7062, 7063, and 9061 assigned for the 18 months post exposure time point histopathology examination. Further animals represent animal number 1241, 3153, 6152, 6260, 7260, 9261, and 9350, which were initially assigned to other groups.

In addition, the following animals showed macroscopic lesion during the necropsy, which were investigated histologically. These animals were 2260, 2262, 3260, 3262, 4210, 4260, 4261, 4262, 7240, and 9260.

Within the lung and the lung-associated lymph nodes of these animals the respective treatment-related findings were detected, which were seen also in the other animals of the respective treatment groups. No further treatment-related lesions were observed in these animals. No primary lung tumors were detected in these animals. Metastases into the lung of primary tumors outside the respiratory tract were seen in one animal of group 9 (Amosite; carcinoma of the adrenal gland). Two animals of group 7 (Chrysotile high) showed an infiltration of the lung by lymphoma cells. The metastases and the lymphomas were interpreted to be incidental without any relation to the treatment.

In addition to the lung and lung-associated lymph nodes, within all the other organs investigated of these animals, there were findings, which represented incidental lesions. They were all interpreted to be spontaneous and unrelated to treatment.

S-2.9 Conclusion

Following the 89 day inhalation and a post exposure period of up to 24 months exposure-related findings were detected only in the lungs and lung-associated lymph nodes (LALN). At the end of the post exposure period (24 months post exposure) only within the group 8 (Crocidolite) and group 9 (Amosite), an increased number of lung tumors were observed. The tumors mainly consisted of adenomas and carcinomas of the bronchiolo-alveolar type. Mesotheliomas or pre-neoplastic pleural lesions were not detected in the thoracic cavity

including lung (visceral) and thoracic wall (parietal) pleura. Only one mesothelioma was observed in the abdominal cavity of one animal of group 8, which was interpreted to be unrelated to the inhalation.

The treatment-related findings decreased in their severity during the post exposure period in group 2 to 7 but were still detectable at the end of the 24 months post exposure period. The decline of the severity is also reflected by a reduced Wagner score of the animals of group 2 to 7. However in group 8 and 9, the severity of the treatment-related findings including the Wagner score remained comparable during the 24 months post exposure period.

S-3 Histopathology images

S-3.1 6 month – histopathology images

Picture 1: 1031-29-HE_x10

Picture 2: 1031-29-HE_x40

Picture 3: 2031-30-MT_x2_5

Picture 4: 2031-30-MT_x20

Picture 5: 2032-30-HE_x2_5

Picture 6: 2032-30-HE_x20

Picture 7: 2032-30-HE_x40

Picture 8: 2032-30-HE_x53_33

Picture 9: 3030-30-HE_x6-5

Picture 10: 3030-30-HE_x20

Picture 11: 3030-30-HE_x40

Picture 12: 3032-29-HE_x13

Picture 13: 3032-29-HE_x53_33

Picture 14: 4032-29-HE_x2_5

Picture 15: 4032-29-HE_x28

Picture 16: 5032-30-HE_x4

Picture 17: 5032-30-HE_x18

Picture 18: 5032-30-HE_x28

Picture 19: 5032-30-HE_x53_33

Picture 20: 5033-29-HE_x5

Picture 21: 5033-29-HE_x10

Picture 22: 5033-29-HE_x20

Picture 23: 5033-29-HE_x53_33

Picture 24: 6032-29-HE_x4

Picture 25: 6032-29-HE_x12

Picture 26: 6032-29-HE_x28

Picture 27: 6032-29-HE_x53_33

Picture 28: 6032-29-HE_x53_34

Picture 29: 6032-30-HE_x7

Picture 30: 6032-30-HE_x25

Picture 31: 6032-30-HE_x26

Picture 32: 6032-30-MT_x53_33

Picture 33: 7030-29-HE_x4

Picture 34: 7030-29-HE_x10

Picture 35: 7030-29-HE_x20

Picture 36: 7030-29-HE_x40

Picture 37: 7030-30-HE_x10

Picture 38: 7030-30-HE_x18

Picture 39: 7030-30-HE_x40

Picture 40: 7030-30-MG_x40

Picture 41: 8031-30-HE_2_5

Picture 42: 8031-30-HE_x10

Picture 43: 8031-30-HE_x20

Picture 44: 8031-30-HE_x28

Picture 45: 8031-30-HE_x33

Picture 46: 8031-30-HE_x40

Picture 47: 8031-30-HE_x53_33

Picture 48: 8031-30-MT_x31

Picture 49: 8031-30-MT_x40

Picture 50: 8031-30-MT_x38

Picture 51: 9030-30-HE_x2_8

Picture 52: 9030-30-HE_x10

Picture 53: 9030-30-HE_x13

Picture 54: 9030-30-HE_x33

Picture 55: 9030-30-HE_x40

Picture 56: 9030-30-MT_x13

Picture 57: 9030-30-MT_x28

Picture 58: 9030-30-MT_x40

Picture 59: 9033-36-HE_x2

Picture 60: 9033-36-HE_x18

Picture 61: 9033-36-HE_x48

S-3.2 12 month - histopathology images

<p style="text-align: center;">Histopathology Images 12 Months post exposure</p> <p style="text-align: center;">Group is indicated in first digit of the animal number</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> 1 – air control 2 – BD Low dose 3 – BD Mid dose 4 – BD High dose 5 – TiO₂ 6 – Chrysotile low dose 7 – Chrysotile High dose 8 – Crocidolite 9 – Amosite 		<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>Type of induction</th> <th>Time Point (after 1st exposure)</th> <th>Group 1</th> <th>Group 2</th> <th>Group 3</th> <th>Group 4</th> <th>Group 5</th> <th>Group 6</th> <th>Group 7</th> <th>Group 8</th> <th>Group 9</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td>OSM1</td> <td>Month 12</td> <td>1050-1053</td> <td>2050-2053</td> <td>3050-3053</td> <td>4050-4053</td> <td>5050-5053</td> <td>6050-6053</td> <td>7050-7053</td> <td>8050-8053</td> <td>9050-9053</td> </tr> </tbody> </table>										Type of induction	Time Point (after 1 st exposure)	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	Group 8	Group 9	OSM1	Month 12	1050-1053	2050-2053	3050-3053	4050-4053	5050-5053	6050-6053	7050-7053	8050-8053	9050-9053
Type of induction	Time Point (after 1 st exposure)	Group 1	Group 2	Group 3	Group 4	Group 5	Group 6	Group 7	Group 8	Group 9																							
OSM1	Month 12	1050-1053	2050-2053	3050-3053	4050-4053	5050-5053	6050-6053	7050-7053	8050-8053	9050-9053																							
<p>Picture 62: Slide1</p>		<p>Picture 63: Slide2</p>																															

2050_accumulation, particle-laden macrophages, alveolar/interstitial

Picture 64: Slide3

3051_hyperplasia, bronchiolo-alveolar

Picture 65: Slide4

3052_Wagner grade 1

Picture 66: Slide5

3052_Wagner grade 1

Picture 67: Slide6

4051_infiltration, mixed inflammatory cells, perivascular

Picture 68: Slide7

4051_Wagner grade 2

Picture 69: Slide8

4051_Wagner grade 2

Picture 70: Slide9

5052_accumulation of particle-laden macrophages, alveolar

Picture 71: Slide10

5052_accumulation of particle-laden macrophages, interstitial

Picture 72: Slide11

5052_accumulation of particle-laden macrophages, LALN

Picture 73: Slide12

6050_Wagner grade 2

Picture 74: Slide13

7050_hyperplasia, bronchiolo-alveolar and accumulation of particle-laden macrophages

Picture 75: Slide14

8050_interstitial fibrosis- masson trichrome staining

Picture 76: Slide15

8050_interstitial fibrosis- masson trichrome staining

Picture 77: Slide16

8050_hyperplasia, bronchiolo-alveolar, alveolar type

Picture 78: Slide17

8050_hyperplasia, bronchiolo-alveolar, alveolar type

Picture 79: Slide18

8052_accumulation of fibre-laden macrophages, LALN

Picture 80: Slide19

8052_hyaline (eosinophilic) droplets, olfactory epithelium

Picture 81: Slide20

9051_Wagner grade 4

Picture 82: Slide21

9052_hyperplasia, bronchiolo-alveolar; accumulation of fibre-laden macrophages; interstitial fibrosis, microgranuloma and syncytial giant cells

Picture 83: Slide22

9053_hyaline (eosinophilic) droplets, olfactory epithelium

Picture 84: Slide23

9053_accumulation of fibre-laden macrophages, LALN

Picture 85: Slide24

S-3.3 18 month - histopathology images

Picture 86: 1060_29 overview 2er

Picture 87: 1060_30

Picture 88: 2062_29 overview 2er

Picture 89: 3062_29 overview 2er

Picture 90: 4061_29 hyperplasia 20er

Picture 91: 4061_29 overview 2er

Picture 92: 5061_29 overview 2er

Picture 93: 5061_29 particle laden ma 1zu1

Picture 94: 6062_29 overview 2er

Picture 95: 6062_30 20er

Picture 96: 7061_29 BALT 40er

Picture 97: 7061_29 BALT

Picture 98: 7061_29 overview 2er

Picture 99: 7061_29 particeleden ma 40er

Picture 100: 8060_29 4er

Picture 101: 8060_29 10er

Picture 102: 8061_29_MT terminal bronchus

Picture 103: 8061_29_MT

Picture 104: 8061_30 overview 2er

Picture 105: 8061_30 terminal bronchus 40er

Picture 106: 9060_29 Overview 2er

Picture 107: 9060_30 2er Übersicht

Picture 108: 9060_30 10er

Picture 109: 9060_30 40er Hyperplasia normal

Picture 110: 9060_30 lipoproteinosis

Picture 111: 9060_30_MT

S-3.4 24 month - histopathology images

Picture 112: 1082-0,51x overview wbar

Picture 113: 1082-10x macroaggreg b wbar

Picture 114: 1082-10x macroaggreg wbar

Picture 115: 1272-2,5x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 116: 1272-20x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 117: 2083-0,59 overview wbar

Picture 118: 3080-0,53x overview wbar

Picture 119: 3080-10x macroagg w chon inflamm wbar

Picture 120: 4083-20x CholGranuloma wbar

Picture 121: 4083-20x Hyp ba wbar

Picture 122: 4084 40x particleMa BALT wbar

Picture 123: 4084-20x CholGranuloma wbar

Picture 124: 4086-10x macroAggreg w chron inflamm wbar

Picture 125: 4093 40x particleMa BALT wbar

Picture 126: 4093-0,61x overview wbar

Picture 127: 4271-2,5x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 128: 4271-20x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 129: 5072-2,5x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 130: 5072-10x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 131: 5072-20x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 132: 5082-40x particMacroph BALT wbar

Picture 133: 5092-10x Hyper ba alveolar type wbar

Picture 134: 5092-20x PartMacrophag wbar

Picture 135: 5098 0,5x overview wbar

Picture 136: 6072-2,5x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 137: 6072-10x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 138: 6072-10x adenoma ba_b wbar

Picture 139: 6072-20x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 140: 6072-20x adenoma ba_b wbar

Picture 141: 6081-40x particMacroph BALT wbar

Picture 142: 6092-0,59x overview wbar

Picture 143: 7083-40x hyp ba w partMacro wbar

Picture 144: 7084-0,59x overview wbar

Picture 145: 8070-2,5x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 146: 8070-20x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 147: 8073-2,5x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 148: 8073-20x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 149: 8082-0,61 overview wbar

Picture 150: 8082-2,5x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 151: 8082-20x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 152: 8082-40x fibre mircogranuloma and giant cells

Picture 153: 8084-40x partMacro BALT wbar

Picture 154: 8094-2,5x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 155: 8094-10x Hyp ba fibrMacros Giant Microgran

Picture 156: 8094-20x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 157: 8094-40x Hyp ba fibrMacros Giant Microgran b

Picture 158: 8094-40x Hyp ba fibrMacros Giant Microgran

Picture 159: 8097-2,5x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 160: 8097-20x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 161: 9073-2,5x adenoma ba b wbar

Picture 162: 9073-2,5x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 163: 9073-20x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 164: 9080-2,5x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 165: 9080-20x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 166: 9081-40x fibrMacro BALT wbar

Picture 167: 9085-0,61x overview wbar

Picture 168: 9085-10x Hyp ba FibMacro etc wbar

Picture 169: 9087-2,5x adenocarcinoma wbar

Picture 170: 9087-20x adenocarcinoma b wbar

Picture 171: 9087-20x adenocarcinoma wbar

Picture 172: 9090-2,5x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 173: 9090-20x carcinoma ba b wbar

Picture 174: 9090-20x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 175: 9090-40x fibrMacro wbar

Picture 176: 9094-2,5x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 177: 9094-20x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 178: 9097-2,5x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 179: 9097-20x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 180: 9098-2,5x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 181: 9098-20x adenoma ba wbar

Picture 182: 9171-2,5x carcinoma ba wbar

Picture 183: 9171-20x carcinoma ba wbar

S-4 Confocal microscopy of the lung

S-4.1 6 month Lung confocal images

Figure 1 A. Maximum Intensity Projections of lung parenchyma with all 9 treatment groups ranging from 6 (A), 12 (B), 18 (C), and 24 (D) month time points. Each row consists of three representative images from each treatment group of each time point.

S-4.2 12 month Lung confocal images

Figure 1 B. Maximum Intensity Projections of lung parenchyma with all 9 treatment groups from 12 (B) month time point. Each row consists of three representative images from each treatment group of each time point.

S-4.3 18 month Lung confocal images

Figure 1 C. Maximum Intensity Projections of lung parenchyma with all 9 treatment groups from 18 (C) month time point. Each row consists of three representative images from each treatment group of each time point.

Group 1

Group 2

Group 3

Group 4

Group 5

Group 6

Group 7

Group 8

Group 9

S-4.4 24 month Lung confocal images

Figure 1 D. Maximum Intensity Projections of lung parenchyma with all 9 treatment groups from 24 (D) month time point. Each row consists of three representative images from each treatment group of each time point.

Group 1

Group 2

Group 3

Group 4

Group 5

Group 6

Group 7

Group 8

Group 9

S-4.5 Confocal microscopy: Percent collagen in the lung

This file can be opened by [GraphPad Prism](#) (version 5.00 or later).

This file contains 3 data tables and 3 info tables:

- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 6M_L_CT_Manual_per_animal:ANOVA results](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 6M_L_CT_Manual_per_animal:Multiple comparisons](#)
- [Descriptive statistics of 6M_L_CT_Manual_per_animal](#)

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 6M_L_CT_Manual_per_animal:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	6M_L_CT_Manual_per_animal				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	75.57				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
squared	0.9572				
Brown-Forsythe test F					
(DFn, DFd)	1.925 (8, 27)				
P value	0.0972				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?No					
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)	16.71				
P value	0.0333				
P value summary	*				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?Yes					
ANOVA table					
	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	976.2	8	122.0	F (8, 27) = 75.57	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	43.60	27	1.615		
Total	1020	35			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	36				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 6M_L_CT_Manual_per_animal:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test								
	Mean	Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Significant?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?	
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.8413	-3.390 to 1.707	No	ns	0.9103	B	Brake:Low	
Ctrl vs. Brake:Mid	0.9009	-1.647 to 3.449	No	ns	0.8793	C	Brake:Mid	
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.3723	-2.921 to 2.176	No	ns	0.9994	D	Brake:High	
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.08284	-2.631 to 2.465	No	ns	0.9999	E	TiO ₂	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	0.4251	-2.123 to 2.973	No	ns	0.9973	F	Chrysotile:Low	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-2.331	-4.879 to 0.2173	No	ns	0.0842	G	Chrysotile:High	
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-11.67	-14.22 to -9.125	Yes	****	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
Ctrl vs. Amosite	-13.60	-16.15 to -11.05	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
Test details								
	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	2.679	3.521	-0.8413	0.8985	4	4	0.9363	27

Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	2.679	1.778	0.9009	0.8985	4	4	1.003	27
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	2.679	3.052	-0.3723	0.8985	4	4	0.4143	27

Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	2.679	2.762	-0.08284	0.8985	4	4	0.09220	27
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	2.679	2.254	0.4251	0.8985	4	4	0.4731	27
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	2.679	5.010	-2.331	0.8985	4	4	2.594	27
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	2.679	14.35	-11.67	0.8985	4	4	12.99	27
Ctrl vs. Amosite	2.679	16.28	-13.60	0.8985	4	4	15.14	27

Descriptive statistics of 6M_L_CT_Manual_per_animal

	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of values	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4	4
Mean	2.679	3.521	1.778	3.052	2.762	2.254	5.010	14.35	16.28
Std. Deviation	0.9533	0.4077	0.9024	0.4368	0.7798	0.5482	1.134	2.396	2.126
Std. Error of Mean	0.4766	0.2039	0.4512	0.2184	0.3899	0.2741	0.5670	1.198	1.063
Geometric mean	2.561	3.504	1.632	3.030	2.659	2.209	4.895	14.19	16.18
Geometric SD factor	1.410	1.119	1.592	1.146	1.401	1.256	1.298	1.191	1.139

This file can be opened by [GraphPad Prism](#) (version 5.00 or later).

This file contains 3 data tables and 3 info tables:

- [Descriptive statistics of 12M_L_CT_Manual_per-animal](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M_L_CT_Manual_per-animal:ANOVA results](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M_L_CT_Manual_per-animal:Multiple comparisons](#)

Descriptive statistics of 12M_L_CT_Manual_per-animal

	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of values	4	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	4
Mean	1.261	1.091	1.419	1.782	2.018	1.057	4.138	23.04	23.47
Std. Deviation	0.5531	0.2712	0.3272	1.019	1.597	0.3629	0.6016	0.4725	3.020
Std. Error of Mean	0.2765	0.1566	0.1636	0.5093	0.7986	0.1814	0.3473	0.2363	1.510
Geometric mean	1.182	1.070	1.390	1.611	1.544	1.004	4.110	23.04	23.33
Geometric SD factor	1.496	1.268	1.261	1.633	2.408	1.470	1.151	1.021	1.133

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M_L_CT_Manual_per-animal:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	12M_L_CT_Manual_per-animal				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	215.6				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
squared	0.9857				
Brown-Forsythe test F (DFn, DFd)	1.692 (8, 25)				
P value	0.1499				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	2848	8	356.1	F (8, 25) = 215.6	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	41.29	25	1.652		
Total	2890	33			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	34				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M_L_CT_Manual_per-animal:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
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Dunnnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Significant?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?	
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	0.1703	-2.637 to 2.977	No	ns	0.9997	B	Brake:Low
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.1575	-2.756 to 2.441	No	ns	0.9997	C	Brakd:Mid
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.5204	-3.119 to 2.078	No	ns	0.9935	D	Brake:High
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.7567	-3.355 to 1.842	No	ns	0.9513	E	TiO ₂
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	0.2044	-2.394 to 2.803	No	ns	0.9997	F	Chrysotile:Low
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-2.876	-5.683 to -0.06942	Yes	*	0.0428	G	Chrysotile:High
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-21.78	-24.38 to -19.18	Yes	****	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite
Ctrl vs. Amosite	-22.21	-24.81 to -19.61	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	Amosite

Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	1.261	1.091	0.1703	0.9816	4	3	0.1735	25
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	1.261	1.419	-0.1575	0.9088	4	4	0.1733	25
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	1.261	1.782	-0.5204	0.9088	4	4	0.5727	25
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	1.261	2.018	-0.7567	0.9088	4	4	0.8326	25
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	1.261	1.057	0.2044	0.9088	4	4	0.2250	25
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	1.261	4.138	-2.876	0.9816	4	3	2.930	25
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	1.261	23.04	-21.78	0.9088	4	4	23.96	25
Ctrl vs. Amosite	1.261	23.47	-22.21	0.9088	4	4	24.44	25

This file can be opened by [GraphPad Prism](#) (version 5.00 or later).

This file contains 3 data tables and 3 info tables:

- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M_CT_Manual:ANOVA results](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M_CT_Manual:Multiple comparisons](#)
- [Descriptive statistics of 18M_CT_Manual](#)

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M_CT_Manual:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	18M_CT_Manual				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	589.3				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.9956				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table					
	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	1312	8	164.0	F (8, 21) = 589.3	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	5.845	21	0.2783		
Total	1318	29			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	30				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M_CT_Manual:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test								
	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Significant?	Summary	Adjusted P ValueA-?			
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.2465	-1.423 to 0.9301	No	ns	0.9924	B	Brake:Low	
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.5767	-1.753 to 0.5999	No	ns	0.6333	C	Brakd:Mid	
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.1980	-1.287 to 0.8914	No	ns	0.9969	D	Brake:High	
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	0.07717	-1.012 to 1.167	No	ns	0.9997	E	TiO ₂	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-0.4507	-1.540 to 0.6387	No	ns	0.7827	F	Chrysotile:Low	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-0.4586	-2.181 to 1.264	No	ns	0.9696	G	Chrysotile:High	
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-16.08	-17.17 to -14.99	Yes	****	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
Ctrl vs. Amosite	-15.55	-16.73 to -14.37	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
Test details								
	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	3.493	3.740	-0.2465	0.4029	4	3	0.6119	21
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	3.493	4.070	-0.5767	0.4029	4	3	1.431	21
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	3.493	3.691	-0.1980	0.3731	4	4	0.5307	21
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	3.493	3.416	0.07717	0.3731	4	4	0.2069	21

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Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	3.493	3.944	-0.4507	0.3731	4	4	1.208	21
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	3.493	3.952	-0.4586	0.5898	4	1	0.7776	21
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	3.493	19.58	-16.08	0.3731	4	4	43.11	21
Ctrl vs. Amosite	3.493	19.04	-15.55	0.4029	4	3	38.59	21

Descriptive statistics of 18M_CT_Manual

	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂		Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of values	4	3	3	4	4	4	1	4	3	
Mean	3.493	3.740	4.070	3.691	3.416	3.944	3.952	19.58	19.04	
Std. Deviation	0.5453	0.2293	0.2242	0.1967	0.3313	0.1716	0.000	1.179	0.1473	
Std. Error of Mean	0.2727	0.1324	0.1295	0.09833	0.1656	0.08579	0.000	0.5895	0.08504	
Geometric mean	3.458	3.735	4.066	3.687	3.404	3.941	3.952	19.55	19.04	
Geometric SD factor	1.185	1.064	1.057	1.054	1.102	1.044	1.000	1.063	1.008	

This file can be opened by [GraphPad Prism](#) (version 5.00 or later).

This file contains 3 data tables and 3 info tables:

- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 24 Month Manual:ANOVA results](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 24 Month Manual:Multiple comparisons](#)
- [Descriptive statistics of 24 Month Manual](#)

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 24_Month_Manual:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	24_Month_Manual				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	617.7				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.9974				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	6.979 (8, 13)				
P value	0.0012				
P value summary	**				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table					
	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	789.5	8	98.69	F (8, 13) = 617.7	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	2.077	13	0.1598		
Total	791.6	21			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	22				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 24_Month_Manual:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test								
	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Significant?	Summary	Adjusted P ValueA-?			
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.2031	-1.211 to 0.8049	No	ns	0.9909	B	Brake:Low	
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.09235	-1.100 to 0.9157	No	ns	0.9996	C	Brakd:Mid	
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.1475	-1.156 to 0.8605	No	ns	0.9977	D	Brake:High	
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.01527	-1.142 to 1.112	No	ns	>0.9999	E	TiO ₂	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-0.4541	-1.581 to 0.6729	No	ns	0.7582	F	Chrysotile:Low	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-0.3948	-1.522 to 0.7322	No	ns	0.8521	G	Chrysotile:High	
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-15.51	-16.64 to -14.39	Yes	****	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
Ctrl vs. Amosite	-15.88	-17.01 to -14.75	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
Test details								
	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	3.598	3.802	-0.2031	0.3264	3	3	0.6224	13
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	3.598	3.691	-0.09235	0.3264	3	3	0.2830	13
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	3.598	3.746	-0.1475	0.3264	3	3	0.4520	13
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	3.598	3.614	-0.01527	0.3649	3	2	0.04185	13

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Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	3.598	4.053	-0.4541	0.3649	3	2	1.245	13
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	3.598	3.993	-0.3948	0.3649	3	2	1.082	13
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	3.598	19.11	-15.51	0.3649	3	2	42.52	13
Ctrl vs. Amosite	3.598	19.48	-15.88	0.3649	3	2	43.52	13

Descriptive statistics of 24_Month_Manual

Ctrl Brake:Low Brakd:Mid Brake:High ^{TiO₂} Chrysotile:Low Chrysotile:High Crocidolite Amosite

Number of values	3	3	3	3	2	2	2	2	2
Mean	3.598	3.802	3.691	3.746	3.614	4.053	3.993	19.11	19.48
Std. Deviation	0.2747	0.2545	0.07543	0.1732	0.1538	0.1833	0.2769	1.029	0.7302
Std. Error of Mean	0.1586	0.1469	0.04355	0.09999	0.1088	0.1296	0.1958	0.7273	0.5163
Geometric mean	3.592	3.796	3.690	3.743	3.612	4.051	3.988	19.10	19.47
Geometric SD factor	1.078	1.069	1.021	1.047	1.043	1.046	1.072	1.055	1.038

S-4.6 Confocal Microscopy: Number of fibers observed by length category

Group	Month	Group-Month	< 5 μm	5-20 μm	> 20 μm
Ctrl	6	Ctrl 6	0	0	0
Brake:Low	6	Brake:Low 6	0	0	0
Brakd:Mid	6	Brakd:Mid 6	0	0	0
Brake:High	6	Brake:High 6	0	31200	0
TiO2	6	TiO2 6	30900	30900	0
Chrysotile:Low	6	Chrysotile:Low 6	63800	31900	0
Chrysotile:High	6	Chrysotile:High 6	176200	246600	0
Crocidolite	6	Crocidolite 6	3717000	9120000	3281000
Amosite	6	Amosite 6	1082000	3210000	2247000
Ctrl	12	Ctrl 12	0	0	0
Brake:Low	12	Brake:Low 12	0	0	0
Brakd:Mid	12	Brakd:Mid 12	0	26400	0
Brake:High	12	Brake:High 12	38400	0	0
TiO2	12	TiO2 12	0	43200	0
Chrysotile:Low	12	Chrysotile:Low 12	0	43600	0
Chrysotile:High	12	Chrysotile:High 12	72200	144400	0
Crocidolite	12	Crocidolite 12	3477000	14850000	12730000
Amosite	12	Amosite 12	5540000	23650000	16170000
Ctrl	18	Ctrl 18	0	0	0
Brake:Low	18	Brake:Low 18	0	0	0
Brakd:Mid	18	Brakd:Mid 18	0	119000	0
Brake:High	18	Brake:High 18	0	0	0
TiO2	18	TiO2 18	0	0	0
Chrysotile:Low	18	Chrysotile:Low 18	0	0	0
Chrysotile:High	18	Chrysotile:High 18	0	0	0
Crocidolite	18	Crocidolite 18	2448100	20790000	12650000
Amosite	18	Amosite 18	2060000	25520000	23040000
Ctrl	24	Ctrl 24	0	0	0
Brake:Low	24	Brake:Low 24	0	0	0
Brakd:Mid	24	Brakd:Mid 24	0	0	0
Brake:High	24	Brake:High 24	0	0	0
TiO2	24	TiO2 24	0	0	0
Chrysotile:Low	24	Chrysotile:Low 24	0	0	0
Chrysotile:High	24	Chrysotile:High 24	144000	144000	0
Crocidolite	24	Crocidolite 24	379000	5490000	3130000
Amosite	24	Amosite 24	2581000	33610000	18730000

S-5 Confocal microscopy of the visceral & parietal pleura

S-5.1 9 month - Percent connective tissue visceral & parietal pleura collagen

S-5.1.1 Visceral pleura

Table format: Column		Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F	Group G	Group H
		Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite
1	Title	4.25250000	5.1275	5.23222222	4.81000000	3.954000000	3.85600000	6.88444444	19.68400000
2	Title	4.20444444	5.5540	5.39000000	5.19666667	4.892727270	5.59125000		20.40666670
3	Title	6.32666667	5.2300	5.52333333	5.17222222	6.243333333	5.07714286	5.61692308	20.47250000
4	Title		5.3100	5.11750000	5.34500000		4.32875000	4.72454545	21.44000000

Group I Amosite	
1	23.94200000
2	13.27400000
3	18.13200000
4	17.46250000

S-5.1.2 Parietal pleura

		Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F	Group G	Group H
		Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite
1		4.71250000	5.01166670	4.16538462	4.67428570	5.57800000	7.34375000	6.20555556	21.9633333
2			5.38000000	6.11375000	5.18500000	6.74090910	5.75428570	5.81500000	14.8271429
3		5.22428571	5.53454550	5.53500000	5.30875000		4.62666670	5.10500000	14.5100000
4		4.32888889	4.89400000	5.92545450	6.18600000	3.67125000	4.31400000		18.6550000

Group I Amosite	
1	18.7000000
2	16.3271429
3	16.2162500
4	16.9225000

S-5.1.3 Visceral pleura

Descriptive statistics		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
		Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
1	Number of values	3	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	4
2										
3	Mean	4.928	5.305	5.316	5.131	5.030	4.713	5.742	20.50	18.20
4	Std. Deviation	1.212	0.1818	0.1778	0.2272	1.151	0.7716	1.085	0.7209	4.389
5	Std. Error of Mean	0.6995	0.09090	0.08892	0.1136	0.6644	0.3858	0.6266	0.3604	2.194
6										
7	Geometric mean	4.836	5.303	5.314	5.127	4.943	4.666	5.674	20.49	17.81
8	Geometric SD factor	1.262	1.035	1.034	1.046	1.257	1.180	1.207	1.036	1.273

Ordinary one-way ANOVA ANOVA results						
1	Table Analyzed	9_Month_V-per animal				
2	Data sets analyzed	A-I				
3						
4	ANOVA summary					
5	F	53.31				
6	P value	<0.0001				
7	P value summary	****				
8	Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
9	R squared	0.9467				
10						
11	Brown-Forsythe test					
12	F (DFn, DFd)	2.088 (8, 24)				
13	P value	0.0781				
14	P value summary	ns				
15	Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
16						
17	Bartlett's test					
18	Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
19	P value					
20	P value summary					
21	Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
22						
23	ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
24	Treatment (between columns)	1234	8	154.2	F (8, 24) = 53.31	P<0.0001
25	Residual (within columns)	69.42	24	2.892		
26	Total	1303	32			
27						
28	Data summary					
29	Number of treatments (columns)	9				
30	Number of values (total)	33				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA Multiple comparisons					
1	Number of families	1			
2	Number of comparisons per family	8			
3	Alpha	0.05			
4					
5	Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary
6	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.3775	-4.059 to 3.304	No	ns
7	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.3879	-4.069 to 3.293	No	ns
8	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.2031	-3.884 to 3.478	No	ns
9	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.1021	-4.037 to 3.833	No	ns
10	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	0.2146	-3.466 to 3.896	No	ns
11	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-0.8141	-4.749 to 3.121	No	ns
12	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-15.57	-19.25 to -11.89	Yes	****
13	Ctrl vs. Amosite	-13.27	-16.96 to -9.594	Yes	****
14					
15	Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.
16	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	4.928	5.305	-0.3775	1.299
17	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	4.928	5.316	-0.3879	1.299
18	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	4.928	5.131	-0.2031	1.299
19	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	4.928	5.030	-0.1021	1.389
20	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	4.928	4.713	0.2146	1.299
21	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	4.928	5.742	-0.8141	1.389
22	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	4.928	20.50	-15.57	1.299
23	Ctrl vs. Amosite	4.928	18.20	-13.27	1.299

1				
2				
3				
4				
5	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
6	0.9996	B	Brake:Low	
7	0.9996	C	Brakd:Mid	
8	0.9998	D	Brake:High	
9	>0.9999	E	TiO ₂	
10	0.9997	F	Chrysotile:Low	
11	0.9910	G	Chrysotile:High	
12	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
13	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
14				
15	n1	n2	q	DF
16	3	4	0.2906	24
17	3	4	0.2986	24
18	3	4	0.1564	24
19	3	3	0.07356	24
20	3	4	0.1652	24
21	3	3	0.5863	24
22	3	4	11.99	24
23	3	4	10.22	24

S-5.1.4 Parietal pleura

Descriptive statistics		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
		Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
1	Number of values	3	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	4
2										
3	Mean	4.755	5.205	5.435	5.339	5.330	5.510	5.709	17.49	17.04
4	Std. Deviation	0.4492	0.3018	0.8800	0.6282	1.550	1.370	0.5580	3.528	1.148
5	Std. Error of Mean	0.2594	0.1509	0.4400	0.3141	0.8948	0.6851	0.3221	1.764	0.5742
6										
7	Geometric mean	4.741	5.198	5.376	5.311	5.168	5.389	5.690	17.23	17.01
8	Geometric SD factor	1.099	1.060	1.191	1.123	1.365	1.271	1.105	1.219	1.068

Ordinary one-way ANOVA							
ANOVA results							
1	Table Analyzed	9_Month_P_per animal					
2	Data sets analyzed	A-I					
3							
4	ANOVA summary						
5	F	45.89					
6	P value	<0.0001					
7	P value summary	****					
8	Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes					
9	R squared	0.9386					
10							
11	Brown-Forsythe test						
12	F (DFn, DFd)	3.757 (8, 24)					
13	P value	0.0055					
14	P value summary	**					
15	Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes					
16							
17	Bartlett's test						
18	Bartlett's statistic (corrected)						
19	P value						
20	P value summary						
21	Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?						
22							
23	ANOVA table	SS		DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
24	Treatment (between columns)	864.9		8	108.1	F (8, 24) = 45.89	P<0.0001
25	Residual (within columns)	56.54		24	2.356		
26	Total	921.4		32			
27							
28	Data summary						
29	Number of treatments (columns)	9					
30	Number of values (total)	33					

Ordinary one-way ANOVA Multiple comparisons					
1	Number of families	1			
2	Number of comparisons per family	8			
3	Alpha	0.05			
4					
5	Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary
6	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.4498	-3.772 to 2.872	No	ns
7	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.6797	-4.002 to 2.642	No	ns
8	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.5833	-3.905 to 2.739	No	ns
9	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.5748	-4.126 to 2.977	No	ns
10	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-0.7545	-4.076 to 2.568	No	ns
11	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-0.9533	-4.505 to 2.598	No	ns
12	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-12.73	-16.06 to -9.412	Yes	****
13	Ctrl vs. Amosite	-12.29	-15.61 to -8.964	Yes	****
14					
15	Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.
16	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	4.755	5.205	-0.4498	1.172
17	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	4.755	5.435	-0.6797	1.172
18	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	4.755	5.339	-0.5833	1.172
19	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	4.755	5.330	-0.5748	1.253
20	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	4.755	5.510	-0.7545	1.172
21	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	4.755	5.709	-0.9533	1.253
22	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	4.755	17.49	-12.73	1.172
23	Ctrl vs. Amosite	4.755	17.04	-12.29	1.172

1				
2				
3				
4				
5	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
6	0.9994	B	Brake:Low	
7	0.9915	C	Brakd:Mid	
8	0.9954	D	Brake:High	
9	0.9972	E	TiO ₂	
10	0.9841	F	Chrysotile:Low	
11	0.9598	G	Chrysotile:High	
12	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
13	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
14				
15	n1	n2	q	DF
16	3	4	0.3837	24
17	3	4	0.5798	24
18	3	4	0.4976	24
19	3	3	0.4587	24
20	3	4	0.6436	24
21	3	3	0.7607	24
22	3	4	10.86	24
23	3	4	10.48	24

Percent Connective Tissue Visceral Pleura (CW) - 9 Months

Percent Connective Tissue Parietal Pleura (CW) - 9 Months

S-5.2 12 month – visceral & parietal pleura collagen

S-5.2.1 Visceral pleura

	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F	Group G	Group H	Group I
	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
1	6.69857143	5.22222222	6.27000000	5.86181818	5.38071429	5.65333333		19.04000000	
2	7.42000000	4.78857143	5.54125000	5.43125000	5.70571429	6.60111111	7.57571429	14.13125000	21.47909090
3	2.68500000	6.08500000	5.72000000	5.17400000	5.32625000	4.72600000	8.71600000	20.33625000	28.80800000
4	4.66555556	5.45500000	4.41428571	5.11888889	5.05857143	8.84500000	7.95200000	27.22666670	21.35555560
5	4.47200000								

S-5.2.2 Parietal pleura

	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F	Group G	Group H
	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite
1	5.29285714	5.88300000	7.66285714	5.26090909	7.20333333	5.77750000		25.0933333
2	5.52454545	5.51500000	3.50200000	5.71500000	4.97857143	6.75250000	7.24714286	22.8662500
3	4.96500000	4.38333333	6.69222222	5.80571429	6.51142857	8.95428571	6.06333333	21.0740000
4	7.55777778	6.31400000	5.09571429	5.86750000	3.84166667	4.94428571	8.33727273	22.6977778

Group I Amosite	
1	19.7520000
2	17.0733333
3	23.7420000
4	17.0400000

S-5.2.3 Visceral Pleura

Descriptive statistics	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	
	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite	
1	Number of values	5	4	4	4	4	3	4	3	
2										
3	Mean	5.188	5.388	5.486	5.396	5.368	6.456	8.081	20.18	23.88
4	Std. Deviation	1.892	0.5407	0.7791	0.3388	0.2656	1.767	0.5810	5.403	4.267
5	Std. Error of Mean	0.8460	0.2704	0.3896	0.1694	0.1328	0.8834	0.3355	2.701	2.464
6										
7	Geometric mean	4.886	5.368	5.442	5.389	5.363	6.285	8.068	19.65	23.64
8	Geometric SD factor	1.493	1.105	1.161	1.064	1.051	1.304	1.074	1.309	1.187

Ordinary one-way ANOVA ANOVA results					
1	Table Analyzed	12_Month_V-per animal			
2	Data sets analyzed	A-I			
3					

4	ANOVA summary					
5	F	31.56				
6	P value	<0.0001				
7	P value summary	****				
8	Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
9	R squared	0.9066				
10						
11	Brown-Forsythe test					
12	F (DFn, DFd)	1.663 (8, 26)				
13	P value	0.1556				
14	P value summary	ns				
15	Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
16						
17	Bartlett's test					
18	Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
19	P value					
20	P value summary					
21	Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
22						
23	ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn)	P valu
24	Treatment (between columns)	1472	8	184.0	F (8, 2)	P<0.00
25	Residual (within columns)	151.6	26	5.831		
26	Total	1624	34			
27						
28	Data summary					
29	Number of treatments (columns)	9				
30	Number of values (total)	35				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA Multiple comparisons					
1	Number of families	1			
2	Number of comparisons per family	8			
3	Alpha	0.05			
4					
5	Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary
6	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.1995	-4.854 to 4.455	No	ns
7	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.2982	-4.952 to 4.356	No	ns
8	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.2083	-4.863 to 4.446	No	ns
9	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.1796	-4.834 to 4.475	No	ns
10	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-1.268	-5.922 to 3.386	No	ns
11	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-2.893	-7.960 to 2.174	No	ns
12	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-15.00	-19.65 to -10.34	Yes	****
13	Ctrl vs. Amosite	-18.69	-23.76 to -13.63	Yes	****
14					
15	Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.
16	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	5.188	5.388	-0.1995	1.620
17	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	5.188	5.486	-0.2982	1.620
18	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	5.188	5.396	-0.2083	1.620
19	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	5.188	5.368	-0.1796	1.620
20	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	5.188	6.456	-1.268	1.620
21	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	5.188	8.081	-2.893	1.763
22	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	5.188	20.18	-15.00	1.620
23	Ctrl vs. Amosite	5.188	23.88	-18.69	1.763

1				
2				
3				
4				
5	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
6	0.9999	B	Brake:Low	
7	0.9997	C	Brakd:Mid	
8	0.9999	D	Brake:High	
9	0.9999	E	TiO ₂	
10	0.9705	F	Chrysotile:Low	
11	0.4905	G	Chrysotile:High	
12	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
13	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
14				
15	n1	n2	q	DF
16	5	4	0.1231	26
17	5	4	0.1841	26
18	5	4	0.1286	26
19	5	4	0.1109	26
20	5	4	0.7829	26
21	5	3	1.641	26
22	5	4	9.257	26
23	5	3	10.60	26

S-5.2.4 Parietal pleura

Descriptive statistics		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
		Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
1	Number of values	4	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4
2										
3	Mean	5.835	5.524	5.738	5.662	5.634	6.607	7.216	22.93	19.40
4	Std. Deviation	1.171	0.8275	1.828	0.2748	1.514	1.730	1.137	1.652	3.160
5	Std. Error of Mean	0.5856	0.4137	0.9141	0.1374	0.7569	0.8652	0.6566	0.8258	1.580
6										
7	Geometric mean	5.755	5.474	5.500	5.657	5.473	6.447	7.155	22.89	19.22
8	Geometric SD factor	1.205	1.171	1.413	1.051	1.327	1.288	1.173	1.074	1.170

Ordinary one-way ANOVA							
ANOVA results							
1	Table Analyzed	12_Month_P_per animal					
2	Data sets analyzed	A-I					
3							
4	ANOVA summary						
5	F	64.78					
6	P value	<0.0001					
7	P value summary	****					
8	Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes					
9	R squared	0.9522					
10							
11	Brown-Forsythe test						
12	F (DFn, DFd)	1.507 (8, 26)					
13	P value	0.2029					
14	P value summary	ns					
15	Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No					
16							
17	Bartlett's test						
18	Bartlett's statistic (corrected)						
19	P value						
20	P value summary						
21	Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?						
22							
23	ANOVA table	SS		DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
24	Treatment (between columns)	1455		8	181.9	F (8, 26) = 64.78	P<0.0001
25	Residual (within columns)	73.01		26	2.808		
26	Total	1528		34			
27							
28	Data summary						
29	Number of treatments (columns)	9					
30	Number of values (total)	35					

Ordinary one-way ANOVA Multiple comparisons					
1	Number of families	1			
2	Number of comparisons per family	8			
3	Alpha	0.05			
4					
5	Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary
6	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	0.3112	-3.063 to 3.685	No	ns
7	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	0.09685	-3.277 to 3.471	No	ns
8	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	0.1728	-3.201 to 3.547	No	ns
9	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	0.2013	-3.173 to 3.575	No	ns
10	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-0.7721	-4.146 to 2.602	No	ns
11	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-1.381	-5.025 to 2.264	No	ns
12	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-17.10	-20.47 to -13.72	Yes	****
13	Ctrl vs. Amosite	-13.57	-16.94 to -10.19	Yes	****
14					
15	Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.
16	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	5.835	5.524	0.3112	1.185
17	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	5.835	5.738	0.09685	1.185
18	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	5.835	5.662	0.1728	1.185
19	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	5.835	5.634	0.2013	1.185
20	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	5.835	6.607	-0.7721	1.185
21	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	5.835	7.216	-1.381	1.280
22	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	5.835	22.93	-17.10	1.185
23	Ctrl vs. Amosite	5.835	19.40	-13.57	1.185

1				
2				
3				
4				
5	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
6	0.9996	B	Brake:Low	
7	0.9999	C	Brakd:Mid	
8	0.9998	D	Brake:High	
9	0.9997	E	TiO ₂	
10	0.9875	F	Chrysotile:Low	
11	0.8412	G	Chrysotile:High	
12	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
13	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
14				
15	n1	n2	q	DF
16	4	4	0.2626	26
17	4	4	0.08173	26
18	4	4	0.1458	26
19	4	4	0.1699	26
20	4	4	0.6516	26
21	4	3	1.079	26
22	4	4	14.43	26

23	4	4	11.45	26
----	---	---	-------	----

Percent Connective Tissue Parietal Pleura (CW) - 12 Months

S-5.3 18 month – visceral & parietal pleura collagen

S-5.3.1 Visceral pleura

	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F	Group G	Group H	Group I
	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
1	5.11800000	4.15666667	4.46000000	4.73000000	5.17285714	5.89000000	8.84333333	20.0057143	25.0250000
2	4.14000000	5.04900000	6.40500000	5.34875000	5.62333333	6.75571429	5.49000000	26.6028571	18.5114286
3	4.52833333	4.81000000	3.77714286		5.27200000			15.9457143	

S-5.3.2 Parietal Pleura

	Group A	Group B	Group C	Group D	Group E	Group F	Group G	Group H	Group I
	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
1	4.220	3.976	4.99333333	6.16285714	5.17666667	5.27428571	7.05333333	22.32142860	23.1236364
2	4.034	5.505	4.42125000	3.82125000	5.29333333	6.65222222	6.05727273	31.30428570	19.8658333
3	5.030	5.705	5.42800000		4.24400000			17.64000000	

S-5.3.3 Visceral pleura

Descriptive statistics	A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I	
	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite	
1	Number of values	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	3	2
2										
3	Mean	4.595	4.672	4.881	5.039	5.356	6.323	7.167	20.85	21.77
4	Std. Deviation	0.4924	0.4619	1.364	0.4375	0.2367	0.6122	2.371	5.379	4.606
5	Std. Error of Mean	0.2843	0.2667	0.7872	0.3094	0.1367	0.4329	1.677	3.105	3.257
6										
7	Geometric mean	4.578	4.656	4.761	5.030	5.353	6.308	6.968	20.40	21.52
8	Geometric SD factor	1.112	1.107	1.310	1.091	1.045	1.102	1.401	1.292	1.238

Ordinary one-way ANOVA					
ANOVA results					
1	Table Analyzed	18_Month_P-per animal			
2	Data sets analyzed	A-I			
3					
4	ANOVA summary				
5	F	19.77			
6	P value	<0.0001			
7	P value summary	****			
8	Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes			
9	R squared	0.9187			
10					
11	Brown-Forsythe test				
12	F (DFn, DFd)	1.775 (8, 14)			
13	P value	0.1661			
14	P value summary	ns			

15	Are SDs significantly different ($P < 0.05$)?	No				
16						
17	Bartlett's test					
18	Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
19	P value					
20	P value summary					
21	Are SDs significantly different ($P < 0.05$)?					
22						
23	ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
24	Treatment (between columns)	1237	8	154.6	F (8, 14) = 19.77	P<0.0001
25	Residual (within columns)	109.5	14	7.818		
26	Total	1346	22			
27						
28	Data summary					
29	Number of treatments (columns)	9				
30	Number of values (total)	23				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA Multiple comparisons					
1	Number of families	1			
2	Number of comparisons per family	8			
3	Alpha	0.05			
4					
5	Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary
6	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.6340	-7.597 to 6.329	No	ns
7	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.5195	-7.483 to 6.444	No	ns
8	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.5641	-8.349 to 7.221	No	ns
9	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.4767	-7.440 to 6.487	No	ns
10	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-1.535	-9.320 to 6.250	No	ns
11	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-2.127	-9.912 to 5.658	No	ns
12	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-19.33	-26.29 to -12.36	Yes	****
13	Ctrl vs. Amosite	-17.07	-24.85 to -9.282	Yes	****
14					
15	Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.
16	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	4.428	5.062	-0.6340	2.283
17	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	4.428	4.948	-0.5195	2.283
18	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	4.428	4.992	-0.5641	2.552
19	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	4.428	4.905	-0.4767	2.283
20	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	4.428	5.963	-1.535	2.552
21	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	4.428	6.555	-2.127	2.552
22	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	4.428	23.76	-19.33	2.283
23	Ctrl vs. Amosite	4.428	21.49	-17.07	2.552

1				
2				
3				
4				
5	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
6	0.9996	B	Brake:Low	
7	0.9997	C	Brakd:Mid	
8	0.9997	D	Brake:High	
9	0.9997	E	TiO ₂	
10	0.9921	F	Chrysotile:Low	
11	0.9517	G	Chrysotile:High	
12	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
13	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
14				
15	n1	n2	q	DF
16	3	3	0.2777	14
17	3	3	0.2276	14
18	3	2	0.2210	14
19	3	3	0.2088	14
20	3	2	0.6015	14
21	3	2	0.8334	14
22	3	3	8.466	14
23	3	2	6.686	14

S-5.3.4 Parietal pleura

Descriptive statistics		A	B	C	D	E	F	G	H	I
		Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
1	Number of values	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	3	2
2										
3	Mean	4.428	5.062	4.948	4.992	4.905	5.963	6.555	23.76	21.49
4	Std. Deviation	0.5296	0.9458	0.5049	1.656	0.5751	0.9743	0.7043	6.944	2.304
5	Std. Error of Mean	0.3058	0.5461	0.2915	1.171	0.3320	0.6890	0.4980	4.009	1.629
6										
7	Geometric mean	4.408	4.998	4.930	4.853	4.881	5.923	6.536	23.10	21.43
8	Geometric SD factor	1.124	1.220	1.109	1.402	1.129	1.178	1.114	1.334	1.113

Ordinary one-way ANOVA						
ANOVA results						
1	Table Analyzed	18_Month_V-per animal				
2	Data sets analyzed	A-I				
3						
4	ANOVA summary					
5	F	19.52				
6	P value	<0.0001				
7	P value summary	****				
8	Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
9	R squared	0.9177				
10						
11	Brown-Forsythe test					
12	F (DFn, DFd)	2.609 (8, 14)				
13	P value	0.0558				
14	P value summary	ns				
15	Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
16						
17	Bartlett's test					
18	Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
19	P value					
20	P value summary					
21	Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
22						
23	ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
24	Treatment (between columns)	1004	8	125.5	F (8, 14) = 19.52	P<0.0001
25	Residual (within columns)	90.00	14	6.429		
26	Total	1094	22			
27						
28	Data summary					
29	Number of treatments (columns)	9				
30	Number of values (total)	23				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA					
Multiple comparisons					
1	Number of families	1			
2	Number of comparisons per family	8			

3	Alpha	0.05			
4					
5	Dunnett's multiple comparisons t	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary
6	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.07644	-6.391 to 6.238	No	ns
7	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.2853	-6.600 to 6.029	No	ns
8	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.4439	-7.504 to 6.616	No	ns
9	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.7606	-7.075 to 5.554	No	ns
10	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-1.727	-8.787 to 5.332	No	ns
11	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-2.571	-9.631 to 4.488	No	ns
12	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-16.26	-22.57 to -9.942	Yes	****
13	Ctrl vs. Amosite	-17.17	-24.23 to -10.11	Yes	****
14					
15	Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.
16	Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	4.595	4.672	-0.07644	2.070
17	Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	4.595	4.881	-0.2853	2.070
18	Ctrl vs. Brake:High	4.595	5.039	-0.4439	2.315
19	Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	4.595	5.356	-0.7606	2.070
20	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	4.595	6.323	-1.727	2.315
21	Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	4.595	7.167	-2.571	2.315
22	Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	4.595	20.85	-16.26	2.070
23	Ctrl vs. Amosite	4.595	21.77	-17.17	2.315

1				
2				
3				
4				
5	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
6	>0.9999	B	Brake:Low	
7	0.9998	C	Brakd:Mid	
8	0.9997	D	Brake:High	
9	0.9995	E	TiO ₂	
10	0.9726	F	Chrysotile:Low	
11	0.8334	G	Chrysotile:High	
12	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
13	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
14				
15	n1	n2	q	DF
16	3	3	0.03693	14
17	3	3	0.1378	14
18	3	2	0.1918	14
19	3	3	0.3674	14
20	3	2	0.7463	14
21	3	2	1.111	14
22	3	3	7.852	14
23	3	2	7.419	14

Percent Connective Tissue Visceral Pleura (CW) - 18 Months

Percent Connective Tissue Parietal Pleura (CW) - 18 Months

S-6 Confocal images of the parietal and visceral pleura
 S-6.1 parietal and visceral pleura at 9 months

S-6.2 parietal and visceral pleura at 12 months

Parietal

Visceral & Parietal

Visceral

Group 1

Group 4

Group 7

Group 8

Group 9

S-6.3 parietal and visceral pleura at 18 months

Parietal

Parietal & Visceral

Visceral

Group 1

Group 4

Group 7

Group 8

Group 9

S-7 Mesothelial Thickness : Visceral and Parietal Pleura

This file can be opened by [GraphPad Prism](#) (version 5.00 or later).

S-7.1 Mesothelial Thickness – 9 months

This file contains 6 data tables and 6 info tables:

- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 9M Meso P New combo:ANOVA results](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 9M Meso P New combo:Multiple comparisons](#)
- [Descriptive statistics of 9M Meso P New combo](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 9M Meso V New combo:ANOVA results](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 9M Meso V New combo:Multiple comparisons](#)
- [Descriptive statistics of 9M Meso V New combo](#)

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 9M_Meso_P_New_combo:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	9M_Meso_P_New_combo				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	63.58				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.9549				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	103 of 384 1.611 (8, 24)				
P value	0.1738				
P value summary	ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	3359	8	419.9	F (8, 24) = 63.58	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	158.5	24	6.605		
Total	3518	32			
Data summary					

Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	33				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 9M_Meso_P_New_combo:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	1.687	-3.875 to 7.250	No	ns	0.9272	B	Brake:Low	
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.7681	-6.331 to 4.794	No	ns	0.9994	C	Brakd:Mid	
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.02354	-5.586 to 5.539	No	ns	>0.9999	D	Brake:High	
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.9889	-6.935 to 4.958	No	ns	0.9971	E	TiO ₂	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-1.174	-6.736 to 4.389	No	ns	0.9900	F	Chrysotile:Low	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-0.8617	-6.808 to 5.085	No	ns	0.9977	G	Chrysotile:High	
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-24.66	-30.22 to -19.10	Yes	****	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
Ctrl vs. Amosite	-22.75	-28.31 to -17.19	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	6.175	4.488	1.687	1.963	3	4	0.8596	24
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	6.175	6.943	-0.7681	1.963	3	4	0.3913	24
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	6.175	6.199	-0.02354	1.963	3	4	0.01199	24
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	6.175	7.164	-0.9889	2.098	3	3	0.4713	24
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	6.175	7.349	-1.174	1.963	3	4	0.5979	24
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	6.175	7.037	-0.8617	2.098	3	3	0.4106	24
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	6.175	30.84	-24.66	1.963	3	4	12.56	24
Ctrl vs. Amosite	6.175	28.92	-22.75	1.963	3	4	11.59	24

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Descriptive statistics of 9M_Meso_P_New_combo

	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of values	3	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	4
Mean	6.175	4.488	6.943	6.199	7.164	7.349	7.037	30.84	28.92
Std. Deviation	0.552	0.2640	1.366	0.6574	0.5237	2.314	3.113	2.692	5.570
Std. Error of Mean	2	0.1320	0.6830	0.3287	0.3024	1.157	1.797	1.346	2.785
	0.318								
Geometric mean	8	4.482	6.833	6.174	7.151	7.003	6.633	30.75	28.51
Geometric SD		1.060	1.236	1.108	1.077	1.465	1.505	1.094	1.218
factor	6.158								
	1.096								

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Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 9M_Meso_V_New_combo:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	9M_Meso_V_New_combo				
Data sets analyzed	A-I, K				
ANOVA summary					
F	28.50				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.9144				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	669.9	9	74.43	F (9, 24) = 28.50	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	62.69	24	2.612		
Total	732.6	33			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	10				
Number of values (total)	34				

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Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 9M_Meso_V_New_combo:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	9							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.6078	-4.176 to 2.960	No	ns	0.9972	B	Brake:Low	
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.8444	-4.412 to 2.723	No	ns	0.9867	C	Brakd:Mid	
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.6815	-4.249 to 2.886	No	ns	0.9965	D	Brake:High	
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-1.076	-4.890 to 2.738	No	ns	0.9615	E	TiO ₂	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-1.139	-4.706 to 2.429	No	ns	0.9273	F	Chrysotile:Low	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-0.01389	-3.828 to 3.800	No	ns	>0.9999	G	Chrysotile:High	

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Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-9.849	-13.42 to -6.281	Yes	****	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
Ctrl vs. Amosite	-12.10	-15.66 to -8.529	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
Ctrl vs. Column K	0.1106	-5.283 to 5.505	No	ns	>0.9999	K	Column K	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	4.524	5.132	-0.6078	1.234	3	4	0.4924	24
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	4.524	5.368	-0.8444	1.234	3	4	0.6841	24
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	4.524	5.205	-0.6815	1.234	3	4	0.5521	24
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	4.524	5.600	-1.076	1.320	3	3	0.8155	24
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	4.524	5.663	-1.139	1.234	3	4	0.9224	24
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	4.524	4.538	-0.01389	1.320	3	3	0.01052	24
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	4.524	14.37	-9.849	1.234	3	4	7.979	24
Ctrl vs. Amosite	4.524	16.62	-12.10	1.234	3	4	9.800	24
Ctrl vs. Column K	4.524	4.413	0.1106	1.866	3	1	0.05924	24

Descriptive statistics of 9M_Meso_V_New_combo

	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite	Data Set-J	Data Set-K
Number of values	3	4	4	4	3	4	3	4	4		1
Mean	4.524	5.132	5.368	5.205	5.600	5.663	4.538	14.37	16.62		4.41
Std. Deviation	0.443	0.4846	0.1879	1.431	0.832	0.3509	0.8784	1.646	3.826		3
Std. Error of Mean	0.256	0.2423	0.09397	0.7156	0.480	0.1755	0.5071	0.8232	1.913		0.00
Geometric mean	2	5.115	5.366	5.076	7	5.654	4.484	14.30	16.31		0.00
Geometric SD factor	4.510	1.097	1.035	1.286	5.559	1.064	1.204	1.126	1.251		0
	1.101				1.161						4.41
											3
											1.00
											0

S-7.2 Mesothelial Thickness – 12 months

This file contains 6 data tables and 6 info tables:

- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M Meso_P per animal:ANOVA results](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M Meso_P per animal:Multiple comparisons](#)
- [Descriptive statistics of 12M Meso_P per animal](#)
- [Descriptive statistics of 12M Meso_V per animal](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M Meso_V per animal:ANOVA results](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M Meso_V per animal:Multiple comparisons](#)

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M Meso_P per animal:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	12M Meso_P per animal				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	26.53				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.8909				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	3.044 (8, 26)				
P value	0.0148				
P value summary	107 of 384 *				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	1137	8	142.1	F (8, 26) = 26.53	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	139.3	26	5.356		
Total	1276	34			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	35				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M Meso_P per animal:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.5138	-5.370 to 4.342	No	ns	0.9996	B	Brake:Low	
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	1.661	-2.800 to 6.122	No	ns	0.8666	C	Brakd:Mid	
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	2.763	-1.697 to 7.224	No	ns	0.4019	D	Brake:High	
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	1.249	-3.212 to 5.709	No	ns	0.9659	E	TiO ₂	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	1.621	-2.840 to 6.081	No	ns	0.8796	F	Chrysotile:Low	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	2.538	-2.318 to 7.394	No	ns	0.5854	G	Chrysotile:High	
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-12.78	-17.24 to -8.316	Yes	****	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
Ctrl vs. Amosite	-11.31	-15.77 to -6.852	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	7.544	8.058	-0.5138	1.690	5	3	0.3040	26
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	7.544	5.883	1.661	1.552	5	4	1.070	26
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	7.544	4.781	2.763	1.552	5	4	1.780	26
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	7.544	6.296	1.249	1.552	5	4	0.8042	26
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	7.544	5.923	1.621	1.552	5	4	1.044	26
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	7.544	5.006	2.538	1.690	5	3	1.502	26
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	7.544	20.32	-12.78	1.552	5	4	8.230	26
Ctrl vs. Amosite	7.544	18.86	-11.31	1.552	5	4	7.287	26

Descriptive statistics of 12M Meso_P per animal

	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of values	5	3	4	4	4	4	3	4	4
Mean	7.544	8.058	5.883	4.781	6.296	5.923	5.006	20.32	18.86
Std. Deviation	1.177	1.157	0.8751	0.9032	3.185	1.123	1.486	3.973	3.665
Std. Error of Mean	0.526	0.6679	0.4376	0.4516	1.593	0.5615	0.8581	1.986	1.832
Geometric mean		8.005	5.831	4.723	5.655	5.831	4.836	20.02	18.59
Geometric SD factor	7.460	1.149	1.171	1.191	1.726	1.237	1.396	1.224	1.214

Descriptive statistics of 12M Meso_V per animal

	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of values	5	4	4	4	4	4	3	4	4
Mean	4.468	5.103	5.026	3.386	4.798	5.147	4.040	11.59	17.70
Std. Deviation	0.828	0.5051	0.4955	0.5665	0.2190	0.3274	0.3216	3.895	4.699
Std. Error of Mean	0.370	0.2526	0.2478	0.2832	0.1095	0.1637	0.1857	1.948	2.350
Geometric mean	6	5.084	5.008	3.349	4.794	5.139	4.032	11.17	17.23
Geometric SD factor	4.407	1.104	1.103	1.191	1.047	1.066	1.083	1.354	1.304
	1.206								

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M Meso_V per animal:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	12M Meso_V per animal				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	20.50				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.8586				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	4.028 (8, 27)				
P value	0.0029				
P value summary	**				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
Bartlett's test	109 of 384				
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	714.5	8	89.31	F (8, 27) = 20.50	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	117.7	27	4.358		
Total	832.2	35			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	36				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 12M Meso_V per animal:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.6340	-4.642 to 3.374	No	ns	0.9977	B	Brake:Low	
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	-0.5574	-4.566 to 3.451	No	ns	0.9994	C	Brakd:Mid	
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	1.082	-2.926 to 5.091	No	ns	0.9719	D	Brake:High	
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.3290	-4.337 to 3.679	No	ns	0.9997	E	TiO ₂	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-0.6782	-4.687 to 3.330	No	ns	0.9974	F	Chrysotile:Low	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	0.4280	-3.936 to 4.792	No	ns	0.9996	G	Chrysotile:High	
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-7.125	-11.13 to -3.116	Yes	***	0.0002	H	Crocidolite	
Ctrl vs. Amosite	-13.23	-17.24 to -9.219	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	4.468	5.103	-0.6340	1.400	5	4	0.4528	27
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	4.468	5.026	-0.5574	1.400	5	4	0.3980	27
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	4.468	3.386	1.082	1.400	5	4	0.7729	27
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	4.468	4.798	-0.3290	1.400	5	4	0.2350	27
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	4.468	5.147	-0.6782	1.400	5	4	0.4843	27
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	4.468	4.040	0.4280	1.525	5	3	0.2808	27
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	4.468	11.59	-7.125	1.400	5	4	5.088	27
Ctrl vs. Amosite	4.468	17.70	-13.23	1.400	5	4	9.446	27

S-7.3 Mesothelial Thickness – 18 months

This file contains 6 data tables and 6 info tables:

- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M Meso P New:ANOVA results](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M Meso P New:Multiple comparisons](#)
- [Descriptive statistics of 18M Meso P New](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M Meso V New:ANOVA results](#)
- [Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M Meso V New:Multiple comparisons](#)
- [Descriptive statistics of 18M Meso V New](#)

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M_Meso_P_New:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	18M_Meso_P_New				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	23.15				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.9297				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	0.8767 (8, 14)				
P value	0.5581				
P value summary	111 of 384 ns				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	No				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	827.1	8	103.4	F (8, 14) = 23.15	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	62.52	14	4.466		
Total	889.6	22			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	23				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M_Meso_P_New:Multiple comparisons

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	-0.7792	-6.042 to 4.484	No	ns	0.9976	B	Brake:Low	
Ctrl vs. Brake:Med	-0.4192	-5.682 to 4.844	No	ns	0.9997	C	Brake:Med	
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-1.045	-6.929 to 4.839	No	ns	0.9946	D	Brake:High	
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.3108	-5.574 to 4.952	No	ns	0.9997	E	TiO ₂	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-0.7079	-6.592 to 5.176	No	ns	0.9995	F	Chrysotile:Low	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-1.556	-7.440 to 4.328	No	ns	0.9590	G	Chrysotile:High	
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-15.21	-20.48 to -9.951	Yes	****	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
Ctrl vs. Amosite	-14.99	-20.87 to -9.105	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	Amosite	
Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	4.788	5.567	-0.7792	1.725	3	3	0.4516	14
Ctrl vs. Brake:Med	4.788	5.207	-0.4192	1.725	3	3	0.2429	14
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	4.788	5.833	-1.045	1.929	3	2	0.5417	14
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	4.788	5.098	-0.3108	1.725	3	3	0.1801	14
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	4.788	5.495	-0.7079	1.929	3	2	0.3670	14
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	4.788	6.344	-1.556	1.929	3	2	0.8068	14
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	4.788	20.00	-15.21	1.725	3	3	8.817	14
Ctrl vs. Amosite	4.788	19.78	-14.99	1.929	3	2	7.770	14

Descriptive statistics of 18M_Meso_P_New

	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brake:Med	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of values	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	3	2
Mean	4.788	5.567	5.207	5.833	5.098	5.495	6.344	20.00	19.78
Std. Deviation	1.099	0.3003	0.2926	0.06482	0.1478	0.4555	0.8657	5.029	2.859
Std. Error of Mean	0.634	0.1734	0.1690	0.04583	0.0853	0.3221	0.6122	2.903	2.022
Geometric mean		5.561	5.201	5.832		5.486	6.314	19.53	19.67
Geometric SD factor	4.699	1.055	1.057	1.011	5.097	1.087	1.147	1.318	1.156

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M_Meso_V_New:ANOVA results

	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E
Table Analyzed	18M_Meso_V_New				
Data sets analyzed	A-I				
ANOVA summary					
F	125.5				
P value	<0.0001				
P value summary	****				
Significant diff. among means (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
R squared	0.9863				
Brown-Forsythe test					
F (DFn, DFd)	5.605 (8, 14)				
P value	0.0026				
P value summary	**				
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?	Yes				
Bartlett's test					
Bartlett's statistic (corrected)					
P value					
P value summary					
Are SDs significantly different (P < 0.05)?					
ANOVA table	SS	DF	MS	F (DFn, DFd)	P value
Treatment (between columns)	795.8	8	99.48	F (8, 14) = 125.5	P<0.0001
Residual (within columns)	11.09	14	0.7924		
Total	806.9	22			
Data summary					
Number of treatments (columns)	9				
Number of values (total)	23				

Ordinary one-way ANOVA of 18M_Meso_V_New:Multiple comparisons

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	Data Set-A	Data Set-B	Data Set-C	Data Set-D	Data Set-E	Data Set-F	Data Set-G	Data Set-H
Number of families	1							
Number of comparisons per family	8							
Alpha	0.05							
Dunnett's multiple comparisons test	Mean Diff.	95.00% CI of diff.	Below threshold?	Summary	Adjusted P Value	A-?		
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	0.3289	-1.888 to 2.546	No	ns	0.9976	B	Brake:Low	
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	0.5267	-1.690 to 2.743	No	ns	0.9766	C	Brakd:Mid	
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	-0.5031	-2.982 to 1.975	No	ns	0.9910	D	Brake:High	
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	-0.3494	-2.566 to 1.867	No	ns	0.9973	E	TiO ₂	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	-0.5968	-3.075 to 1.882	No	ns	0.9748	F	Chrysotile:Low	
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	-0.4226	-2.901 to 2.056	No	ns	0.9956	G	Chrysotile:High	
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	-14.46	-16.68 to -12.25	Yes	****	<0.0001	H	Crocidolite	
Ctrl vs. Amosite	-14.10	-16.58 to -11.62	Yes	****	<0.0001	I	Amosite	

Test details	Mean 1	Mean 2	Mean Diff.	SE of diff.	n1	n2	q	DF
Ctrl vs. Brake:Low	4.704	4.376	0.3289	0.7268	3	3	0.4525	14
Ctrl vs. Brakd:Mid	4.704	4.178	0.5267	0.7268	3	3	0.7246	14
Ctrl vs. Brake:High	4.704	5.208	-0.5031	0.8126	3	2	0.6191	14
Ctrl vs. TiO ₂	4.704	5.054	-0.3494	0.7268	3	3	0.4808	14
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:Low	4.704	5.301	-0.5968	0.8126	3	2	0.7344	14
Ctrl vs. Chrysotile:High	4.704	5.127	-0.4226	0.8126	3	2	0.5201	14
Ctrl vs. Crocidolite	4.704	19.17	-14.46	0.7268	3	3	19.90	14
Ctrl vs. Amosite	4.704	18.81	-14.10	0.8126	3	2	17.35	14

Descriptive statistics of 18M_Meso_V_New

	Ctrl	Brake:Low	Brakd:Mid	Brake:High	TiO ₂	Chrysotile:Low	Chrysotile:High	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of values	3	3	3	2	3	2	2	3	2
Mean	4.704	4.376	4.178	5.208	5.054	5.301	5.127	19.17	18.81
Std. Deviation	0.448	0.3771	0.08181	0.2227	0.4791	0.05127	0.5368	0.7783	2.895
Std. Error of Mean	0	0.2177	0.04723	0.1575	0.2766	0.03625	0.3796	0.4494	2.047
Geometric mean	6	4.365	4.177	5.205	5.039	5.301	5.113	19.16	18.69
Geometric SD factor	4.691	1.088	1.020	1.044	1.097	1.010	1.111	1.041	1.167
	1.097								

S-8 Particle and fiber lung burdens at 45, 89, 180 and 450 days

Group	Time days	N	Mean Total Particles & Fibers per Lung*	No Particles per lung* (Means)	No Particles per lung* (Std.Dev.)	No Fibers L<5 µm/lung* (Means)	No Fibers L<5 µm/lung* (Std.Dev.)	No Fibers L 5-20 µm/lung (Means)	No Fibers L 5-20 µm/lung (Std.Dev.)	No Fibers L>20 µm/lung (Means)	No Fibers L>20 µm/lung (Std.Dev.)	Total No Fibers/lung (Means)	Total No Fibers/lung (Std.Dev.)	Number of fibers L>20µm evaluated (Means)	Number of fibers L>20µm evaluated (Std.Dev.)
1	45	4	13,688,058	13,666,911	6,192,211	21,147	42,293	0	0	0	0	21,147	42,293	0.0	0.0
1	89	4	100,499,970	100,052,367	19,561,163	437,030	434,826	10,573	13,498	0	0	447,603	430,751	0.0	0.0
1	180	4	13,622,397	13,622,397	4,995,982	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
1	450	4	239,863,203	239,834,986	141,709,447	21,163	14,109	7,054	14,109	0	0	28,218	23,040	0.0	0.0
2	45	4	27,346,491	25,610,138	15,498,101	1,667,620	1,712,790	68,734	46,885	0	0	1,736,353	1,755,224	0.0	0.0
2	89	4	83,966,629	81,390,552	12,957,528	2,299,409	1,666,369	276,668	127,059	0	0	2,576,077	1,789,826	0.0	0.0
2	180	4	43,094,886	41,922,565	16,019,717	1,094,783	636,266	77,538	58,975	0	0	1,172,320	690,679	0.0	0.0
2	450	4	29,303,617	29,243,701	5,629,145	54,629	29,558	5,287	3,524	0	0	59,915	30,725	0.0	0.0
3	45	4	116,825,994	107,240,838	88,852,912	8,837,937	8,726,879	740,170	456,670	7,049	8,139	9,585,156	9,136,046	0.5	0.6
3	89	4	81,525,249	66,988,533	24,258,288	13,148,088	8,656,099	1,385,103	782,509	3,524	7,049	14,536,716	9,382,432	0.3	0.5
3	180	4	50,730,283	47,573,371	12,765,186	2,818,566	706,053	338,346	157,932	0	0	3,156,912	849,865	0.0	0.0
3	450	4	36,215,048	36,082,882	12,196,211	107,495	19,411	24,671	12,209	0	0	132,166	25,979	0.0	0.0
4	45	4	94,665,097	85,834,451	62,028,229	8,305,482	7,428,374	516,350	341,215	8,815	17,629	8,830,646	7,756,653	0.6	1.3
4	89	4	111,445,657	86,389,501	53,366,285	24,065,790	17,213,984	986,842	344,891	3,524	4,070	25,056,157	17,541,997	0.3	0.3
4	180	4	35,604,231	33,915,774	15,338,289	1,621,493	1,354,047	66,964	35,711	0	0	1,688,457	1,385,847	0.0	0.0
4	450	3	27,058,825	26,906,099	2,196,254	112,782	14,098	39,944	14,673	0	0	152,726	22,659	0.0	0.0
5	45	4	130,894,782	128,594,338	28,770,242	2,081,864	318,183	215,054	133,506	3,526	7,052	2,300,444	243,295	0.3	0.5
5	89	4	206,101,386	205,563,910	63,746,984	521,617	379,855	15,860	3,524	0	0	537,477	382,478	0.0	0.0
5	180	4	270,870,748	270,870,748	67,073,594	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0.0	0.0
5	450	4	47,278,693	47,158,862	17,703,076	98,684	26,374	21,147	9,969	0	0	119,831	35,942	0.0	0.0
6	45	4	39,046,871	21,539,555	18,012,464	15,369,061	6,608,316	2,037,353	1,136,607	100,902	95,506	17,507,316	7,458,502	6.1	4.8
6	89	4	214,837,028	161,572,872	26,747,642	44,427,393	19,172,220	8,632,346	2,897,209	204,417	55,503	53,264,157	21,662,105	14.5	3.9
6	180	4	35,305,196	29,072,682	14,889,788	5,279,154	1,204,772	939,262	200,645	14,098	17,266	6,232,514	1,341,554	1.0	1.2
6	450	3	196,122,827	178,043,969	130,640,531	17,040,136	18,453,168	994,070	1,021,098	44,652	45,859	18,078,858	19,519,933	3.2	3.3
7	45	4	88,327,864	80,160,359	10,707,756	6,582,638	2,770,831	1,542,558	913,666	42,310	38,624	8,167,505	3,719,141	3.0	2.7
7	89	4	202,979,662	136,106,871	55,960,256	55,185,649	19,668,180	11,396,376	3,777,121	290,766	102,209	66,872,791	23,297,727	20.6	7.3
7	180	4	56,277,974	45,707,923	3,644,568	7,959,569	982,617	2,555,853	293,921	54,629	12,038	10,570,051	1,245,595	3.9	0.9
7	450	4	297,669,267	267,160,921	202,577,188	29,035,743	19,874,832	1,400,296	266,733	72,307	29,015	30,508,346	20,106,319	5.1	2.1
8	45	4	127,133,665	71,573,189	10,874,609	31,181,347	12,383,010	19,467,307	4,052,912	4,911,822	1,116,617	55,560,476	16,789,148	100.3	0.3

8	89	4	149,661,491	81,469,637	40,753,319	30,332,700	10,930,900	28,804,511	7,759,368	9,054,643	2,346,361	68,191,854	18,737,437	100.0	0.0
8	180	4	169,720,207	103,913,127	15,227,848	32,798,090	14,654,318	24,982,381	6,178,706	8,026,610	1,478,047	65,807,081	20,035,578	100.0	0.0
8	450	4	208,571,231	165,800,937	62,131,458	9,631,220	4,030,316	22,588,918	5,406,220	10,550,156	3,223,858	42,770,294	9,456,822	100.3	0.3
9	45	4	156,007,870	71,608,577	39,837,101	47,423,543	18,658,078	29,911,831	4,837,534	7,063,919	864,375	84,399,293	23,651,289	100.0	0.0
9	89	4	231,798,633	121,630,205	20,188,445	57,729,698	16,011,772	40,793,714	6,406,276	11,645,015	1,382,871	110,168,427	22,299,391	100.0	0.0
9	180	4	218,787,417	123,477,445	48,299,890	39,715,436	19,757,145	44,003,423	5,895,677	11,591,113	1,121,689	95,309,972	24,729,062	100.6	0.5
9	450	4	554,099,190	475,018,668	115,352,039	28,917,533	7,505,216	39,487,304	14,388,626	10,675,685	2,180,981	79,080,522	15,984,096	100.1	0.3

* It should be noted that the number of particles and short fibers included debris from the lung ashing as well as exposure related particles and fibers.

S-9 Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

For Study: 02G16015
Title: Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat
Requested By: Heinrich Ernst
Job Number: 46282
Animal Reference: Animal Name
Animals Excluded: 1010, 1011, 1012, 1013, 1020, 1021, 1022, 1023, 1030, 1031, 1032, 1033, 1050, 1051, 1052, 1053, 1060, 1061, 1062, 1063, 1070, 1071, 1072, 1073, 1080, 1081, 1082, 1083, 1084, 1085, 1086, 1087, 1088, 1089, 1090, 1091, 1092, 1093, 1094, 1095, 1096, 1097, 1098, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2020, 2021, 2022, + others.

Day Numbers: All
Groups: All
Observation Type: Histo - Neoplastic and Non-Neoplastic
Observation Summary: Incidence
Report Format: Group within Sex
Tissues: All
Rationalisation: Day_45
Removal Reasons: All
Completed Animals Only: No
Animals with Observations Only: No
Major Pathological Findings Only: No
Split Observations by: GRADE
Split Table by: Sex
Use Alternative Descriptions: No
Repeat First Group on Each Page: No
Style: Landscape - 12 Columns
Include: NVL Tissues; NE Tissues; Neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; TUMOUR TYPE; ORIGIN; CLASSIFICATION; Non-neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; SIZE

S-9.1 Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
hematopoietic tissue						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lymphoma, [M]: malignant						
larynx						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	3	4	3	4
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0	0	0	0
..... present, no grade	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	1	0	1	0
..... very slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
..... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
liver						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells						
..... present, no grade						
lung						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
..... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0

¹ [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	4 f ⁺				
.... very slight	0 ¹	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	3	4 f ⁺
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
Fibrosis, Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Fibrosis, Pleural	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
Giant Cells, Syncytial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	1 ¹	0	0	0	0	2
.... very slight	1 ⁺	0	0	0	0	2
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell	0	1	0	1	0	0
.... very slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... present, no grade	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	0 ^{c+}	1	1	1	0	1
.... very slight	0	1	1	1	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Pleural	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Perivascular	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
Microgranuloma	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	2
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	2
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 2	0 ¹	4 ^{f+}	4 ^{f+}	4 ^{f+}	4 ^{f+}	2

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
Wagner Grade 3	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	2
Wagner Grade 4	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 1	4 ¹	0 f ⁺				
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0	0	0	0	1	1
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	1	1
lung associated lymph nodes (Ialn)						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	3	2	3	2
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	0	1	1	1	1	1
.... very slight	0	1	1	1	1	1
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid	0	1	0	1	0	1
.... slight	0	1	0	1	0	1
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... present, no grade	0	0	0	0	0	0
lymph node, nos						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lymph node, nos (Continued...)						
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells						
.... present, no grade						
nasal cavity						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4	4	4	4
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... present, no grade	0	0	0	0	0	0
nasopharynx						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4	4	4	4
spleen						
Examined	0	0	0	0	1	0
Extramedullary Hematopoiesis					1	
.... severe					1	
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells					0	
.... present, no grade					0	
trachea						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	3	1	4	4

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
trachea (Continued...)						
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	0 c ¹	0	1	3	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	1	2	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	1	0	0

1 [c - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
hematopoietic tissue			
Examined	0	1	0
Lymphoma, [M]; malignant		1	
larynx			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	3
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	1	0
.... present, no grade	0	1	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0
liver			
Examined	0	1	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells		1	
.... present, no grade		1	
lung			
Examined	4	4	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	2	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... slight	0	2	4 f ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	4 f ¹	0	0
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Fibrosis, Interstitial	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Fibrosis, Pleural	0	1	1
.... very slight	0	1	1
.... slight	0	0	0
Giant Cells, Syncytial	1	3	4 f ¹
.... very slight	1	3	4 f ¹
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	4	4	4
.... very slight	4	0	0
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	1	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... present, no grade	0	1	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... slight	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	4 f ¹	3
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	2	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	2	3	3
.... slight	0	1	1
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Pleural	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	3	0
.... slight	0	1	4 f ¹
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Perivascular	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Microgranuloma	4 f ¹	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Wagner Grade 2	0	0	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
Wagner Grade 3	4 f ¹	0	0
Wagner Grade 4	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Wagner Grade 1	0 f ¹	0 f ¹	0 f ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (ln)			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	2	1
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid	0	1	2
.... slight	0	1	2
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	1	0
.... present, no grade	0	1	0
lymph node, nos			
Examined	0	1	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lymph node, nos (Continued...)			
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells		1	
.... present, no grade		1	
nasal cavity			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	4
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	1	0
.... present, no grade	0	1	0
nasopharynx			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4
spleen			
Examined	0	1	0
Extramedullary Hematopoiesis		0	
.... severe		0	
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells		1	
.... present, no grade		1	
trachea			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl

Removal Reason: ALL	Male			
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite	
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	
trachea (Continued...)				
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	0	
.... very slight	0	0	0	
.... slight	0	0	0	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	2	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	3	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	2	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	3	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	2	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	3	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 2	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 3	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 4	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 1	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	2	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	3	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	trachea : Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	c
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Microgranuloma	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Microgranuloma, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Wagner Grade 3	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 4	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 4	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Key Page

Measurement/Statistics

<u>Measurement</u>	<u>Descriptive</u>	<u>Comparative</u>	<u>Arithmetic/Adjusted</u>	<u>Transformation</u>
Pathology Observation	Count Positives	Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact		

Group Information

<u>Short Name</u>	<u>Long Name</u>	<u>Report Headings</u>	
1	Clean air	Clean air	control
2	brake dust low	brake dust	low
3	brake dust mid	Brake dust	mid
4	brake dust high	Brake dust	high
5	Particel Control	Titanium-	dioxide
6	Chrysotile low	Chrysotile	low
7	Chrysotile high	Chrysotile	high
8	Crocidolite	Crocido-	lite
9	Amosite	Amosite	

Removal Reason Grouping

<u>Grouping Name</u>	<u>Abbreviation</u>	<u>Removal Reasons</u>
Killed - Terminal Kill	TeKi	Killed - Terminal Kill
Killed - Moribund	US	Killed - Moribund
Found Dead	FD	Found Dead

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Key Page**Rationalisation Details**

Rationalisation: Day_45

Merges

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, focal, very slight

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, focal, very slight

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Microgranuloma, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Microgranuloma, focal, very slight

lung, Microgranuloma, multifocal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, multifocal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, multifocal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, multifocal, very slight

Edits

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Key Page**Edits (Continued)**

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, focal, slight

lung, Fibrosis, Interstitial, interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, Pleural, pleural, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, pleural, focal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, Pleural, pleural, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, pleural, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl)

Key Page

Edits (Continued)

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, perivascular, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Pleural, pleural, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, pleural, focal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, peribronchiolar, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, peribronchiolar, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, focal, slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 45
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-onl

End Of Print

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

For Study: 02G16015
Title: Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat
Requested By: Heinrich Ernst
Job Number: 46658
Animal Reference: Animal Name
Animals Excluded: 1000, 1001, 1002, 1003, 1020, 1021, 1022, 1023, 1030, 1031, 1032, 1033, 1050, 1051, 1052, 1053, 1060, 1061, 1062, 1063, 1070, 1071, 1072, 1073, 1080, 1081, 1082, 1083, 1084, 1085, 1086, 1087, 1088, 1089, 1090, 1091, 1092, 1093, 1094, 1095, 1096, 1097, 1098, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2020, 2021, 2022, + others.

Day Numbers: All
Groups: All
Observation Type: Histo - Neoplastic and Non-Neoplastic
Observation Summary: Incidence
Report Format: Group within Sex
Tissues: LARYNX; LUNG; LUNG ASSOCIATED LYMPH NODES (LALN); NASAL CAVITY; NASOPHARYNX; TRACHEA
Rationalisation: Day_90
Removal Reasons: All
Completed Animals Only: No
Animals with Observations Only: No
Major Pathological Findings Only: No
Split Observations by: GRADE
Split Table by: Sex
Use Alternative Descriptions: No
Repeat First Group on Each Page: No
Style: Landscape - 12 Columns
Include: NVL Tissues; NE Tissues; Neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; TUMOUR TYPE; ORIGIN; CLASSIFICATION; Non-neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; SIZE

S-9.2 Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
larynx						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	3	4	4	4
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	4 f ⁺				
.... very slight	0 ¹	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	3	4 f ⁺
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
Fibrosis, Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
Fibrosis, Pleural	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Giant Cells, Syncytial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hemorrhage, Alveolar	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	0 ¹	0	1	1	0	4 ^{f†}
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	1	1	0	4 ^{f†}
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell	0	0	0	1	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	0 ^{c+}	2	2	0	2	3
.... very slight	0 ^{c+}	2	2	0	2	3

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	1	3
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	1	3
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar	2	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Microgranuloma(s)	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	4 f ⁺
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	4 f ⁺
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 2	0 ¹	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	0
Wagner Grade 3	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	4 f ⁺
Wagner Grade 4	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 1	4 ¹	0 f ⁺				
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (laln)						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	3	3	3	2

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (ln) (Continued...)						
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	0	0	1	1	1	2
.... very slight	0	0	1	1	1	2
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
nasal cavity						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4	4	4	4
Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory Epithelial	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
nasopharynx						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4	4	4	4
trachea						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	4	4	4	4	4
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0

1 [cc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
trachea (Continued...) slight	0	0	0	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
larynx			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	3	2
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	1	1	1
.... very slight	0	1	1
.... slight	1	0	0
lung			
Examined	4	4	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	4 f ¹	0	0
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Fibrosis, Interstitial	2	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	2	3	0
.... slight	0	1	4 f ¹

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
Fibrosis, Pleural	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
Giant Cells, Syncytial	1	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	1	4 f ¹	2
.... slight	0	0	2
Hemorrhage, Alveolar	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	4 f ¹	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	1	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	1	3	3
.... slight	0	1	1
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	3	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	3	4 f ¹	4 f ¹

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	4 f ¹	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Microgranuloma(s)	2	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	2	0	0
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Wagner Grade 2	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 3	2	0	0
Wagner Grade 4	2	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Wagner Grade 1	0 f ¹	0 f ¹	0 f ¹
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0	1	1
.... very slight	0	1	1
lung associated lymph nodes (ln)			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	1	2

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (ln) (Continued...)			
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0	3	2
.... very slight	0	3	2
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid	0	1	2
.... slight	0	1	2
nasal cavity			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	3
Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory Epithelial	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
nasopharynx			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4
trachea			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	4
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Removal Reason: ALL	Male			
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite	
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	
trachea (Continued...) slight	0	1	0	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	2	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	3	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	2	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	3	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma(s) <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : Microgranuloma(s) <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma(s), very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	6	lung : Microgranuloma(s), very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma(s), slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	2	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	3	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 3 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 3 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 4 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	2	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	3	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, very slight	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	7	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma(s)	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma(s)	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma(s), slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma(s), slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 4	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 4	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Key Page

Measurement/Statistics

<u>Measurement</u>	<u>Descriptive</u>	<u>Comparative</u>	<u>Arithmetic/Adjusted</u>	<u>Transformation</u>
Pathology Observation	Count Positives	Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact		

Group Information

<u>Short Name</u>	<u>Long Name</u>	<u>Report Headings</u>	
1	Clean air	Clean air	control
2	brake dust low	brake dust	low
3	brake dust mid	Brake dust	mid
4	brake dust high	Brake dust	high
5	Particel Control	Titanium-	dioxide
6	Chrysotile low	Chrysotile	low
7	Chrysotile high	Chrysotile	high
8	Crocidolite	Crocido-	lite
9	Amosite	Amosite	

Removal Reason Grouping

<u>Grouping Name</u>	<u>Abbreviation</u>	<u>Removal Reasons</u>
Killed - Terminal Kill	TeKi	Killed - Terminal Kill
Killed - Moribund	US	Killed - Moribund
Found Dead	FD	Found Dead

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Key Page

Rationalisation Details

Rationalisation: Day_90

Merges

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, focal, very slight

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, peribronchiolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, multifocal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, peribronchiolar, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, multifocal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, multifocal, very slight

lung, Microgranuloma(s), focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Microgranuloma, focal, very slight

lung, Microgranuloma, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, multifocal, very slight

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, focal, very slight

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, multifocal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, multifocal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, multifocal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

Edits

larynx, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Key Page**Edits (Continued)**

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, focal, slight
lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight
lung, Hemorrhage, Alveolar, alveolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Hemorrhage, alveolar, focal, very slight
lung, Fibrosis, Interstitial, interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, multifocal, very slight
lung, Fibrosis, Interstitial, interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, multifocal, slight
lung, Fibrosis, Pleural, pleural, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, pleural, focal, very slight
lung, Fibrosis, Pleural, pleural, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, pleural, focal, slight
lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, focal, slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

Key Page

Edits (Continued)

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Pleural, pleural, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, pleural, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, perivascular, focal, very slight

lung, Microgranuloma(s), multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Microgranuloma, multifocal, slight

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory Epithelial, olfactory epithelial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, olfactory epithelial, multifocal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations, Day 89
(score expansion)

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study

End Of Print

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

For Study: 02G16015
Title: Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat
Requested By: Heinrich Ernst
Job Number: 47540
Animal Reference: Animal Name
Animals Excluded: 1000, 1001, 1002, 1003, 1010, 1011, 1012, 1013, 1030, 1031, 1032, 1033, 1050, 1051, 1052, 1053, 1060, 1061, 1062, 1063, 1070, 1071, 1072, 1073, 1080, 1081, 1082, 1083, 1084, 1085, 1086, 1087, 1088, 1089, 1090, 1091, 1092, 1093, 1094, 1095, 1096, 1097, 1098, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2010, 2011, 2012, + others.

Day Numbers: All
Groups: All
Observation Type: Histo - Neoplastic and Non-Neoplastic
Observation Summary: Incidence
Report Format: Group within Sex
Tissues: All
Rationalisation: 3M_PE
Removal Reasons: All
Completed Animals Only: No
Animals with Observations Only: No
Major Pathological Findings Only: No
Split Observations by: GRADE
Split Table by: Sex
Use Alternative Descriptions: No
Repeat First Group on Each Page: No
Style: Landscape - 12 Columns
Include: NVL Tissues; NE Tissues; Neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; TUMOUR TYPE; ORIGIN; CLASSIFICATION; Non-neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; SIZE

S-9.3 Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations 3 months

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
larynx						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	3	4	1	2	3
Hemorrhage, Subepithelial	1	1	0	1	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0	1	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0	0	1	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	1	0	0	2	1	1
.... very slight	1	0	0	2	1	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	4 f ⁺				
.... very slight	0 ¹	4 f ⁺				
Fibrosis, Interstitial	0 ¹	1	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... very slight	0 ¹	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Fibrosis, Pleural	0	1	0	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0	0	1	0
Giant Cells, Syncytial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	1 ¹	0	2	0	1	4
.... very slight	1 ¹	0	2	0	1	4
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ^{c+}	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	0 ¹	3	0	2	0	4 ^f
.... very slight	0 ^{c+}	3	0	2	0	4 ^f
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Pleural	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	2
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	2
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Microgranuloma	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	3
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	3
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 2	0 ¹	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	0
Wagner Grade 3	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	4 f ⁺
Wagner Grade 4	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 1	4 ¹	0 f ⁺				
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0 ¹	2	3	2	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺
.... very slight	0 ¹	2	3	2	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (Iain)						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	1	1	0	2	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	0 ⁺	3	3	3	2	4 ^{ft}
.... very slight	0 ⁺	3	3	3	2	4 ^{ft}
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid	0	0	0	2	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	2	0	1
nasal cavity						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	2	3	3	3	3
Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory Epithelial	1	2	1	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... slight	1	2	0	0	1	0
Droplets, Hyaline, Respiratory Epithelial	1	2	1	0	1	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
nasal cavity (Continued...)						
.... very slight	1	2	1	0	1	0
Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	1	1	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	1	1	0	0
Hyperplasia, Nalt	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
nasopharynx						
Examined	4	4	4	3	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4	3	4	4
prostate						
Examined	1	0	0	0	0	0
Inflammation; purulent	1					
.... severe	1					
skin/subcutaneous tissue						
Examined	0	0	0	1	0	0
Abscess, Subcutaneous				1		
.... severe				1		

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
trachea						
Examined	4	4	4	3	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	3	3	3	4
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	0	1	1	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	1	0	1	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
larynx			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	3	2
Hemorrhage, Subepithelial	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	1	1	2
.... very slight	1	1	1
.... slight	0	0	1
lung			
Examined	4	4	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	4 f ¹	0	0
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
Fibrosis, Interstitial	4 f ¹	4 f ¹	4 f ¹

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido-lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Fibrosis, Pleural	1	1	2
.... very slight	1	1	2
Giant Cells, Syncytial	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	3	0
.... slight	0	1	4 f ¹
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	4	4	4
.... very slight	4	0	0
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	1	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	1	3	2
.... slight	0	1	2
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	2	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	2	3	2
.... slight	0	1	2

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Pleural	1	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	4 f ¹	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Microgranuloma	4 f ¹	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Wagner Grade 2	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 3	4 f ¹	0	0
Wagner Grade 4	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Wagner Grade 1	0 f ¹	0 f ¹	0 f ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	4 f ¹	0	0
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0	3	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	2	4 f ¹

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... slight	0	1	0
lung associated lymph nodes (laln)			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	1	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	2	4 f ¹
.... slight	0	2	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	3	0	0
.... very slight	3	0	0
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid	0	1	1
.... slight	0	1	1
nasal cavity			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	1
Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory Epithelial	0	1	2
.... very slight	0	0	2
.... slight	0	1	0
Droplets, Hyaline, Respiratory Epithelial	0	1	3

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
nasal cavity (Continued...)			
.... very slight	0	1	3
Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Nalt	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
nasopharynx			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4
prostate			
Examined	0	0	0
Inflammation; purulent			
.... severe			
skin/subcutaneous tissue			
Examined	0	0	0
Abscess, Subcutaneous			
.... severe			

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
trachea			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	3	3
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	1	1	1
.... very slight	1	1	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	2	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	3	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	2	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	3	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	6	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma, very slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma, slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 2	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	2	lung : Wagner Grade 2	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	3	lung : Wagner Grade 2	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 2	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 2	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 3	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 3	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 4	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 1	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	2	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	3	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	6	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	6	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Microgranuloma <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Microgranuloma, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Wagner Grade 3 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 4 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 4 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	7	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Key Page

Measurement/Statistics

<u>Measurement</u>	<u>Descriptive</u>	<u>Comparative</u>	<u>Arithmetic/Adjusted</u>	<u>Transformation</u>
Pathology Observation	Count Positives	Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact		

Group Information

<u>Short Name</u>	<u>Long Name</u>	<u>Report Headings</u>	
1	Clean air	Clean air	control
2	brake dust low	brake dust	low
3	brake dust mid	Brake dust	mid
4	brake dust high	Brake dust	high
5	Particel Control	Titanium-	dioxide
6	Chrysotile low	Chrysotile	low
7	Chrysotile high	Chrysotile	high
8	Crocidolite	Crocido-	lite
9	Amosite	Amosite	

Removal Reason Grouping

<u>Grouping Name</u>	<u>Abbreviation</u>	<u>Removal Reasons</u>
Killed - Terminal Kill	TeKi	Killed - Terminal Kill
Killed - Moribund	US	Killed - Moribund
Found Dead	FD	Found Dead

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Key Page**Rationalisation Details**

Rationalisation: 3M_PE

Merges

larynx, Hemorrhage, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Hemorrhage, subepithelial, focal, very slight

larynx, Hemorrhage, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, Interstitial, interstitial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, focal, very slight

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, focal, very slight

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, peribronchiolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, peribronchiolar, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, multifocal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, focal, slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, multifocal, slight

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, focal, very slight

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Microgranuloma, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Microgranuloma, focal, very slight

lung, Microgranuloma, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, multifocal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (laln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung associated lymph nodes (laln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (laln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, multifocal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (laln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung associated lymph nodes (laln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (laln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, multifocal, very slight

nasal cavity, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

nasal cavity, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

Edits

larynx, Hemorrhage, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Hemorrhage, subepithelial, focal, slight

larynx, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Key Page**Edits (Continued)**

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

lung, Hemorrhage, Alveolar, alveolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Hemorrhage, alveolar, focal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, Interstitial, interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, multifocal, slight

lung, Fibrosis, Pleural, pleural, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, pleural, focal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, Pleural, pleural, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, pleural, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Pleural, pleural, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

Key Page**Edits (Continued)**

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, pleural, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, perivascular, focal, very slight

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory Epithelial, olfactory epithelial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, olfactory epithelial, multifocal, very slight

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory Epithelial, olfactory epithelial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, olfactory epithelial, multifocal, slight

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, Respiratory Epithelial, respiratory epithelial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, respiratory epithelial, multifocal, very slight

skin/subcutaneous tissue, Abscess, Subcutaneous, subcutaneous, focal, severe

Is used to report the following findings:

skin/subcutaneous tissue, Abscess(Es), subcutaneous, focal, severe

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 3 months post exposure

End Of Print

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

For Study: 02G16015
Title: Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat
Requested By: Heinrich Ernst
Job Number: 47665
Animal Reference: Animal Name
Animals Excluded: 1000, 1001, 1002, 1003, 1010, 1011, 1012, 1013, 1020, 1021, 1022, 1023, 1050, 1051, 1052, 1053, 1060, 1061, 1062, 1063, 1070, 1071, 1072, 1073, 1080, 1081, 1082, 1083, 1084, 1085, 1086, 1087, 1088, 1089, 1090, 1091, 1092, 1093, 1094, 1095, 1096, 1097, 1098, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2010, 2011, 2012, + others.

Day Numbers: All
Groups: All
Observation Type: Histo - Neoplastic and Non-Neoplastic
Observation Summary: Incidence
Report Format: Group within Sex
Tissues: All
Rationalisation: 6M_PE
Removal Reasons: All
Completed Animals Only: No
Animals with Observations Only: No
Major Pathological Findings Only: No
Split Observations by: GRADE
Split Table by: Sex
Use Alternative Descriptions: No
Repeat First Group on Each Page: No
Style: Landscape - 12 Columns
Include: NVL Tissues; NE Tissues; Neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; TUMOUR TYPE; ORIGIN; CLASSIFICATION; Non-neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; SIZE

S-9.4 Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations 6 months

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
larynx						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	3	2	3	4	4
Dilatation, Submucosal Glands	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
Hemorrhage, Subepithelial	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	1	0	2	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	2	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	3	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺
.... very slight	0 ¹	3	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	3	4 f ⁺
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
Fibrosis, Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	1
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	1
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Fibrosis, Pleural	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Giant Cells, Syncytial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	0 ⁺	1	2	1	1	4 ^{ft}
.... very slight	0	1	2	1	1	3
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	1
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	0 ⁺	1	1	1	1	4 ^{ft}
.... very slight	0	1	1	1	1	2
.... slight	0 ^{c+}	0	0	0	0	2

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	0 ¹	0	0	0	2	4 ^{f†}
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	2	4 ^{f†}
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Interstitial	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Pleural	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
Microgranuloma	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	2
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	2
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 2	0 ¹	3	4 ^{f+}	4 ^{f+}	3	0
Wagner Grade 3	0 ^{c+}	0	0	0	1	3
Wagner Grade 4	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	1
Wagner Grade 1	4 ¹	1	0 ^{f+}	0 ^{f+}	0 ^{f+}	0 ^{f†}
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0 ¹	1	1	3	3	4 ^{f†}
.... very slight	0 ¹	1	1	3	3	4 ^{f†}

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (Iain)						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	1	0	0	3
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ^{c+}	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ^{c+}	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	0 ¹	1	3	4 ^{f+}	4 ^{f+}	1
.... very slight	0 ¹	1	3	4 ^{f+}	4 ^{f+}	1
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
nasal cavity						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	2	3	3	3	3
Corpora Amylacea, Olfactory epithelial	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory epithelial	1	0	1	0	0	1

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
nasal cavity (Continued...)						
.... very slight	1	0	1	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Droplets, Hyaline, Respiratory epithelial	0 c ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 c ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Nalt	0	0	1	1	1	0
.... slight	0	0	1	1	1	0
nasopharynx						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4	4	4	4
trachea						
Examined	4	4	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	4	3	4	3	3
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	1	0	1	0	1	1

1 [c - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	4	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
trachea (Continued...)						
.... very slight	1	0	1	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
larynx			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	2	3	2
Dilatation, Submucosal Glands	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Hemorrhage, Subepithelial	0	0	2
.... slight	0	0	2
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	2	1	1
.... very slight	1	1	1
.... slight	1	0	0
lung			
Examined	4	4	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	1	0
.... slight	0	3	4 f ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial	4 f ¹	0	0
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido-lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
Fibrosis, Interstitial	4 f ¹	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	4 f ¹	2	0
.... slight	0	2	4 f ¹
Fibrosis, Pleural	0	0	2
.... very slight	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
Giant Cells, Syncytial	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	4 f ¹	2
.... slight	0	0	2
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	4 f ¹	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	2	0	0
.... slight	2	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	2	0
.... slight	0	2	4 f ¹
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	3	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	3	4	2
.... slight	0	0	2

¹ [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	4 f ¹	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	4 f ¹	2	0
.... slight	0	2	4 f ¹
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Interstitial	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Pleural	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous	0	1	1
.... slight	0	1	1
Microgranuloma	4 f ¹	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Wagner Grade 2	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 3	2	0	0
Wagner Grade 4	2	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Wagner Grade 1	0 f ¹	0 f ¹	0 f ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	4 f ¹	0	0
.... very slight	4 f ¹	0	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
lung associated lymph nodes (Iain)			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	1	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	2	2
.... slight	0	2	2
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	3	0	0
.... very slight	3	0	0
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid	1	0	2
.... slight	1	0	2
nasal cavity			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	2	1	1
Corpora Amylacea, Olfactory epithelial	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory epithelial	1	3	2

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
nasal cavity (Continued...)			
.... very slight	1	2	0
.... slight	0	1	2
Droplets, Hyaline, Respiratory epithelial	0	2	2
.... very slight	0	2	2
Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell	1	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
.... slight	1	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
Hyperplasia, Nalt	1	0	3
.... slight	1	0	3
nasopharynx			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	4	4
trachea			
Examined	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	4	4
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial	1	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
trachea (Continued...)			
.... very slight	1	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	3	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	3	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, very slight	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, very slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	6	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, slight	c
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma, very slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma, slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 2	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	3	lung : Wagner Grade 2	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 2	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 3	c
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 4	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 1	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	3	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	4	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	nasal cavity : Droplets, Hyaline, Respiratory epithelial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	nasal cavity : Droplets, Hyaline, Respiratory epithelial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	8	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Fibrosis, Interstitial, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Microgranuloma	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Microgranuloma, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 4	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 4	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Key Page

Measurement/Statistics

<u>Measurement</u>	<u>Descriptive</u>	<u>Comparative</u>	<u>Arithmetic/Adjusted</u>	<u>Transformation</u>
Pathology Observation	Count Positives	Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact		

Group Information

<u>Short Name</u>	<u>Long Name</u>	<u>Report Headings</u>	
1	Clean air	Clean air	control
2	brake dust low	brake dust	low
3	brake dust mid	Brake dust	mid
4	brake dust high	Brake dust	high
5	Particel Control	Titanium-	dioxide
6	Chrysotile low	Chrysotile	low
7	Chrysotile high	Chrysotile	high
8	Crocidolite	Crocido-	lite
9	Amosite	Amosite	

Removal Reason Grouping

<u>Grouping Name</u>	<u>Abbreviation</u>	<u>Removal Reasons</u>
Killed - Terminal Kill	TeKi	Killed - Terminal Kill
Killed - Moribund	US	Killed - Moribund
Found Dead	FD	Found Dead

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Key Page**Rationalisation Details**

Rationalisation: 6M_PE

Merges

larynx, Hemorrhage, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Hemorrhage, subepithelial, focal, very slight

larynx, Hemorrhage, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

nasal cavity, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

nasal cavity, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, Interstitial, interstitial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, focal, very slight

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, focal, very slight

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, peribronchiolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, focal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Peribronchiolar, peribronchiolar, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, multifocal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, multifocal, slight

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, focal, very slight

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Microgranuloma, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Microgranuloma, focal, very slight

lung, Microgranuloma, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, multifocal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, multifocal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, multifocal, very slight

Edits

larynx, Hemorrhage, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Hemorrhage, subepithelial, focal, slight

larynx, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Subepithelial, subepithelial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Key Page**Edits (Continued)**

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Alveolar/Interstitial, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, slight

lung, Hemorrhage, Alveolar, alveolar, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Hemorrhage, alveolar, focal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, Interstitial, interstitial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, multifocal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Interstitial, interstitial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Perivascular, perivascular, focal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Key Page**Edits (Continued)**

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, perivascular, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, Pleural, pleural, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, pleural, focal, slight

lung, Fibrosis, Pleural, pleural, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, pleural, focal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, Pleural, pleural, focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, pleural, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, Pleural, pleural, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, pleural, focal, very slight

nasal cavity, Corpora Amylacea, Olfactory epithelial, olfactory epithelial, focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Corpora Amylacea, olfactory epithelial, focal, very slight

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory epithelial, olfactory epithelial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, olfactory epithelial, multifocal, very slight

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, Olfactory epithelial, olfactory epithelial, multifocal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, olfactory epithelial, multifocal, slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

Key Page

Edits (Continued)

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, Respiratory epithelial, respiratory epithelial, multifocal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Droplets, Hyaline, respiratory epithelial, multifocal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 6 months post exposure

End Of Print

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations – 12 months

For Study: 02G16015
Title: Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat
Requested By: Dirk Schaudien
Job Number: 48778
Animal Reference: Animal Name
Animals Excluded: 1000, 1001, 1002, 1003, 1010, 1011, 1012, 1013, 1020, 1021, 1022, 1023, 1030, 1031, 1032, 1033, 1060, 1061, 1062, 1063, 1070, 1071, 1072, 1073, 1080, 1081, 1082, 1083, 1084, 1085, 1086, 1087, 1088, 1089, 1090, 1091, 1092, 1093, 1094, 1095, 1096, 1097, 1098, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2010, 2011, 2012, + others.

Day Numbers: All
Groups: All
Observation Type: Histo - Neoplastic and Non-Neoplastic
Observation Summary: Incidence
Report Format: Group within Sex
Tissues: All
Rationalisation: None
Removal Reasons: All
Completed Animals Only: No
Animals with Observations Only: No
Major Pathological Findings Only: No
Split Observations by: GRADE
Split Table by: Sex
Use Alternative Descriptions: No
Repeat First Group on Each Page: No
Style: Landscape - 12 Columns
Include: NVL Tissues; NE Tissues; Neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; TUMOUR TYPE; ORIGIN; CLASSIFICATION; Non-neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; SIZE

S-9.5 Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations 12 months

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
larynx						
Examined	4	3	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	1	1	3	2	3	3
Dilatation, Submucosal Glands	1	1	1	1	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1	0	0	1
.... slight	1	1	0	1	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell	2	1	1	1	1	0
.... very slight	1	1	1	1	1	0
.... slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
lung						
Examined	4	3	4	4	4	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	0 ¹	1	3	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺
.... very slight	0 ¹	1	3	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺
Fibrosis	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Giant Cells, Syncytial	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	0 ¹	0	1	2	0	4 ^{f†}
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	1	2	0	4 ^{f†}
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell	0 ¹	0	0	1	1	3
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	1	1	3
.... slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell	1	1	0	2	0	0
.... very slight	1	1	0	2	0	0
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar	1	1	1	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	1	1	0	0	0
Microgranuloma	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 2	0 ⁺	1	3	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	2
Wagner Grade 3	0 c ⁺	0	0	0	0	2
Wagner Grade 4	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 1	4 ¹	2	1	0 f ⁺	0 f ⁺	0 f ⁺
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0 ¹	2	4 f ⁺	3	4 f ⁺	2
.... very slight	0 ¹	2	4 f ⁺	3	4 f ⁺	2
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (Iain)						
Examined	4	3	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	1	0	0	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	0 ¹	0	3	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	3	4 f ⁺	3	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (ln) (Continued...)						
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid	0	0	0	0	2	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	2	0
nasal cavity						
Examined	4	3	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	0	0	2	0	2	2
Corpora Amylacea	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Droplets, Hyaline	2	3	2	4	2	1
.... very slight	2	0	1	2	2	1
.... slight	1	2	1	2	0	0
.... moderate	0	1	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell	0	1	0	1	0	1
.... very slight	0	1	0	1	0	1
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell	1	0	0	1	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
Hyperplasia, Nalt	1	0	1	1	0	0
.... slight	1	0	1	1	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	4	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
nasopharynx						
Examined	4	3	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	4	4	4	4
skin/subcutaneous tissue						
Examined	0	0	0	0	1	1
Tumor, Hair Follicle, [B]; benign					0	1
Abscess(Es)					1	0
.... severe					1	0
trachea						
Examined	4	3	4	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	3	3	3	4	4
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell	1	0	1	1	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	1	1	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
thymus						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	1
Thymoma, [M]; malignant						1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido-lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	3	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
larynx			
Examined	3	4	4
No Visible Lesions	1	3	3
Dilatation, Submucosal Glands	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell	2	0	1
.... very slight	2	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0
lung			
Examined	3	4	4
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... slight	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	3 f ¹	0	0
.... very slight	3 f ¹	0	0
Fibrosis	1	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	1	1	1
.... slight	0	3	4 f ¹
Giant Cells, Syncytial	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	3	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... very slight	0	4 f ¹	0
.... slight	0	0	4 f ¹
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	2	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	2	1	0
.... slight	0	3	4 f ¹
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type	0	1	0
.... slight	0	1	0
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell	2	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	2	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... slight	0	3	2
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Microgranuloma	1	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	1	2	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	3	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... slight	0	2	4 f ¹
Wagner Grade 2	1	0	0
Wagner Grade 3	2	0	0
Wagner Grade 4	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
Wagner Grade 1	0 f ¹	0 f ¹	0 f ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	3 f ¹	0	0
.... very slight	3 f ¹	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt	0	2	3
.... very slight	0	2	3
lung associated lymph nodes (Iain)			
Examined	3	4	4
No Visible Lesions	0	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	0	4 f ¹	4 f ¹
.... very slight	0	2	3
.... slight	0	2	1
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	3 f ¹	0	0
.... very slight	3 f ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido-lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	3	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (ln) (Continued...)			
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid	0	1	1
.... slight	0	1	1
nasal cavity			
Examined	3	4	4
No Visible Lesions	2	0	0
Corpora Amylacea	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
Droplets, Hyaline	1	3	2
.... very slight	1	2	1
.... slight	0	1	1
.... moderate	0	1	1
Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell	0	1	2
.... very slight	0	1	2
.... slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Nalt	0	0	2
.... slight	0	0	2

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	3	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
nasopharynx			
Examined	3	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	4	4
skin/subcutaneous tissue			
Examined	0	0	0
Tumor, Hair Follicle, [B]; benign			
Abscess(Es)			
.... severe			
trachea			
Examined	3	4	4
No Visible Lesions	3	3	3
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell	0	1	1
.... very slight	0	1	1
.... slight	0	0	0
thymus			
Examined	0	0	0
Thymoma, [M]; malignant			

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Fibrosis, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	6	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 3 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 4 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	3	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	3	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (Ialn) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (Ialn) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, very slight	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	8	lung : Fibrosis	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Fibrosis	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Fibrosis, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma, slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 4	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 4	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	7	lung associated lymph nodes (ln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, very slight	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

Key Page**Measurement/Statistics**

<u>Measurement</u>	<u>Descriptive</u>	<u>Comparative</u>	<u>Arithmetic/Adjusted</u>	<u>Transformation</u>
Pathology Observation	Count Positives	Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact		

Group Information

<u>Short Name</u>	<u>Long Name</u>	<u>Report Headings</u>	
1	Clean air	Clean air	control
2	brake dust low	brake dust	low
3	brake dust mid	Brake dust	mid
4	brake dust high	Brake dust	high
5	Particel Control	Titanium-	dioxide
6	Chrysotile low	Chrysotile	low
7	Chrysotile high	Chrysotile	high
8	Crocidolite	Crocido-	lite
9	Amosite	Amosite	

Removal Reason Grouping

<u>Grouping Name</u>	<u>Abbreviation</u>	<u>Removal Reasons</u>
Killed - Terminal Kill	TeKi	Killed - Terminal Kill
Killed - Moribund	US	Killed - Moribund
Found Dead	FD	Found Dead

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 12 months post exposure

End Of Print

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

For Study: 02G16015
Title: Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat
Requested By: Dirk Schaudien
Job Number: 49863
Animal Reference: Animal Name
Animals Excluded: 1000, 1001, 1002, 1003, 1010, 1011, 1012, 1013, 1020, 1021, 1022, 1023, 1030, 1031, 1032, 1033, 1050, 1051, 1052, 1053, 1070, 1071, 1072, 1073, 1080, 1081, 1082, 1083, 1084, 1085, 1086, 1087, 1088, 1089, 1090, 1091, 1092, 1093, 1094, 1095, 1096, 1097, 1098, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2010, 2011, 2012, + others.

Day Numbers: All
Groups: All
Observation Type: Histo - Neoplastic and Non-Neoplastic
Observation Summary: Incidence
Report Format: Group within Sex
Tissues: All
Rationalisation: 18M_PE
Removal Reasons: All
Completed Animals Only: No
Animals with Observations Only: No
Major Pathological Findings Only: No
Split Observations by: GRADE
Split Table by: Sex
Use Alternative Descriptions: No
Repeat First Group on Each Page: No
Style: Landscape - 12 Columns
Include: NVL Tissues; NE Tissues; Locators; Neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; TUMOUR TYPE; ORIGIN; CLASSIFICATION; Non-neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; SIZE; DISTRIBUTION

S-9.6 Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations 18 months

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	4	3	3	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
larynx						
Examined	4	3	3	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	0	2	1	2	3	2
Dilatation, Submucosal Glands; focal	1	0	1	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	1	0	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; (multi)focal	3	1	1	2	1	2
.... very slight	2	1	1	1	1	2
.... slight	1	0	0	1	0	0
liver						
Examined	0	1	0	0	0	0
Adenoma, Hepatocellular; benign		1				
Focus Of Cellular Alteration, Basophilic Nos; focal		0				
.... moderate		0				
lung						
Examined	4	3	3	4	4	4
alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	3	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal	0 ¹	1	2	4 ^{f+}	4 ^{f+}	4 ^{f+}
.... very slight	0 ¹	1	2	4 ^{f+}	4 ^{f+}	4 ^{f+}
interstitial; Fibrosis; (multi)focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Giant Cells, Syncytial; (multi)focal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal	0 ^{c+}	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ^{c+}	0	0	0	0	0
Granuloma, Foreign-Body; multifocal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; (multi)focal	0	1	0	1	1	2
.... very slight	0	1	0	1	1	2
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type, focal	1	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	3	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type with atypia, focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very severe	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell; focal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal	0 ⁺	0	0	0	1	1
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	1	1
alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	3	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; (multi)focal	1	1	0	2	0	0
.... very slight	1	1	0	2	0	0
interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
Inflammation, Chronic; (multi)focal	1	0	0	1	0	1
.... very slight	1	0	0	1	0	1
Lipoproteinosis, Alveolar; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; (multi)focal	3 c ¹	3	1	1	0	1
.... very slight	2	2	0	0	0	1
.... slight	1	1	1	1	0	0
Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous; (multi)focal	1	0	1	1	0	1
.... very slight	1	0	1	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
Microgranuloma; (multi)focal	0 +	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 +	0	0	0	0	0
Microgranuloma; multifocal	0 +	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 +	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [c - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	4	3	3	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
Wagner Grade 2	0 ¹	1	2	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺	4 f ⁺
Wagner Grade 4	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 1	4 ¹	2	1	0 f ⁺	0 f ⁺	0 f ⁺
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; (multi)focal	0 ⁺	0	1	3	4 f ⁺	1
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	1	3	4 f ⁺	1
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt; (multi)focal	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (Iain)						
Examined	4	3	3	4	4	4
No Visible Lesions	4	3	1	0	1	4
Not Examined: No Significant Tissue Present In Section	0	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	0 c ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 c ⁺	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	3	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (ln) (Continued...)						
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal	0 ¹	0	2	4 f ⁺	2	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	2	4 f ⁺	2	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
skin/subcutaneous tissue						
Examined	3	0	0	0	0	0
subcutaneous; Hemorrhage; focal	1					
.... moderate	1					
Hyperplasia, Epithelial; squamous, focal	1					
.... severe	1					
Inflammation, Chronic Active; ulcerated, focal	1					
.... severe	1					
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	1					
.... slight	1					
Laceration; focal	1					
.... slight	1					
trachea						
Examined	4	3	3	4	4	4

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [cc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	3	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
trachea (Continued...)						
No Visible Lesions	2	3	2	4	3	3
subepithelial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; (multi)focal	2	0	1	0	1	1
.... very slight	2	0	1	0	1	1
thymus						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	1
Thymoma, [M]; malignant						1
pituitary gland						
Examined	1	0	1	0	0	0
Adenoma, Pars Distalis; benign	1		1			
kidney						
Examined	0	0	1	0	0	0
bilateral; Nephropathy, Chronic Progressive; multifocal			1			
.... slight			1			
testis						
Examined	0	0	1	0	0	0
Adenoma, Interstitial (Leydig) Cell; benign			0			
Atrophy, Tubular; multifocal			0			
.... very slight			0			
Atrophy, Tubular; diffuse			1			

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	4	3	3	4	4	4
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
testis (Continued...)						
.... severe			1			
epididymis						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	0
Reduced Sperm, Luminal; diffuse						
.... very severe						
seminal vesicles						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	0
bilateral; Atrophy; diffuse						
.... slight						
thyroid gland						
Examined	0	0	0	1	0	0
Carcinoma, Follicular Cell; malignant				1		

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido-lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	1	4	3
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
larynx			
Examined	1	4	3
No Visible Lesions	1	1	3
Dilatation, Submucosal Glands; focal	0	2	0
.... very slight	0	2	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; (multi)focal	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0
liver			
Examined	0	1	0
Adenoma, Hepatocellular; benign		0	
Focus Of Cellular Alteration, Basophilic Nos; focal		1	
.... moderate		1	
lung			
Examined	1	4	3
alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	0	4 f ¹	3 f ¹
.... very slight	0	1	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	1	4	3
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... slight	0	3	3 f ¹
alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal	1	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0
interstitial; Fibrosis; (multi)focal	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0
interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal	0	3	3 f ¹
.... slight	0	3	3 f ¹
Giant Cells, Syncytial; (multi)focal	0	4 f ¹	1
.... very slight	0	4 f ¹	1
Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal	0	0	2
.... slight	0	0	2
Granuloma, Foreign-Body; multifocal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; (multi)focal	1	1	0
.... very slight	1	1	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal	0	3	3 f ¹
.... slight	0	3	3 f ¹
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type, focal	0	0	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido-lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	1	4	3
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... very slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type with atypia, focal	0	1	1
.... very severe	0	1	1
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell; focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal	0	4 f ¹	0
.... very slight	0	4 f ¹	0
peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal	0	0	3 f ¹
.... slight	0	0	3 f ¹
perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal	0	2	3 f ¹
.... very slight	0	2	3 f ¹
alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal	0	4 f ¹	0
.... very slight	0	4 f ¹	0
alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	0	3 f ¹
.... slight	0	0	3 f ¹

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido-lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	1	4	3
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; (multi)focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic; (multi)focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Lipoproteinosis, Alveolar; multifocal	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; (multi)focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous; (multi)focal	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0
Microgranuloma; (multi)focal	0	3	0
.... very slight	0	3	0
Microgranuloma; multifocal	0	0	3 f ¹
.... slight	0	0	3 f ¹

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	1	4	3
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
Wagner Grade 2	1	0	0
Wagner Grade 4	0	4 f ¹	3 f ¹
Wagner Grade 1	0	0 f ¹	0 f ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; (multi)focal	1	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt; (multi)focal	0	3	2
.... very slight	0	3	2
lung associated lymph nodes (Iain)			
Examined	0	4	3
No Visible Lesions		1	0
Not Examined: No Significant Tissue Present In Section	1	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal		1	1
.... very slight		1	1
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal		2	2
.... slight		2	2

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido-lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	1	4	3
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (ln) (Continued...)			
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal		0	0
.... very slight		0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal		0	0
.... slight		0	0
skin/subcutaneous tissue			
Examined	0	0	0
subcutaneous; Hemorrhage; focal			
.... moderate			
Hyperplasia, Epithelial; squamous, focal			
.... severe			
Inflammation, Chronic Active; ulcerated, focal			
.... severe			
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal			
.... slight			
Laceration; focal			
.... slight			
trachea			
Examined	1	4	3

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	1	4	3
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
trachea (Continued...)			
No Visible Lesions	0	3	2
subepithelial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; (multi)focal	1	1	1
.... very slight	1	1	1
thymus			
Examined	0	0	0
Thymoma, [M]; malignant			
pituitary gland			
Examined	0	0	0
Adenoma, Pars Distalis; benign			
kidney			
Examined	0	0	0
bilateral; Nephropathy, Chronic Progressive; multifocal			
.... slight			
testis			
Examined	0	1	0
Adenoma, Interstitial (Leydig) Cell; benign		1	
Atrophy, Tubular; multifocal		1	
.... very slight		1	
Atrophy, Tubular; diffuse		0	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	1	4	3
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
testis (Continued...)			
.... severe		0	
epididymis			
Examined	0	1	0
Reduced Sperm, Luminal; diffuse		1	
.... very severe		1	
seminal vesicles			
Examined	0	1	0
bilateral; Atrophy; diffuse		1	
.... slight		1	
thyroid gland			
Examined	0	0	0
Carcinoma, Follicular Cell; malignant			

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	6	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 2	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 2	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 2	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 2	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 4	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 1	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; (multi)focal	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; (multi)focal	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	4	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	4	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; (multi)focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 4 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 4 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 1	f
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Key Page

Measurement/Statistics

<u>Measurement</u>	<u>Descriptive</u>	<u>Comparative</u>	<u>Arithmetic/Adjusted</u>	<u>Transformation</u>
Pathology Observation	Count Positives	Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact		

Group Information

<u>Short Name</u>	<u>Long Name</u>	<u>Report Headings</u>	
1	Clean air	Clean air	control
2	brake dust low	brake dust	low
3	brake dust mid	Brake dust	mid
4	brake dust high	Brake dust	high
5	Particel Control	Titanium-	dioxide
6	Chrysotile low	Chrysotile	low
7	Chrysotile high	Chrysotile	high
8	Crocidolite	Crocido-	lite
9	Amosite	Amosite	

Removal Reason Grouping

<u>Grouping Name</u>	<u>Abbreviation</u>	<u>Removal Reasons</u>
Killed - Terminal Kill	TeKi	Killed - Terminal Kill
Killed - Moribund	US	Killed - Moribund
Found Dead	FD	Found Dead

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Key Page**Rationalisation Details**

Rationalisation: 18M_PE

Merges

larynx, Hemorrhage, subepithelial, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Hemorrhage, subepithelial, focal, very slight

larynx, Hemorrhage, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, (multi)focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, slight

larynx, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Fibrosis, interstitial, multifocal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, focal, very slight

lung, Giant Cells, Syncytial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, focal, very slight

lung, Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, (multi)focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, focal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, peribronchiolar, multifocal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, (multi)focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, focal, slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, perivascular, multifocal, slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, alveolar/interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, interstitial, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, interstitial, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, interstitial, multifocal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, pleural, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, pleural, focal, very slight

lung, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, pleural, multifocal, very slight

lung, Inflammation, Chronic, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Inflammation, Chronic, focal, very slight

lung, Inflammation, Chronic, multifocal, very slight

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, focal, very slight

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, multifocal, very slight

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, (multi)focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, focal, slight

lung, Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar, multifocal, slight

lung, Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous, focal, very slight

lung, Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous, multifocal, very slight

lung, Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous, (multi)focal, slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous, focal, slight

lung, Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous, multifocal, slight

lung, Microgranuloma, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Microgranuloma, focal, very slight

lung, Microgranuloma, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt, multifocal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, focal, very slight

lung, Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt, multifocal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, (multi)focal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

Key Page**Merges (Continued)**

Is used to report the following findings:

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, multifocal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, focal, very slight

lung associated lymph nodes (ln), Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, multifocal, very slight

nasal cavity, Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell, focal, very slight

nasal cavity, Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell, multifocal, very slight

nasal cavity, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, subepithelial, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

nasal cavity, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

nasal cavity, Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, (multi)focal, very slight

Is used to report the following findings:

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, focal, very slight

trachea, Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell, subepithelial, multifocal, very slight

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 18 months post exposure

End Of Print

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

For Study: 02G16015
Title: Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study (nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat
Requested By: Dirk Schaudien
Job Number: 52607
Animal Reference: Animal Name
Animals Excluded: 1000, 1001, 1002, 1003, 1010, 1011, 1012, 1013, 1020, 1021, 1022, 1023, 1030, 1031, 1032, 1033, 1050, 1051, 1052, 1053, 1060, 1061, 1062, 1063, 2000, 2001, 2002, 2003, 2010, 2011, 2012, 2013, 2020, 2021, 2022, 2023, 2030, 2031, 2032, 2033, 2050, 2051, 2052, 2053, 2060, 2061, 2062, 2063, 3000, 3001, + others.

Day Numbers: All
Groups: All
Observation Type: Histo - Neoplastic and Non-Neoplastic
Observation Summary: Incidence
Report Format: Group within Sex
Tissues: All
Rationalisation: None
Removal Reasons: All
Completed Animals Only: No
Animals with Observations Only: No
Major Pathological Findings Only: No
Split Observations by: GRADE
Split Table by: Sex
Use Alternative Descriptions: No
Repeat First Group on Each Page: No
Style: Landscape - 12 Columns
Include: NVL Tissues; NE Tissues; Locators; Neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; TUMOUR TYPE; ORIGIN; CLASSIFICATION; Non-neoplastic - QUALIFIERS; SIZE; DISTRIBUTION

S-9.7 Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations 24 months

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung						
Examined	31	31	31	31	31	31
Adenocarcinoma; malignant	0	0	0	0	0	0
Adenoma, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; benign	1 c ¹	0	0	0	0	1
Adenoma, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; with atypia, benign	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carcinoma, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; malignant	0	0	0	1	1	0
alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	0 +	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 +	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 +	0	0	0	0	0
alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	0 +	3	10 +	22 +	25 +	19 +
.... very slight	0 +	3	10 +	20 +	24 +	19 +
.... slight	0	0	0	2	1	0
Autolysis; diffuse	1	1	2	3	2	1
.... slight	1	0	2	0	2	0
.... moderate	0 c ¹	1	0	1	0	1
.... severe	0	0	0	2	0	0
Congestion; diffuse	1	1	1	0	1	1
.... slight	1	1	1	0	1	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [c - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0	0	0	1
alveolar; Edema; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
interstitial; Fibrosis; focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
pleural; Fibrosis; focal	1 c ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
pleural; Fibrosis; multifocal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Granuloma, Cholesterol; focal	6	3	2	3	2	1
.... very slight	5	3	0	3	2	1

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... slight	1	0	1	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1	0	0	0
Granuloma, Cholesterol; multifocal	0	2	1	2	0	2
.... very slight	0	2	1	0	0	2
.... slight	0	0	0	2	0	0
alveolar; Hemorrhage; chronic, focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
alveolar; Hemorrhage; chronic, multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
alveolar; Hemorrhage; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
alveolar; Hemorrhage; acute, focal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
pleural; Hyperplasia; focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
pleural; Hyperplasia; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
balt; Hyperplasia; lymphoid, focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; focal	0 c ¹	0	1	3	3	3
.... very slight	0 c ¹	0	1	2	3	3
.... slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal	0 +	0	1	1	0	3
.... very slight	0 +	0	1	1	0	3
.... slight	0 +	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0 +	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type, focal	1	5	1	4	2	4
.... very slight	0	3	0	1	0	0
.... slight	0	2	1	1	1	3
.... moderate	1	0	0	0	1	1
.... severe	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... very severe	0	0	0	1	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type, multifocal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [c - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type with atypia, focal	1	1	0	2	0	0
.... moderate	0 c ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very severe	1	1	0	2	0	0
Hyperplasia, Mesothelial; focal	0 c ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 c ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Mesothelial; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell; focal	1	1	0	0	1	0
.... very slight	1	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0	1	0	0
alveolar; Infiltration, Granulocytic Cell; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0

1 [c - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
pleural; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
pleural; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	1	1
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	1	1
.... slight	0 ⁺	0	0	0	0	0
interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	1 c ⁺	1	0	2	6	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... very slight	1 c ¹	1	0	2	6	0
interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	8 +	2	1 f ⁺	8	1 f ⁺	2
.... very slight	7 +	1	1	6	1	2
.... slight	1	1	0	2	0	0
perivascular; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
perivascular; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	0 c ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
pleural; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	4	2	2	3	6	3
.... very slight	4	2	2	3	6	3
pleural; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	2 c ¹	1	2	5	0	0
.... very slight	2 c ¹	1	2	5	0	0
Inflammation, Acute; focal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Inflammation, Acute; multifocal	1	0	1	0	0	1
.... very slight	1	0	1	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	1

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [c - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... severe	0	0	0	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic; focal	2	4	1	0	3	5
.... very slight	1	4	1	0	3	4
.... slight	1	0	0	0	0	1
Inflammation, Chronic; multifocal	11 ¹	5	11	3 c ⁺	4 c ⁺	10
.... very slight	5 c ⁺	4	8	2	3	9
.... slight	6	1	3	1	1	1
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; multifocal	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1	0	0	0
pleural; Inflammation, Chronic Active; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
Lipoproteinosis, Alveolar; focal	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
Lipoproteinosis, Alveolar; multifocal	0	1	2	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	1	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [cc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... severe	0	0	0	0	0	0
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; focal	2	3	3	1	0	0
.... very slight	2	2	3	1	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; multifocal	22 ¹	18	20	21	16	20
.... very slight	12 c ⁺	10	12	12	15	7
.... slight	9 c ⁺	7	6	9	1 ⁺	12
.... moderate	1	1	2	0	0	1
Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous; focal	0	1	3	3	3	1
.... very slight	0	1	3	3	3	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous; multifocal	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	1	0	0
Metaplasia, Fibro-Osseous; focal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
Metastasis/-Es From Primary In Adrenal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... present, no grade	0	0	0	0	0	0
Metastasis/-Es From Primary In Liver	0	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [cc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
.... present, no grade	0	0	0	0	0	0
Metastasis/-Es From Primary In Thyroid; focal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... present, no grade	1	0	0	0	0	0
Metastasis/-Es From Primary In Thyroid; multifocal	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... present, no grade	0	1	0	0	0	0
Microgranuloma; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 2	0 ¹	3	10 ⁺	22 ⁺	25 ⁺	18 ⁺
Wagner Grade 3	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	1
Wagner Grade 4	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Wagner Grade 1	31 ¹	28	21 ⁺	9 ⁺	6 ⁺	12 ⁺
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; focal	0	0	1	0	1	1
.... very slight	0	0	1	0	1	1
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	6 ^{f+}	19 ⁺	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	6 ^{f+}	19 ⁺	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)						
Metastasis-/Es From Primary Site Unknown	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... present, no grade	0	0	0	1	0	0
Adhesion To Thoracic Wall; focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (Iain)						
Examined	28	29	26	30	30	28
No Visible Lesions	27	28	24	22	11	22
Not Examined: No Significant Tissue Present In Section	3	2	5	1	1	3
Not Examined: Tissue Not Taken At Necropsy	0	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0 ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; focal	0	0	0	0	2	1
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	2	1
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	0 ¹	0	2	6 ^{f+}	16 ⁺	2
.... very slight	0 ¹	0	2	6 ^{f+}	14 ⁺	2
.... slight	0	0	0	0	2	0
Autolysis; diffuse	1	1	0	2	0	1
.... slight	1	0	0	0	0	1

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (ln) (Continued...)						
.... moderate	0	1	0	1	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0	1	0	0
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid; diffuse	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	1
Infiltrated By Histiocytic Sarcoma Cells	0	0	0	0	1	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0	1	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; plasmacytic, multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Resorption; blood, diffuse	1	0	0	0	0	1
.... slight	1	0	0	0	0	1
larynx						
Examined	31	31	31	31	31	31
No Visible Lesions	18	17	20	17	25	20
Not Examined: Tissue Not Taken At Necropsy	0	0	0	0	0	0
Autolysis; diffuse	1	1	1	4	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	1	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	3	0	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
larynx (Continued...)						
.... severe	1	0	0	1	0	0
Dilatation, Submucosal Glands; focal	0	0	2	4	1	2
.... very slight	0	0	1	2	1	1
.... slight	0	0	1	2	0	1
Erosion; focal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Epithelial; focal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	3	3	5	1	0	3
.... very slight	3	1	3	0	0	1
.... slight	0	2	2	1	0	2
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	3	1	1	0	0	0
.... very slight	3	1	1	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	5	6	4	3	5	5
.... very slight	5	5	4	2	5	3
.... slight	0	1	0	1	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
larynx (Continued...)						
subepithelial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	1	2	0	3	1	2
.... very slight	1	1	0	1	0	1
.... slight	0	1	0	1	1	1
.... moderate	0	0	0	1	0	0
Inflammation; chronic, focal	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
nasal cavity						
Examined	31	31	30	30	31	31
No Visible Lesions	13	17	14	13	16	15
Not Examined: Autolysis Precludes Diagnosis	0	0	0	0	0	0
Autolysis; diffuse	1	1	1	3	1	1
.... slight	0	1	0	2	1	0
.... moderate	1	0	1	1	0	1
olfactory epithelial; Droplets, Hyaline; multifocal	15	12	16	13	15	15
.... very slight	5	1	5	2	4	6
.... slight	4	7	5	5	2	4
.... moderate	5	4	4	6	8	3
.... severe	1	0	2	0	1	2

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
nasal cavity (Continued...)						
respiratory epithelial; Droplets, Hyaline; multifocal	6	2	4	8	3	4
.... very slight	5 c ¹	1	2	6	1	2
.... slight	0	1	1	2	2	2
.... moderate	1	0	1	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell; focal	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
Hyperplasia, Respiratory Epithelial; focal	1	1	0	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0	0	1	0
Infiltrated By Tumour Cells	0	0	0	0	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	3 c ¹	1	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	3 c ¹	1	0	0	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	1	1	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	1	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0

1 [c - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
nasal cavity (Continued...)						
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Inflammation; purulent, multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Nalt; focal	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
nasopharynx						
Examined	31	31	30	30	31	31
No Visible Lesions	30	30	29	30	31	30
Autolysis; diffuse	1	1	1	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	1	0	0	1
.... moderate	1	0	0	0	0	0
Metastasis/-Es From Primary In Skin	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... present, no grade	0	0	0	0	0	0
trachea						
Examined	31	31	30	31	31	31
No Visible Lesions	27	26	26	26	28	29
Autolysis; diffuse	1	1	2	4	2	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
trachea (Continued...)						
.... slight	0	0	0	0	2	0
.... moderate	0	1	2	3	0	1
.... severe	1	0	0	1	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	3	4	2	1	1	1
.... very slight	3	4	2	1	1	1
diaphragm						
Examined	28	28	28	27	28	28
No Visible Lesions	26	27	27	27	26	27
Autolysis; diffuse	1	1	0	0	0	1
.... slight	0	1	0	0	0	1
.... moderate	1	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia; focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltrated By Histiocytic Sarcoma Cells	0	0	0	0	1	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; mixed, focal	1	0	1	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	1	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
diaphragm (Continued...)						
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; mixed, multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
liver						
Examined	10	6	9	5	7	5
Adenoma, Hepatocellular; benign	1	0	1	0	0	0
Carcinoma, Hepatocellular; malignant with metastasis	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carcinoma, Hepatocellular; malignant	0	1	0	0	0	0
Angiectasis; focal	2 c ¹	1	1	0	3	0
.... very slight	1	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	1	0	1	0	2	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	1	0
Angiectasis; multifocal	1 +	2	0	1	2	3

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [c - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
liver (Continued...)						
.... very slight	0	0	0	1	1	1
.... slight	1 c ¹	2	0	0	1	2
Autolysis; diffuse	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0	1	0	0
Change, Fatty; focal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Change, Fatty; multifocal	3 c ¹	1	2	2	4	4
.... very slight	2 +	1	0	0	2	4
.... slight	1	0	2	1	2	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	1	0	0
Change, Fatty; diffuse	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cyst(S); blood-stained, focal	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	1	0	0	0
Cyst(S); focal	0 c ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
Degeneration, Cystic; focal	0	0	0	0	1	0

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Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
liver (Continued...)						
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
Hyperplasia, Bile Duct; focal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bile Duct; multifocal	1	0	0	0	1	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0	1	0	0
periportal; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; mixed, multifocal	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
periportal; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
periportal; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	0	1	1	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	1	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
liver (Continued...)						
Necrosis, Hepatocellular; focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Necrosis, Hepatocellular; multifocal	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1	0	0	0
Nodule, Hepatodiaphragmatic; focal	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	1	0	0	0
Pigmentation; multifocal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Focus Of Cellular Alteration, Clear Cell; focal	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	1	0	0
Focus Of Cellular Alteration, Tigroid; focal	2	0	2	0	1	2
.... very slight	2	0	2	0	1	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	1
Focus Of Cellular Alteration, Tigroid; multifocal	4	2	1	2	1	0
.... very slight	1	1	0	1	0	0
.... slight	3	1	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1	1	1	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
liver (Continued...)						
Focus Of Cellular Alteration, Basophilic Nos; focal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0	0	1	0
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion	0	1	0	0	0	0
Cyst, Bile Duct; focal	1	1	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	1	1	0	0	0	0
skin/subcutaneous tissue						
Examined	2	6	11	7	5	8
Adenoma, Sebaceous Cell; benign	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carcinoma, Sebaceous Cell; malignant	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carcinoma, Squamous Cell; malignant	0	0	0	0	0	1
Fibroma; benign	0	0	1	1	1	2
Fibrosarcoma; malignant	0	1	0	0	0	0
Hemangiosarcoma; malignant	0	0	0	0	0	1
Keratoacanthoma; benign	0	0	0	1	0	1
Lipoma; benign	0	0	0	0	1	0
Papilloma; benign	0	0	1	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
skin/subcutaneous tissue (Continued...)						
Schwannoma, [M]; malignant	0	0	1	0	0	0
Tumor, Basal Cell, [B]; benign	0	0	0	0	0	0
Tumor, Hair Follicle, [B]; benign	1	1	3	4	1	0
Fibrosarcoma, Pleomorphic; malignant, incidental	0	0	0	1	0	0
subcutaneous; Abscess(Es); focal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0	0	0	0
Cyst(S), Squamous; focal	0	0	1	0	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... very severe	0	0	0	0	0	1
Fibrosis, Dermal; focal	1	2	0	0	1	0
.... moderate	1	1	0	0	0	0
.... severe	0	1	0	0	1	0
Granulation Tissue; chronic, focal	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Epithelial; squamous, focal	1	1	1	0	1	1
.... slight	0	0	1	0	1	0
.... moderate	1	1	0	0	0	1
Hyperplasia, Epithelial; squamous, multifocal	0	0	1	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
skin/subcutaneous tissue (Continued...)						
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	1	0	0	0
Inflammation, Acute; multifocal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	1	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; ulcerated, focal	0	1	2	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	2	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; ulcerated, multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	1	2	1	0	0	2
.... slight	1	1	1	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	1	0	0	0	1
.... very severe	0	0	0	0	0	1
Inflammation, Chronic Active; multifocal	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1	0	0	0
pituitary gland						
Examined	8	3	5	4	3	6
No Visible Lesions	0	0	0	0	0	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
pituitary gland (Continued...)						
Adenoma, Pars Distalis; benign	7	3	5	4	2	4
Adenoma, Pars Distalis; benign, probably fatal	0	0	0	0	1	0
Adenoma, Pars Distalis; multiple, benign	1	0	0	0	0	0
Carcinoma, Pars Distalis; malignant	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Pars Distalis; focal	0	1	0	0	0	1
.... severe	0	1	0	0	0	1
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion	0	0	0	0	0	0
brain						
Examined	0	0	2	1	0	1
Astrocytoma, [M]; malignant, fatal			0	0		0
Oligodendroglioma, [M]; malignant			0	0		1
Tumor, Granular Cell, [M]; malignant			0	0		0
Compression; focal			2	1		0
.... slight			2	0		0
.... moderate			0	1		0
.... severe			0	0		0
ventricular; Dilatation; diffuse			2	1		0
.... slight			2	1		0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
brain (Continued...)						
.... moderate			0	0		0
Infiltrated By Tumour Cells; focal			0	0		0
.... present, no grade			0	0		0
thyroid gland						
Examined	4	7	4	4	1	2
No Visible Lesions	0	0	0	0	0	0
Adenoma, C-Cell; benign	1	0	0	0	0	0
Adenoma, Follicular Cell; benign	0 ¹	0	0	3	0	0
Adenoma, Follicular Cell; cystic, benign	1	3	1	0	0	2
Carcinoma, C-Cell; malignant with metastasis	1	1	0	0	0	0
Carcinoma, C-Cell; malignant	0	0	0	0	0	0
Carcinoma, Follicular Cell; malignant	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, C-Cell; diffuse	0	2	0	1	0	0
.... slight	0	2	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	1	0	0
Hyperplasia, Follicular Cell; cystic, focal	1	0	2	0	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... moderate	0	0	1	0	0	0

1 [cc - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
thyroid gland (Continued...)						
.... severe	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... very severe	1	0	0	0	0	0
Follicle, Cystic; focal	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	1	0	0
Follicle, Cystic; multifocal	0	2	1	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1	0	0	0
parathyroid gland						
Examined	1	0	0	1	0	0
No Visible Lesions	0			1		
Hyperplasia; diffuse	1			0		
.... moderate	1			0		
adrenal gland						
Examined	0	0	1	0	1	0
Adenoma, Cortical; benign			1		0	
Carcinoma, Cortical; malignant with metastasis			0		0	
Carcinoma, Cortical; malignant, probably fatal			0		0	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
adrenal gland (Continued...)						
Pheochromocytoma, [B]; benign			0		1	
testis						
Examined	5	6	8	2	5	4
Adenoma, Interstitial (Leydig) Cell; benign	1	2	0	0	0	2
bilateral; Adenoma, Interstitial (Leydig) Cell; benign	0	0	0	0	0	0
Edema; diffuse	1	1	5	1	4	1
.... very slight	0	0	1	0	1	0
.... slight	1	1	1	1	3	1
.... moderate	0	0	3	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Interstitial (Leydig) Cell; diffuse	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hypertrophy, Mesothelial; focal	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1	0	0	0
Spermatocele, Rete Testis; focal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0	0	0	0
Atrophy, Tubular; diffuse	4	3	5	2	2	3
.... very slight	1	0	2	0	2	0
.... slight	1	1	1	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
testis (Continued...)						
.... moderate	1	0	2	0	0	2
.... severe	1	1	0	1	0	1
.... very severe	0	1	0	1	0	0
unilateral; Atrophy, Tubular; diffuse	1	1	3	0	1	1
.... very slight	0	0	2	0	0	0
.... slight	1	1	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0	0	1	1
epididymis						
Examined	1	1	0	1	1	3
unilateral; Granuloma, Spermatic; focal	0	1		0	0	0
.... very slight	0	1		0	0	0
unilateral; Granuloma, Spermatic; multifocal	1	0		0	0	0
.... severe	1	0		0	0	0
Spermatocele; focal	0	0		0	0	1
.... very severe	0	0		0	0	1
Reduced Sperm, Luminal; diffuse	0	1		1	1	2
.... very slight	0	0		0	1	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
epididymis (Continued...)						
.... slight	0	1		0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0		0	0	0
.... severe	0	0		0	0	2
.... very severe	0	0		1	0	0
prostate						
Examined	1	0	5	0	2	3
No Visible Lesions	0		0		0	1
Atrophy; diffuse	1		3		1	1
.... very slight	0		0		1	0
.... slight	1		3		0	1
Dilatation; diffuse	0		0		0	0
.... moderate	0		0		0	0
Hyperplasia; focal	0		0		1	0
.... slight	0		0		1	0
.... moderate	0		0		0	0
Hyperplasia; multifocal	0		1		0	0
.... very slight	0		1		0	0
Hyperplasia, Atypical; focal	0		0		0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
prostate (Continued...)						
.... moderate	0		0		0	0
Inflammation; chronic, multifocal	0		0		1	0
.... slight	0		0		1	0
Inflammation; focal	0		1		1	0
.... very slight	0		0		1	0
.... slight	0		1		0	0
Inflammation; multifocal	0		1		0	1
.... very slight	0		0		0	0
.... slight	0		0		0	1
.... moderate	0		1		0	0
seminal vesicles						
Examined	3	2	5	2	2	3
No Visible Lesions	0	0	0	0	0	1
bilateral; Atrophy; diffuse	3	2	4	2	2	2
.... very slight	0	1	0	0	2	1
.... slight	3	1	4	2	0	1
Autolysis; diffuse	0	0	0	1	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
	Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
seminal vesicles (Continued...)						
.... moderate	0	0	0	1	0	1
Dilatation; diffuse	0 c ¹	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0 c ¹	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0	0	0	0
bilateral; Inflammation, Necrotizing; multifocal	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	1	0	0	0
kidney						
Examined	3	4	3	4	2	7
Cyst(S); focal	0	1	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	1	0	0	0	0
Dilatation, Pelvic; diffuse	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Epithelial; diffuse	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	1	0	0	0	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0	0	0	0

1 [c - Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
kidney (Continued...)						
pelvic; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; multifocal	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	1	0
bilateral; Nephropathy, Chronic Progressive; multifocal	2	3	3	4	1	6
.... very slight	1	1	1	1	0	2
.... slight	0	1	0	2	1	2
.... moderate	0	1	2	0	0	1
.... severe	1	0	0	0	0	1
.... very severe	0	0	0	1	0	0
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion	0	0	0	0	0	1
spleen						
Examined	1	1	3	3	2	3
Hemangioma; benign	1	0	0	0	0	0
Hemangioma; benign, probably fatal	0	0	0	0	1	0
Autolysis; diffuse	0	0	0	1	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0	1	0	0
Congestion; diffuse	0	0	2	0	0	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
spleen (Continued...)						
.... slight	0	0	2	0	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	0	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0	0	0	0
Degeneration; diffuse	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... severe	0	0	0	0	0	1
Extramedullary Hematopoiesis; diffuse	0	1	1	1	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0	0	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	1	0	0	0
.... severe	0	1	0	1	0	0
Infiltrated By Histiocytic Sarcoma Cells	0	0	0	0	1	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0	1	0	0
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion	0	0	0	1	0	0
thymus						
Examined	1	0	1	1	0	0
Thymoma, [B]; benign	0		1	0		
Thymoma, [M]; malignant	1		0	0		
Autolysis; diffuse	0		0	0		
.... severe	0		0	0		

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
thymus (Continued...)						
Congestion; multifocal	0		0	0		
.... moderate	0		0	0		
Involution, Physiological; diffuse	0		0	1		
.... severe	0		0	1		
hematopoietic tissue						
Examined	0	0	0	1	1	0
Lymphoma, [M]; malignant				1	0	
Sarcoma, Histiocytic; malignant				0	1	
stomach, glandular						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	0
Adenocarcinoma; malignant						
mural; Inflammation; ulcerated, diffuse						
.... slight						
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion						
stomach, nonglandular						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	1
Hyperplasia, Squamous Cell; focal						0
.... moderate						0
Hyperplasia, Squamous Cell; multifocal						1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
stomach, nonglandular (Continued...)						
.... slight						1
Hyperplasia, Squamous Cell; diffuse						0
.... very slight						0
mural; Inflammation; ulcerated, diffuse						1
.... slight						0
.... moderate						1
mural; Inflammation; focal						0
.... moderate						0
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion						0
pancreas						
Examined	1	0	0	0	0	0
Pheochromocytoma, Complex, [B]; benign	0					
Dilatation, Ductal; focal	1					
.... moderate	1					
abdominal cavity						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	1
Fibrosarcoma; malignant						1
Mesothelioma, [M]; malignant						0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
tooth						
Examined	1	3	1	4	4	1
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	1	3	1	4	2	1
.... very slight	0	0	0	0	1	0
.... slight	1	2	1	4	1	1
.... moderate	0	1	0	0	0	0
bilateral; Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	0	0	0	0	2	0
.... slight	0	0	0	0	2	0
oral cavity						
Examined	1	0	0	0	0	0
Carcinoma, Adenosquamous; malignant	1					
eye						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	0
retinal; Atrophy; diffuse						
.... slight						
corneal; right; Inflammation; focal						
.... severe						
esophagus						
Examined	0	0	0	1	0	0
Dilatation; diffuse				1		

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male					
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0
esophagus (Continued...)						
.... moderate				1		
lymph node, mandibular						
Examined	0	0	0	1	1	0
Autolysis; diffuse				1	0	
.... severe				1	0	
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid; diffuse				0	1	
.... very slight				0	1	
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells				1	0	
lymph node, mesenteric						
Examined	0	0	0	1	0	0
Hemangiosarcoma; malignant				1		
lymph node, mediastinal						
Examined	0	1	4	0	1	0
Hemangiosarcoma; malignant		0	0		1	
Resorption; blood, diffuse		1	4		0	
.... very slight		1	0		0	
.... slight		0	4		0	
jejunum						
Examined	0	0	0	0	0	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male						
	Clean air control	brake dust low	Brake dust mid	Brake dust high	Titanium-dioxide	Chrysotile low	
Number of Animals:	31	31	31	31	31	31	
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0	0	0	0	
jejunum (Continued...)							
Leiomyosarcoma; malignant							1
preputial gland							
Examined	1	0	0	0	0	0	
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	1						
.... moderate	1						

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung			
Examined	31	31	31
Adenocarcinoma; malignant	0	0	1
Adenoma, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; benign	0	1	4
Adenoma, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; with atypia, benign	0	1	1
Carcinoma, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; malignant	0	3	3
alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	0	29 ¹	29 ¹
.... very slight	0	21 ⁺	18 ⁺
.... slight	0	8 ⁺	11 ⁺
alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	22 ¹	0	0
.... very slight	22 ¹	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Autolysis; diffuse	5	5	2
.... slight	0	2	1
.... moderate	5	2	1
.... severe	0	1	0
Congestion; diffuse	4	0	0
.... slight	2	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ccc - Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... moderate	1	0	0
.... severe	1	0	0
alveolar; Edema; multifocal	1	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0
interstitial; Fibrosis; focal	1	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0
interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal	0	29 ¹	29 ¹
.... very slight	0	16 ⁺	9 ⁺
.... slight	0	13 ⁺	20 ⁺
pleural; Fibrosis; focal	0	2	4
.... very slight	0	1	2
.... slight	0	1	2
pleural; Fibrosis; multifocal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal	0	26 ¹	27 ¹
.... very slight	0	26 ¹	27 ¹
Granuloma, Cholesterol; focal	3	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

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Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... slight	2	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
Granuloma, Cholesterol; multifocal	2	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0
alveolar; Hemorrhage; chronic, focal	0	1	0
.... slight	0	1	0
alveolar; Hemorrhage; chronic, multifocal	0	0	2
.... very slight	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
alveolar; Hemorrhage; multifocal	0	1	0
.... moderate	0	1	0
alveolar; Hemorrhage; acute, focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
pleural; Hyperplasia; focal	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0
pleural; Hyperplasia; multifocal	1	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
balt; Hyperplasia; lymphoid, focal	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; focal	5	0	0
.... very slight	5	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal	15 ¹	30 ¹	30 ¹
.... very slight	13 ⁺	4	3
.... slight	2	20 ⁺	12 ⁺
.... moderate	0	6 ^{f+}	15 ⁺
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type, focal	5	7	6
.... very slight	1	2	1
.... slight	2	3	3
.... moderate	2	1	1
.... severe	0	1	1
.... very severe	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type, multifocal	2	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0

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Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... moderate	1	1	0
Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type with atypia, focal	1	4	3
.... moderate	0	3	0
.... severe	1	0	2
.... very severe	0	1	1
Hyperplasia, Mesothelial; focal	0	3	1
.... very slight	0	3	0
.... slight	0	0	1
Hyperplasia, Mesothelial; multifocal	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
Hyperplasia, Neuroendocrine Cell; focal	1	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0
alveolar; Infiltration, Granulocytic Cell; multifocal	1	0	1
.... slight	1	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	10 ¹	11 ¹
.... very slight	0	10 ¹	10 ¹
.... slight	0	0	1
perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	10 ¹	12 ¹
.... very slight	0	10 ¹	12 ¹
pleural; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0
pleural; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0
alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	1	27 ⁺	28 ⁺
.... very slight	0	24 ⁺	24 ⁺
.... slight	1	3	4
interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	2	0	1

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

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Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... very slight	2	0	1
interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	8	0 ¹	2
.... very slight	8	0 ^{f+}	0 ^{f+}
.... slight	0	0	2
perivascular; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
perivascular; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	0	1	3
.... very slight	0	1	1
.... slight	0	0	2
pleural; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	3	2	1
.... very slight	3	2	1
pleural; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	0	0	2
.... very slight	0	0	2
Inflammation, Acute; focal	1	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0
Inflammation, Acute; multifocal	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [ff - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.01]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... severe	0	0	1
Inflammation, Chronic; focal	3	1	0
.... very slight	2	1	0
.... slight	1	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic; multifocal	10	1 ¹	3 ^{c+}
.... very slight	8	0	3
.... slight	2	1	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	1	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; multifocal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
pleural; Inflammation, Chronic Active; multifocal	1	0	0
.... moderate	1	0	0
Lipoproteinosis, Alveolar; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Lipoproteinosis, Alveolar; multifocal	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0

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Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... severe	0	1	0
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; focal	0	3	0
.... very slight	0	2	0
.... slight	0	1	0
Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; multifocal	18	9 ¹	10 ⁺
.... very slight	8	6	3 ⁺
.... slight	10	3	7
.... moderate	0	0	0
Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous; focal	2	1	0
.... very slight	1	1	0
.... slight	1	0	0
Metaplasia, Chondro-Osseous; multifocal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Metaplasia, Fibro-Osseous; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Metastasis/-Es From Primary In Adrenal	0	0	1
.... present, no grade	0	0	1
Metastasis/-Es From Primary In Liver	0	0	1

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Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
.... present, no grade	0	0	1
Metastasis/-Es From Primary In Thyroid; focal	0	0	0
.... present, no grade	0	0	0
Metastasis/-Es From Primary In Thyroid; multifocal	0	0	0
.... present, no grade	0	0	0
Microgranuloma; multifocal	0	21 ¹	24 ¹
.... very slight	0	21 ¹	24 ¹
Wagner Grade 2	14 ¹	0	0
Wagner Grade 3	12 ⁺	0	0
Wagner Grade 4	1	31 ¹	31 ¹
Wagner Grade 1	4 ¹	0 ¹	0 ¹
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal	2	0	0
.... very slight	2	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal	0	4	5
.... very slight	0	4	5

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Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung (Continued...)			
Metastasis-/Es From Primary Site Unknown	0	0	0
.... present, no grade	0	0	0
Adhesion To Thoracic Wall; focal	0	0	1
lung associated lymph nodes (laln)			
Examined	28	29	30
No Visible Lesions	19	11	17
Not Examined: No Significant Tissue Present In Section	2	2	1
Not Examined: Tissue Not Taken At Necropsy	1	0	0
Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	0	16 ¹	11 ¹
.... very slight	0	8 ⁺	11 ¹
.... slight	0	8 ⁺	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; focal	1	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0
Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	5	0	0
.... very slight	5	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Autolysis; diffuse	2	2	0
.... slight	0	0	0

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Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
lung associated lymph nodes (ln) (Continued...)			
.... moderate	2	2	0
.... severe	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid; diffuse	0	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	1
Infiltrated By Histiocytic Sarcoma Cells	0	0	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; plasmacytic, multifocal	1	0	0
.... slight	1	0	0
Resorption; blood, diffuse	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
larynx			
Examined	29	31	31
No Visible Lesions	20	22	21
Not Examined: Tissue Not Taken At Necropsy	2	0	0
Autolysis; diffuse	3	1	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
.... slight	1	0	0
.... moderate	2	1	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
larynx (Continued...)			
.... severe	0	0	0
Dilatation, Submucosal Glands; focal	0	1	3
.... very slight	0	1	2
.... slight	0	0	1
Erosion; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Epithelial; focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	1	0	1
.... very slight	1	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	1	1	2
.... very slight	0	0	1
.... slight	1	1	1
subepithelial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	4	4	3
.... very slight	3	3	2
.... slight	1	1	1
.... moderate	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
larynx (Continued...)			
subepithelial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	1	2	1
.... very slight	1	2	0
.... slight	0	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	0
Inflammation; chronic, focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
nasal cavity			
Examined	31	30	31
No Visible Lesions	14	20	17
Not Examined: Autolysis Precludes Diagnosis	0	1	0
Autolysis; diffuse	5	2	0
.... slight	3	0	0
.... moderate	2	2	0
olfactory epithelial; Droplets, Hyaline; multifocal	13	7	12
.... very slight	6	1	1
.... slight	2	2	2
.... moderate	3	3	6
.... severe	2	1	3

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
nasal cavity (Continued...)			
respiratory epithelial; Droplets, Hyaline; multifocal	4	4	9
.... very slight	3	1	7
.... slight	1	1	2
.... moderate	0	1	0
.... severe	0	1	0
Hyperplasia, Mucous Cell; focal	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0
Hyperplasia, Respiratory Epithelial; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Infiltrated By Tumour Cells	1	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	1	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	0	0	2

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
nasal cavity (Continued...)			
.... very slight	0	0	2
Inflammation; purulent, multifocal	0	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	1
Hyperplasia, Nalt; focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
nasopharynx			
Examined	31	31	31
No Visible Lesions	30	29	30
Autolysis; diffuse	1	2	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	2	0
.... moderate	1	0	0
Metastasis/-Es From Primary In Skin	0	0	1
.... present, no grade	0	0	1
trachea			
Examined	31	31	31
No Visible Lesions	24	28	26
Autolysis; diffuse	5	3	2

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido-lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
trachea (Continued...)			
.... slight	0	1	0
.... moderate	4	1	2
.... severe	1	1	0
subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
subepithelial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	2	0	2
.... very slight	2	0	2
diaphragm			
Examined	29	29	29
No Visible Lesions	26	25	26
Autolysis; diffuse	2	1	1
.... slight	2	0	1
.... moderate	0	1	0
Hyperplasia; focal	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
Infiltrated By Histiocytic Sarcoma Cells	0	0	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; mixed, focal	0	1	1
.... very slight	0	1	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
diaphragm (Continued...)			
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; mixed, multifocal	0	2	0
.... very slight	0	2	0
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
Inflammation, Chronic Active; multifocal	1	0	0
.... moderate	1	0	0
liver			
Examined	8	16	10
Adenoma, Hepatocellular; benign	0	1	1
Carcinoma, Hepatocellular; malignant with metastasis	0	0	1
Carcinoma, Hepatocellular; malignant	0	0	0
Angiectasis; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
Angiectasis; multifocal	5 f ¹	12 +	4

+ [Footnote is displayed in the Comments and Markers page]

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
liver (Continued...)			
.... very slight	0	4	0
.... slight	5 f ¹	8	4
Autolysis; diffuse	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0
Change, Fatty; focal	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
Change, Fatty; multifocal	7 f ¹	5	3
.... very slight	6	2	1
.... slight	1	3	1
.... moderate	0	0	1
Change, Fatty; diffuse	0	1	0
.... slight	0	1	0
Cyst(S); blood-stained, focal	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0
Cyst(S); focal	0	0	3
.... slight	0	0	2
.... moderate	0	0	1
Degeneration, Cystic; focal	0	0	0

1 [f - Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05]

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
liver (Continued...)			
.... slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bile Duct; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Bile Duct; multifocal	2	1	0
.... very slight	2	0	0
.... slight	0	1	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells	0	0	0
periportal; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; mixed, multifocal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
periportal; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
periportal; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	1	1	0
.... very slight	1	1	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	1	0	0
.... very slight	1	0	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal	3	1	0
.... very slight	3	1	0
.... slight	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
liver (Continued...)			
Necrosis, Hepatocellular; focal	0	1	0
.... very slight	0	1	0
Necrosis, Hepatocellular; multifocal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
Nodule, Hepatodiaphragmatic; focal	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0
Pigmentation; multifocal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Focus Of Cellular Alteration, Clear Cell; focal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
Focus Of Cellular Alteration, Tigroid; focal	2	3	1
.... very slight	0	1	0
.... slight	1	2	1
.... moderate	1	0	0
Focus Of Cellular Alteration, Tigroid; multifocal	3	1	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	1	1	0
.... moderate	2	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
liver (Continued...)			
Focus Of Cellular Alteration, Basophilic Nos; focal	0	3	1
.... slight	0	1	1
.... moderate	0	1	0
.... severe	0	1	0
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion	0	0	0
Cyst, Bile Duct; focal	0	1	0
.... moderate	0	1	0
skin/subcutaneous tissue			
Examined	4	7	3
Adenoma, Sebaceous Cell; benign	1	0	0
Carcinoma, Sebaceous Cell; malignant	0	1	1
Carcinoma, Squamous Cell; malignant	0	0	1
Fibroma; benign	1	0	1
Fibrosarcoma; malignant	1	2	1
Hemangiosarcoma; malignant	0	0	0
Keratoacanthoma; benign	0	1	0
Lipoma; benign	0	0	0
Papilloma; benign	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
skin/subcutaneous tissue (Continued...)			
Schwannoma, [M]; malignant	0	0	0
Tumor, Basal Cell, [B]; benign	0	1	0
Tumor, Hair Follicle, [B]; benign	0	1	0
Fibrosarcoma, Pleomorphic; malignant, incidental	0	0	0
subcutaneous; Abscess(Es); focal	0	1	0
.... severe	0	1	0
Cyst(S), Squamous; focal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
.... very severe	0	0	0
Fibrosis, Dermal; focal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0
Granulation Tissue; chronic, focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Epithelial; squamous, focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Epithelial; squamous, multifocal	0	1	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
skin/subcutaneous tissue (Continued...)			
.... moderate	0	1	0
.... severe	0	0	0
Inflammation, Acute; multifocal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; ulcerated, focal	1	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
.... severe	1	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; ulcerated, multifocal	0	1	0
.... moderate	0	1	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
.... very severe	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; multifocal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
pituitary gland			
Examined	6	6	6
No Visible Lesions	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
pituitary gland (Continued...)			
Adenoma, Pars Distalis; benign	3	6	6
Adenoma, Pars Distalis; benign, probably fatal	0	0	0
Adenoma, Pars Distalis; multiple, benign	1	0	0
Carcinoma, Pars Distalis; malignant	1	0	0
Hyperplasia, Pars Distalis; focal	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion	1	0	0
brain			
Examined	2	0	1
Astrocytoma, [M]; malignant, fatal	1		0
Oligodendroglioma, [M]; malignant	0		0
Tumor, Granular Cell, [M]; malignant	0		1
Compression; focal	1		0
.... slight	0		0
.... moderate	0		0
.... severe	1		0
ventricular; Dilatation; diffuse	1		0
.... slight	0		0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
brain (Continued...)			
.... moderate	1		0
Infiltrated By Tumour Cells; focal	1		0
.... present, no grade	1		0
thyroid gland			
Examined	2	2	1
No Visible Lesions	0	1	0
Adenoma, C-Cell; benign	0	0	0
Adenoma, Follicular Cell; benign	0	0	1
Adenoma, Follicular Cell; cystic, benign	0	0	0
Carcinoma, C-Cell; malignant with metastasis	0	0	0
Carcinoma, C-Cell; malignant	1	0	0
Carcinoma, Follicular Cell; malignant	1	0	0
Hyperplasia, C-Cell; diffuse	0	1	0
.... slight	0	1	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Follicular Cell; cystic, focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
thyroid gland (Continued...)			
.... severe	0	0	0
.... very severe	0	0	0
Follicle, Cystic; focal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
Follicle, Cystic; multifocal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
parathyroid gland			
Examined	0	0	0
No Visible Lesions			
Hyperplasia; diffuse			
.... moderate			
adrenal gland			
Examined	0	1	1
Adenoma, Cortical; benign		0	0
Carcinoma, Cortical; malignant with metastasis		0	1
Carcinoma, Cortical; malignant, probably fatal		1	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
adrenal gland (Continued...)			
Pheochromocytoma, [B]; benign		0	0
testis			
Examined	4	3	5
Adenoma, Interstitial (Leydig) Cell; benign	1	1	0
bilateral; Adenoma, Interstitial (Leydig) Cell; benign	1	0	0
Edema; diffuse	1	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	1	0	0
Hyperplasia, Interstitial (Leydig) Cell; diffuse	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
Hypertrophy, Mesothelial; focal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
Spermatocoele, Rete Testis; focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Atrophy, Tubular; diffuse	1	2	4
.... very slight	1	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
testis (Continued...)			
.... moderate	0	0	1
.... severe	0	1	0
.... very severe	0	1	1
unilateral; Atrophy, Tubular; diffuse	0	0	1
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0
epididymis			
Examined	1	1	1
unilateral; Granuloma, Spermatic; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
unilateral; Granuloma, Spermatic; multifocal	0	0	0
.... severe	0	0	0
Spermatocele; focal	0	0	0
.... very severe	0	0	0
Reduced Sperm, Luminal; diffuse	1	1	1
.... very slight	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
epididymis (Continued...)			
.... slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1
.... severe	0	0	0
.... very severe	1	1	0
prostate			
Examined	1	3	6
No Visible Lesions	0	0	0
Atrophy; diffuse	0	2	3
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	2	3
Dilatation; diffuse	0	1	0
.... moderate	0	1	0
Hyperplasia; focal	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1
Hyperplasia; multifocal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
Hyperplasia, Atypical; focal	1	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
prostate (Continued...)			
.... moderate	1	0	0
Inflammation; chronic, multifocal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Inflammation; focal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
Inflammation; multifocal	0	0	3
.... very slight	0	0	2
.... slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	1
seminal vesicles			
Examined	2	3	6
No Visible Lesions	0	0	0
bilateral; Atrophy; diffuse	1	1	5
.... very slight	0	0	1
.... slight	1	1	4
Autolysis; diffuse	2	0	1
.... slight	1	0	1

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
seminal vesicles (Continued...)			
.... moderate	1	0	0
Dilatation; diffuse	0	2	0
.... moderate	0	2	0
Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
bilateral; Inflammation, Necrotizing; multifocal	0	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
kidney			
Examined	6	2	7
Cyst(S); focal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
Dilatation, Pelvic; diffuse	1	0	0
.... slight	0	0	0
.... moderate	1	0	0
Hyperplasia, Epithelial; diffuse	0	0	1
.... moderate	0	0	1
Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	0	0
.... very slight	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
kidney (Continued...)			
pelvic; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
Inflammation, Chronic Active; multifocal	0	0	0
.... moderate	0	0	0
bilateral; Nephropathy, Chronic Progressive; multifocal	6	2	7
.... very slight	3	0	1
.... slight	1	0	2
.... moderate	1	1	2
.... severe	1	1	1
.... very severe	0	0	1
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion	0	0	0
spleen			
Examined	0	2	2
Hemangioma; benign		0	0
Hemangioma; benign, probably fatal		0	0
Autolysis; diffuse		0	0
.... moderate		0	0
Congestion; diffuse		1	2

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
spleen (Continued...)			
.... slight		0	0
.... moderate		1	1
.... severe		0	1
Degeneration; diffuse		0	0
.... severe		0	0
Extramedullary Hematopoiesis; diffuse		2	1
.... slight		1	1
.... moderate		0	0
.... severe		1	0
Infiltrated By Histiocytic Sarcoma Cells		0	0
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells		0	0
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion		0	0
thymus			
Examined	2	1	0
Thymoma, [B]; benign	1	0	
Thymoma, [M]; malignant	0	0	
Autolysis; diffuse	0	1	
.... severe	0	1	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
thymus (Continued...)			
Congestion; multifocal	1	0	
.... moderate	1	0	
Involution, Physiological; diffuse	0	0	
.... severe	0	0	
hematopoietic tissue			
Examined	0	0	0
Lymphoma, [M]; malignant			
Sarcoma, Histiocytic; malignant			
stomach, glandular			
Examined	1	1	1
Adenocarcinoma; malignant	0	1	0
mural; Inflammation; ulcerated, diffuse	0	0	1
.... slight	0	0	1
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion	1	0	0
stomach, nonglandular			
Examined	1	0	3
Hyperplasia, Squamous Cell; focal	0		1
.... moderate	0		1
Hyperplasia, Squamous Cell; multifocal	0		0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
stomach, nonglandular (Continued...)			
.... slight	0		0
Hyperplasia, Squamous Cell; diffuse	0		1
.... very slight	0		1
mural; Inflammation; ulcerated, diffuse	0		1
.... slight	0		1
.... moderate	0		0
mural; Inflammation; focal	0		1
.... moderate	0		1
No Correlation To Macroscopic Lesion	1		0
pancreas			
Examined	0	0	1
Pheochromocytoma, Complex, [B]; benign			1
Dilatation, Ductal; focal			0
.... moderate			0
abdominal cavity			
Examined	0	1	0
Fibrosarcoma; malignant		0	
Mesothelioma, [M]; malignant		1	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocidolite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
tooth			
Examined	2	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	2		
.... very slight	0		
.... slight	1		
.... moderate	1		
bilateral; Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal	0		
.... slight	0		
oral cavity			
Examined	0	0	0
Carcinoma, Adenosquamous; malignant			
eye			
Examined	0	0	1
retinal; Atrophy; diffuse			1
.... slight			1
corneal; right; Inflammation; focal			1
.... severe			1
esophagus			
Examined	0	0	0
Dilatation; diffuse			

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido- lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
esophagus (Continued...)			
.... moderate			
lymph node, mandibular			
Examined	0	0	0
Autolysis; diffuse			
.... severe			
Hyperplasia, Lymphoid; diffuse			
.... very slight			
Infiltrated By Lymphoma/Leukaemic Cells			
lymph node, mesenteric			
Examined	0	0	0
Hemangiosarcoma; malignant			
lymph node, mediastinal			
Examined	0	0	0
Hemangiosarcoma; malignant			
Resorption; blood, diffuse			
.... very slight			
.... slight			
jejunum			
Examined	0	0	0

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Removal Reason: ALL	Male		
	Chrysotile high	Crocido-lite	Amosite
Number of Animals:	31	31	31
Number of Completed Animals:	0	0	0
jejunum (Continued...) Leiomyosarcoma; malignant			
preputial gland Examined	0	0	0
Inflammation, Chronic Active; focal moderate			

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Adenoma, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; benign <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	3	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	5	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	3	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	4	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	5	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Autolysis; diffuse, moderate <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : pleural; Fibrosis; focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal, moderate <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; alveolar type with atypia, focal, moderate <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Mesothelial; focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Hyperplasia, Mesothelial; focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	3	lung : interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	1	lung : interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : pleural; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : pleural; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Inflammation, Chronic; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	4	lung : Inflammation, Chronic; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	5	lung : Inflammation, Chronic; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Inflammation, Chronic; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	lung : Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	5	lung : Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung : Microgranuloma; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	3	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 3 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 4 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	3	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	5	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	6	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages, Balt; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	1	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	4	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	5	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	1	nasal cavity : respiratory epithelial; Droplets, Hyaline; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	nasal cavity : subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	1	nasal cavity : subepithelial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; focal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	c

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	1	liver : Angiectasis; focal	c
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	liver : Angiectasis; multifocal	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	
ALL	Male	1	liver : Angiectasis; multifocal, slight	c
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	liver : Change, Fatty; multifocal	c
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	liver : Change, Fatty; multifocal, very slight	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	1	liver : Cyst(S); focal	c
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	thyroid gland : Adenoma, Follicular Cell; benign	cc
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.01	
ALL	Male	1	seminal vesicles : Dilatation; diffuse	c
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	1	seminal vesicles : Dilatation; diffuse, moderate	c
			<i>Comment:</i> Group Factor Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact: Test: Chi-Squared p < 0.05	
ALL	Male	8	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	
ALL	Male	9	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal	ccc
			<i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	8	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	9	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.01	ff
ALL	Male	9	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	7	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	7	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Accumulation, Particle-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	8	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	9	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	8	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	9	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.01	ff
ALL	Male	8	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : interstitial; Fibrosis; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	9	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	8	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	9	lung : Giant Cells, Syncytial; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	7	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	8	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	7	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	8	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal, moderate <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : Hyperplasia, Bronchiolo-Alveolar; multifocal, moderate <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	9	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	9	lung : peribronchiolar; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	9	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	9	lung : perivascular; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	9	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	8	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	9	lung : alveolar/interstitial; Infiltration, Inflammatory Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	8	lung : interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.01	ff
ALL	Male	8	lung : interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	9	lung : interstitial; Infiltration, Mononuclear Cell; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	lung : Inflammation, Chronic; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	9	lung : Inflammation, Chronic; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.05	c
ALL	Male	8	lung : Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	9	lung : Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.01	cc
ALL	Male	9	lung : Macrophage Aggregation, Alveolar; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.01	cc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	8	lung : Microgranuloma; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	9	lung : Microgranuloma; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	7	lung : Wagner Grade 2 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	7	lung : Wagner Grade 3 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 4 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 4 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	7	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	8	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc
ALL	Male	9	lung : Wagner Grade 1 <i>Comment:</i> Test: Chi-Squared - Pearson 2 Sided p < 0.001	ccc

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Comments and Markers

Removal Reason	Sex	Group	Measurement	Marker
ALL	Male	8	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	9	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.01	ff
ALL	Male	9	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, very slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.001	fff
ALL	Male	8	lung associated lymph nodes (laln) : Accumulation, Fibre-Laden Macrophages; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.01	ff
ALL	Male	7	liver : Angiectasis; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	8	liver : Angiectasis; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.01	ff
ALL	Male	7	liver : Angiectasis; multifocal, slight <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f
ALL	Male	7	liver : Change, Fatty; multifocal <i>Comment:</i> Test: Fisher's Exact 2 Sided p < 0.05	f

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

Key Page

Measurement/Statistics

<u>Measurement</u>	<u>Descriptive</u>	<u>Comparative</u>	<u>Arithmetic/Adjusted</u>	<u>Transformation</u>
Pathology Observation	Count Positives	Chi-Squared & Fisher's Exact		

Group Information

<u>Short Name</u>	<u>Long Name</u>	<u>Report Headings</u>	
1	Clean air	Clean air	control
2	brake dust low	brake dust	low
3	brake dust mid	Brake dust	mid
4	brake dust high	Brake dust	high
5	Particel Control	Titanium-	dioxide
6	Chrysotile low	Chrysotile	low
7	Chrysotile high	Chrysotile	high
8	Crocidolite	Crocido-	lite
9	Amosite	Amosite	

Removal Reason Grouping

<u>Grouping Name</u>	<u>Abbreviation</u>	<u>Removal Reasons</u>
Killed - Terminal Kill	TeKi	Killed - Terminal Kill
Killed - Moribund	US	Killed - Moribund
Found Dead	FD	Found Dead

Pathology - Intergroup Comparison of Pathology Observations

02G16015 - Subchronic (13 week) brake dust inhalation toxicology study
(nose-only) with lifelong follow-up in the rat, 24 months post exposure - all

End Of Print

S-10 Methods for Histopathology and Confocal Microscopy

S-10.1 Tissue preparation for histopathology and confocal microscopy:

In animals assigned for lung histopathology and confocal microscopy (4 rats/group), the lungs and the lower half of the trachea were collected with the attached mediastinal tissue. In addition, the diaphragm was collected for confocal microscopy. Macroscopic abnormalities of the respiratory tract and gross lesions were recorded, and the wet lung weight measured and recorded.

S-10.2 Histopathology:

The left lung lobe of each animal assigned to lung histopathology was fixed in 10% neutral-buffered formalin solution by gentle instillation (via trachea following tying off right mainstem bronchus) under a hydrostatic pressure of 25 cm. In addition, the LALN (lung-associated lymph nodes) were fixed separately. The lung was then immersion-fixed for at least 2 days in formalin similar to the other organs.

The histopathological examination followed the approach as developed in the previous 28 day brake dust study performed at Fraunhofer ITEM using both H&E and Masson's Trichrome stains. The Wagner score¹ was determined (McConnell and Davis, 2002). In addition, a semi-qualitative evaluation of the collagen deposition was performed (McConnell et al, 1999).

For histopathological evaluation, all prepared slides were transferred to Fraunhofer ITEM with appropriate documentation and details of the gross macroscopic findings. Histopathological observations were recorded using the PROVANTIS system (version 8.4.3.1 or higher). Findings were scored using a grading scale of:

- none (0) – no lesion present
- minimal or very slight (1) – lesion covering ~ up to 5 % of the slide
- slight (2) – lesion covering ~ up to 25 % of the slide
- moderate (3) – lesion covering ~ up to 50 % of the slide
- severe (4) – lesion covering ~ 50-75 % of the slide
- and very severe (5) - lesion covering ~ > 75 % of the slide

These are approximate ranges and may vary depending upon the lesion type.

¹ Grade 1 = No lesion observed.

Grade 2 = A few macrophages in the lumen of the terminal bronchioles and alveoli.

Grade 3 = Presence of cuboidal epithelium lining the proximal alveoli (bronchiolization). No collagen but reticulin fibres may be present in the interstitium at the junction of the terminal bronchiole and alveolus. Luminal macrophages are more conspicuous and mononuclear cells may be found in the interstitium.

Grade 4 = Minimal collagen deposition at the level of the terminal bronchiole and alveolus. Increased bronchiolization with associated mucoid debris suggesting glandular pattern.

Grade 5 = Interlobular linking of the lesions described in Grade 4 and increased severity of fibrosis.

Grade 6 = Early consolidation. Parenchymal decrease is apparent.

Grade 7 = Marked fibrosis and consolidation.

Grade 8 = Complete obstruction of most airways.

S-10.3 Confocal microscopy:

The right lung lobes of each animal assigned to lung histopathology/confocal microscopy were fixed in modified Karnovsky fixative made with phosphate buffered saline by gentle instillation under a hydrostatic pressure of 25 cm. The diaphragm was also fixed in modified Karnovsky. The tissues were then immersion-fixed for at least 2 days.

Tissue preparation for lung burden measurements: In the animals assigned for lung burden analysis (4 rats/group), rats were sacrificed, the abdominal cavity was opened, and the diaphragm from the chest wall was excised (scalpel and forceps) at the insertion boundary of the chest wall along the entire circumference of contact between the chest wall and the diaphragm. The entire diaphragm was removed intact avoiding touching the parietal surface and placed in a new clean bottle/vial, capped, sealed, labelled and then quickly deep frozen at -80°C. The upper half of the trachea, the lungs, and the lower half of the trachea were also collected with the attached mediastinal tissue. The mediastinal lymph nodes and the tracheobronchial lymph nodes were resected and immediately inserted into appropriate labelled plastic bags and quickly deep-frozen at -80°C.

The deep-frozen tissue samples were dispatched for freeze drying and low temperature ashing on dry ice to the Inhalation Toxicology & Chemical Risk Assessment department of the Fraunhofer Institute, Hannover, Germany. Following this, Fraunhofer sent the ashed diaphragms to GSA for fiber counting and sizing.

Tissue preparation for confocal / low temperature microscopy: On days 45 and 89 during exposure and at 3, 9, 12 and 18 months post-exposure, 4 animals per group, chestwalls were prepared without delay upon animal termination by injection of at least 150 mg/kg bw. sodium pentobarbital intraperitoneal (i.p.) and exsanguination via peritoneal incision of the liver with care taken not to invade the lung cavity or puncture the diaphragm. A short length of PE 190 tubing was inserted into the trachea proximal to the brachial plexus and secured with silk suture. The chest wall was skinned and separated and was suspended at the neck region and slowly lowered over 1 min into liquid nitrogen with care taken not to submerge the open end of the tracheal tube into the liquid nitrogen. The snap-frozen chest walls were then bagged and numbered for low temporary storage at -80°C. The frozen chest walls were then dispatched packed on dry ice by express courier to Rogers Imaging Corporation (RIC) for processing and analysis. Upon receipt, chestwalls were inventoried and maintained on dry ice. Individual chestwalls were positioned on a dry ice-cooled copper plate cutting platform mounted on a thin-kerf band saw. Beginning at the xyphoid process, sequential cross section chestwall slabs 4 mm thick were cut using a band saw cutting toward the brachial plexus until no lung profile remained. Every cut slab was immediately place on dry ice until positioned in a tissue processing cassette. Cassettes were placed in cryofixation solution containing anhydrous methanol and anhydrous acetone in a mixture of three parts methanol to one part acetone at -80°C, then placed in an ultralow freezer maintained at -80°C. Cryofixation fluid was replaced periodically until no free ice crystals remained. Cassettes were then placed in cryofluid containers maintained at -20°C. Cryofluid was weekly replaced until solution cleared, then cassettes were transferred to anhydrous methanol for two weeks with several changes in methanol, transferred to -4°C, then brought to room temperature in absolute methanol on stir plate. Methanol was replaced with anhydrous methanol containing 0.0001% Lucifer yellow-CH (Electron Microscopy Sciences, Erie, PA) for 48 hours. Stained chestwall slabs were placed in fresh methanol and embedded in Spurr epoxy. Embedded chestwall slabs were

prepared for microscopic analysis by removal of the top 1.5 mm from the block, then the chestwall surface was polished to a glass smooth finish using a diamond lapidary tool. Polished chestwall slabs were then cover-slipped and placed on the microscope stage for examination. The chestwall processing and confocal image collection are described in Bernstein et al. (2018).

S-10.4 Statistical analyses

One-way ANOVA followed by Dunnett's multiple comparisons test was performed using GraphPad Prism version 8.1.2 for Windows, GraphPad Software, San Diego, California USA, www.graphpad.com".

Graphs and summary statistics were prepared using STATISTICA (data analysis software system), TIBCO Software Inc. (2018) <http://tibco.com>.